

**AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING
CUSTOMERS TOWARDS E-BANKING ADOPTION IN THE
NIGERIAN BANKING SECTOR**

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ABSTRACT

The advancement in information technologies is changing the face of offering service in the business environment. Such advances encourage banks to invest in the new technologies (e-banking) to offer up-to-date service that goes beyond traditional service to their customers. Despite huge investments by the Nigeria banks, the level of adoption of e-banking service is still low. This research focuses on the Nigeria Banking Sector by investigating the factors that affect electronic banking (e-banking) adoption in Nigeria using 14 constructs of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) and Demographic related factors. The research taking this approach in developing countries such as Nigeria is scarce. By using the TAM-DIT framework and demographic variables, this thesis therefore aimed to understand the factors influencing banking customers towards the adoption of e-banking products and services. A convergence parallel mixed-method research design was employed, where quantitative and qualitative research approach were blended to achieve the objectives of the research. In the first phase of the study, a survey questionnaire of 176 banks customers of Guaranteed Trust Bank and First City Monument Bank in Nigeria were analysed using T-Test Statistic, Regression and Correlation Analysis. The second part which involves the qualitative study (semi-structured interviews) involving 10 customers of the two banks analysed by thematic content analysis.

The research findings from the mixed-method approach revealed that perceived advantage/perceived usefulness, the complexity of use/perceived ease of use, the cost of e-banking, security and risk were factors that affect customers' attitude to adopt e-banking. Additionally, deficiencies in information technology infrastructure and lack of e-banking regulation policies stand out as factors that hinder e-banking development in Nigeria. The result also found all demographic variables marital status, educational level, occupation, income, religion and culture except gender and age as significant influencing factors determining customers' e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector. Furthermore, ATM, internet banking and mobile banking were found to be the most utilised e-banking channels in Nigeria. These research findings have great implications for banking institutions in terms of formulating effective e-banking strategies. Particularly, it offers insights for banking organisations, practitioners and the Nigerian banks' policy maker (Central Bank of Nigeria) when formulating e-banking adoption strategies. This study contributes to the literature on e-banking practices using TAM-DIT and demographic variables. This is an area where studies have not been sufficiently researched and where there have been limited findings on factors influencing customers' attitude towards e-banking adoption. It also contributes by providing a better understanding of the fragmented findings on factors affecting customers towards e-banking adoption, particularly in response to the calls for research on demographic factors. Moreover, the study contributes by developing a multi-perspective e-banking model that can inform future research and help the wider body of knowledge that inform bank management, bank stakeholders and e-banking practitioners in Nigeria. In addition, it can help to understand the influences that can causes e-banking resistance in Nigeria and other developing countries. Finally, it provides e-banking adoption strategies that can help boost the level of e-banking usage in the country.

DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is entirely my work, the content has been appropriately referenced where necessary and has not been previously submitted to any institution of learning for any qualification or degree.

DEDICATION

To God be the glory, this thesis is dedicated to my lovely husband, who has been my source of finance and strength for this programme. My father, the late Alhaji Akanji Olawale Odutolu Lawal and my mother Alhaja Fausat Apinke Odutolu Lawal who laid the foundation of education in my life and my entire family who has stood by me throughout this DBA journey.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
ATM	Automated Teller Banking
B2B	Business to Business
CA	Correlation Analysis
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CPMM	Convergent Parallel Mixed Methods
DBA	Doctor of Business Administration
DIT	Diffusion of innovation theory
E-banking	Electronic Banking
EFT	Electronic Fund Transfer
E-world	Electronic world
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
FCMB	First City Monument Bank
GTB	Guaranteed Trust Bank
ICT	Information communication technology
IT	Information Technologies
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test
M-banking	Mobile Banking
NBS	Nigeria Banking Sector
NCC	Nigeria Communication corporation
PA	Perceived Advantage
PCOU	Perceived complexity of use
PESTEL	Political Economic Socio Technology Legal
POS	Pont of Sales
PU	Perceived Usefulness
STVM	Strategic Value Management
SIA	Strategy into Action
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Scientist
SQ	Service Quality
TAM	Technology acceptance model
UWS	University of West of Scotland

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CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Globalization, development in innovation technologies and competition in various economies' financial system have reshaped the banking industry and brought a complete paradigm shift to the traditional banking services globally (Orji *et al.* 2018; Johnson, 2005). The explosive development in the Information Communication Technologies have caused economic integration, removed digital barriers and changed the way business is conducted (Oyewole *et al.* 2013), especially in electronic banking as it impacts customers' need and expectation (Cajetan and Patrick 2017). The ICT growth and the changing customer needs have caused an intense restructuring of the banking industry and significant changes in banking services and strategies (Loonamand O'Loughlin, 2008), made banks to introduce sophisticated products, to increase their markets and geographical coverage (Wisdom, 2012). According to Hoehle, *et al.* (2012), the proliferation of these new ICTs such as internet, touch-dial mobile banking has changed the ways banks serve their customers (Hoehle, *et al.* 2012). This technology has turned banking service to e-world (Stephen, 2011), rebrand the face of the banking industry and brought new standards to banks' services and their production process (Frame and White, 2014). Banks in Nigeria are no exception to these ICT growths, have deployed innovation technologies to strengthen their facilities, tailored their services and automated their operations since after the recapitalization and consolidation exercises to meet their ever-changing customers' needs (Orji *et al.* 2018).

Specifically, electronic banking (e-banking); the use of technology to communicate instructions and receive information from a financial institution where accounts are held via the internet, automated teller machine and mobile has become the main method of marketing multi-channel services to customers and challenging the traditional banking models (Cortiñas *et al.*, 2010). As this EB (e.g. internet banking, mobile banking, electronic fund transfer) is substantially reshaping the financial service industry (Weill and Woerner, 2015). The introduction is forcing banks to refine their bank strategies to capture and retain their customers as customer expectation increases (Monferrer-Tirado *et al.*, 2016). This paradigm shift has led to a situation where traditional banking system needs to change to satisfy the changing demands of their customers while needs to cope with the effects of the technology infusion propelling the changes (Deloitte, 2015).

In particular, the advent of EB has experienced tremendous growth, transformed the core of the banking business and has changed the conventional/traditional financial services operating system/practices dominated by offline employee-oriented services (Yooseock, 2019). This EB has transformed the Nigeria banking practice, commercial banks' huge investment in telecommunication networks and various e-banking services can be seen as an effort towards measuring up with the global standard. Currently, EB in Nigeria has changed service delivery system for the customers in the banking sector. No doubt, numerous benefits are related to customers and banks adopting e-banking innovations such as increasing service quality for both the bank and their customers, saving cost and increases bank revenues, speedy delivery, safety, convenience and increases competition among banks (Chandio *et al* 2013; Onodugo 2015), and others.

Despite the e-banking stated benefits the adoption and diffusion of e-banking in less developed countries are still far from uniform compared to the developed worlds (Inegbedion 2018; Dobindga, 2013). Indeed, the adoption of e-banking in less developed countries cannot be said to be adequate after several years of introducing e-banking services (Kariyawasam and Jayasiri 2016; Inegbedion, 2018). There appears to be a gap between the banks and their clients in the adoption of e-banking services. Recent studies by scholars such as Inegbedion *et. al.* (2019); Agwu (2017); Agu, Simon and Onwuka (2016); Tarhini, *et al.* (2015); Bojuwon (2015) confirmed the low adoption levels of e-banking channels. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the factors affecting or restraining customers from adopting e-banking in Nigeria.

Several researches have been carried out on factors inhibiting e-banking adoption and acceptance in a global context and in Nigeria domain. However, most of these studies in the banking industries have been conducted mostly in advanced countries (Gill, Bunker, and Seltsikas 2015; Mbama and Ezepue 2017). This area is underrepresented and not sufficiently researched in the emerging economies such as Nigeria where banks are trying to improve their e-banking system to better banks operations, reduce their costs and increase efficiency (Inegbedion, *et al.* 2019). Agwu (2017) claimed that studies on e-banking in Nigeria are limited and further argued that customers' adoption of e-banking innovation service is crucial for the development of the Nigeria banking sector. E-banking is unarguably under-researched and needs further research (Olawepo 2013). Thus, the current study attempts to contribute to the research gap by focusing on the banking sector of an emerging economy such as Nigeria and closes this gap with an empirical investigation of the factors affecting e-banking in Nigeria.

Furthermore, most of the previous studies examined e-banking using Technology Acceptance (TAM) or Diffusion of Innovation Theory factors to study e-banking excluding demographic factors to uncover the factors inhibiting e-banking adoption. Moreover, some of the previous studies conducted in Nigeria focused on e-banking acceptance and service quality (Awara and Anyadighibe 2014; Agwu 2017); e-banking adoption and consumer behaviour (Abubakar and Rosmaini 2012; Tarhini, *et al.* 2015; Agwu 2017); attitude and exposure to e-banking can facilitate uptake (Inegbedion 2019; Bojuwon 2015). However, no single study in Nigeria has studied EB holistically in conjunction with Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) especially after the 2004 consolidation and recapitalization exercise in Nigeria. This suggests the need to explore factors affecting customers' e-banking adoption in Nigeria as similar studies carried out in the country of study have not adopted this approach. Therefore, this research fills the need for a composite understanding of the factors affecting e-banking uptake in Nigeria adopting the TAM and DIT models as this area has not been fully explored in literature. Furthermore, there is a need for an in-depth understanding of the factors influencing customer behavioural intention to adopt e-banking in Nigeria and to promote e-banking adoption.

1.2 Problem Statement

Banking organizations worldwide are rapidly changing to electronic-based service delivery, thus changing the way service is rendered to customers. Nigeria banks are no exception, they have invested heavily in innovative (new) technologies and increasingly deploying various e-banking services for convenient banking (Oginni, Omoyele and Ogunwole 2013)

Despite efforts to develop easier available banking services in Nigeria, e-banking remains largely unnoticed by customers with low adoption rates reported (Asikhia, 2011; Yaqub *et al.*, 2013; Asiegbu, Nwakanma and Etus 2015; Tarhini *et al.* 2016) thus confirming Ezeoha's (2005) view that traditional branch banking is preferred in Africa, particularly in Nigeria. To some extent, this reflects a country that was not known for innovations in banking, mainly because there were few banks experiencing little competition (Awara and Anyadighibe, 2014). However, a changing and competitive operating environment has led to increasing investment in new technologies, to provide both e-banking services and to generate insights into customer behaviour (Oginni, Omoyele and Ogunwole 2013). Tarhini, *et al.* (2016), noted little research about e-banking adoption in Nigeria and suggested further study focusing on both culture and religion as significant influencers in behaviour. Their suggestion and the proposal by

Themistocleus *et al* (2015) for developing a framework of influences and perspectives therefore informs the present research.

1.3 Rationale for the Study

Despite the economic significance of banking to Nigeria's GDP (any source for this? research about e-banking adoption is scant (Inegbedion *et. al.* 2019; Agwu 2014). Pioneering scholars investigating e-banking adoption also have their limitations. Small sample sizes, an absence of inclusion of cultural and religious influences reveal the need for further study (Tarhini, *et al.* 2015; Agwu, 2017; Inegbedion, 2019). So, by adopting a convergent parallel mixed method approach to this investigation, influential demographic and non-demographic factors are explored.

The necessity for change in customer banking behaviour is clearly driven by advances in technological capability and is a topic of interest for the author who for some time, has been both a participating customer and researcher. As a Nigerian national, studying the volatility of Nigerian stock prices peaked interest and prompted focus on e-banking.

In sum, personal experience and observation regarding internet banking raised the curiosity and the motivation to investigate e-banking focusing on the Nigerian banking sector. Specifically, the lack of sufficient studies on e-banking in the Nigerian context initiated the zeal in conducting this study. The study contributes and fills existing gaps in the literature related to E-banking and focuses mainly on the e-banking channels (internet banking, mobile banking, ATM, EFT and Mobile banking) considered the core e-banking channels in Nigeria and a wide range of demographics factors. The research aim is discussed in the next section

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

1.4.1 Research Aim

Based on the discussion above, the main research aim is to investigate the factors affecting customers towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector and provide recommendations to promote e-banking adoption.

1.4.2 Research Objectives

In order to achieve the main research aim, the following objectives were formulated from the research problem;

1. To qualitatively ascertain the influences affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria.

2. To investigate the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria using mixed-method.
3. To ascertain the bank customers most patronised e-banking channels in Nigeria.
4. To develop an e-banking model that can help inform the recommendations on future e-banking adoption strategies.

1.5 Research Questions

The following research questions were generated from the study research objectives;

- What are the influences affecting the development of e-banking adoption in Nigeria?
- What factors are currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector?
- What are the customers most patronized e-banking channels in Nigeria?
- How can the e-banking adoption rate be improved in the Nigerian banking sector?

1.6 Scope of the Research

The research was limited in scope to only customers of two commercial banks in Nigeria: Guaranteed Trust Bank and First City Monument Bank. Conversely, data was collected through survey questionnaires and interviews in Lagos and Ogun Nigeria in May 2019. The participants were banks customers who are users of e-banking products and services in Nigeria.

1.7 Significance of the Research

This research is considered significantly important for the Nigeria's economy as it aims to investigate the factors that influence e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector. Understanding the factors may help in enhancing e-banking uptake continual usage. In addition, it will contribute to the scanty literature on e-banking in Nigeria and finding of this study will help reveal useful information that can help the Nigeria banking practitioners to improve and better their e-banking services. Moreover, the research recommendations will assist in formulating effective policies that can promote e-banking adoption. Overall, having better insights of the influencing factors that affect e-banking adoption should help in understating future emerging technologies in developing countries, particularly in the Nigeria banking sector.

1.8 Contributions to Knowledge

This research provides a significant contribution to e-banking literature by identifying and filling an existing gap in the literature, by addressing e-banking issues in entirety without exclusion in Nigeria and the less developed countries where to the best of the researcher no single study of this nature has been conducted; and studying the impact on the customer

satisfaction. Moreover, this study contributes generally to the body of knowledge by examining e-banking adoption levels in Nigeria banks building on the limitations identified by previous researchers. In general, this thesis contributes to the theory and practice of electronic banking by investigating e-banking development, strategies and challenges within the Nigeria context using the TAM and DIT as the theoretical framework. In all, this section briefly highlighted the contributions of the thesis and the conclusion chapter detailed the overall contributions of this research.

1.9 Brief Description of the Research Methodology

The research study was conducted using the pragmatist philosophical approach and employed a mixed-method strategy. The Pragmatism philosophy approach believes that a research philosophy should be view as a continuum and not an option that stands in opposite positions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015). Particularly, a mixed methodological approach of the pragmatist was adopted because is the most suitable philosophical approach for the study on exploration of e-banking adoption. The positivist approach was not chosen as the topic under investigation cannot fit into the methodological stance of the positivist. The mixed-method approach provides the researcher opportunity to examine the perception of individual banks customers on the subject matter using the Convergent Parallel Mixed Methods. The Convergent Parallel Mixed was adopted because the method gives room for an empirical investigation of this nature using the survey questionnaire and in-depth interview for bank customers who are e-banking users.

The study used both deductive and inductive approach to investigate the research topic. The deductive approach gives room for theory and hypothesis development. The inductive approach enables data to be collected and theory to be developed due to data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015). Overall, the study used deductive for the positivism (quantitative) and inductive for the interpretivism (qualitative) data.

The research strategies used for the study include various data collection and data analysis methods. Survey strategies was adopted for the research. The survey strategy was adopted because it appears most suitable for exploratory and descriptive research of this nature; suitable for answering the research questions of the study; suitable for quantitative data and help to provide the study with understanding the perception of the individual bank customers.

However, the mixed-method design was also adopted for the research as it seems more appropriate for exploratory and descriptive research of this nature; can provide a suitable answer to the interview questions of the study and help the researcher to gain an in-depth

understanding of the research area. A mixed-method enables holistic view of the processes involved and the realization of the research topic (Yin, 2011), and particularly regarded as a more appropriate approach for the banking sector (Eckert *et. al.* 2009). The need for rich empirical data related to factors affecting e-banking uptake suggests that a mixed-method approach is appropriate since it allows in-depth examination (Basias, Themistocleous and Morabito, 2015).

This research used a random and purposely sampling technique to select two banks from the current 22 commercial banks in Nigeria; First City Monument Bank (FCMB) and Guaranteed Trust Bank (GTB), these banks are new generations banks. The research study collected data through primary sources using well-structured questionnaires and through a face-to-face interview to gain better insights into the factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria from the participants. Data analysis was conducted through the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS) for the quantitative part and the qualitative data analysis was analysed using a content analysis approach as recommended by Powell-Taylo and Renner (2003).

1.10 Structure of the Thesis

The structure of the thesis was informed by the conceptual map which was informed by the research aims/questions and serves as the roadmap to the thesis. The thesis contains seven chapters (see figure 7.1).

Chapter One provides the background of the study and presents the problem statement, including the research aims and objectives. A rationale and justification for the research is included demonstrating the scope and detail of the significance of the study.

Chapter Two discusses e-banking in global and Nigeria contexts and provides a critical analysis of the relevant studies on e-banking adoption. Necessary descriptions of the various electronic channels, the trend performance of e-banking channels in Nigeria and the factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria are explored. An empirical review, conceptual frameworks, including the theories used to investigate e-banking adoption in the Nigeria context are revealed and are supplemented by relevant customer relationship management content in relation to e-banking.

Chapter Three relates the details of the research methodology, design and research philosophy adopted for the study including the rationale for the choice of pragmatism. Also, the chapter provides information about the research approach, research strategy and the choice of mixed method. Furthermore, data sources are identified, data collection techniques employed are

described comprising the survey questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. Importantly, research ethics, accessibility and participation rates including the pilot study conducted for the research are explained. The final part of the chapter provides thorough discussion regarding the sampling technique, data analysis process and limitation of the study.

Chapter Four presents general background into Nigerian banking by providing an overview of the country including a background review of the Nigeria banking industry structure and the various reforms that led to the development of e-banking. Furthermore, a critical examination of the Nigeria banking environment is presented using PESTEL analysis. The chapter concludes by providing justification for the choice of banks for study and comparatives of the E-banking practice in GTB and FCMB Banks.

Chapter Five focuses on the analysis and results of the quantitative and qualitative parts of the study. The chapter includes analysis of data survey questionnaire where descriptive and statistical tests such as T-test, validity including KMO and Bartlett's Test, reliability test through Cronbach's Alpha; and Person Product-Monument Coefficient analysis are used to test the constructs of the research questions. Furthermore, the chapter also details the interviews data analysis and the findings generated from the data using Thematic network analysis approach. A comparative analysis of quantitative and qualitative findings is equally discussed, and a reversed e-banking adoption model developed.

Chapter Six elaborates on the key findings of the study in relation to the research objectives and questions. In addition, it presents the summary of the principal findings generated from the quantitative and qualitative study and highlights the most patronised e-banking channels in Nigeria based on the geographical locations of the banks chosen.

Chapter Seven concludes the thesis by returning to the aim and objectives and what has been achieved. There is a summary of research findings and detail of theoretical, methodological and practical contributions. Moreover, the chapter discusses the research implications for practitioners and policy makers highlighting limitations and future research direction.

Figure 1.1: Roadmap of the Thesis

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

The preceding chapter provided a detailed view of the background of the study and clearly identified the research gap that this research aims to address. This chapter provides a critical review of relevant literature in the area of e-banking informing the understanding of the subject matter. This chapter is structured into seven main sections as follows:

- section 2.1 analysis how technology is transforming banking and how this then translates in a Nigerian context covering the areas of electronic banking adoption in Nigeria, the chronological development of e-banking channels in Nigeria, challenges of Electronic banking in Nigeria
- section 2.2 examines the concept of electronic banking covering the areas of e-banking benefits, challenges of electronic banking
- analysis of e-banking adoption leading to the discussion of electronic banking channels/products and services, trend performance of e-banking channels in Nigeria, technology adoption process, factors influencing e-banking adoption including the discussion of psychological factors, sociological factors and economic factors (section 2.3).
- presentation of the empirical review on E-banking adoption in the global context and in Nigeria domain to uncover a wider view of the factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria (section 2.4)
- section 2.5 discusses the theoretical models covering the theories of Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein and 1975); Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen 1985), Technology Acceptance Model and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) to explore the factors influencing behavioural intention of customers to adopt e-banking innovations.
- a discussion of the conceptual framework and the integration of some constructs of TAM and DIT and other factors as major factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria (section 2.5.1).
- analysis of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) covering areas such as customer satisfaction as key determinants of electronic banking, customer satisfaction and e-banking services and dimensions of E-banking services affecting customer satisfaction.
- section 2.7 the last section provides the chapter summary on the development and influences affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

2.1 Technology and Global Banking Transformation

This section presents banking sector transformation through technology- in global context and in Nigeria domain to ascertain the development and influences affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

The rapid digitalization of banking system has reshaped the financial service industry worldwide with new opportunities. This digital transformation (e.g., mobile and internet banking) is substantially transforming the banking industry (Weill and Woerner, 2015), and

has led to a change in the traditional banking system or branch banking to meet the changing demands of customers and at the same time coping with the effects of the technology infusion driving the changes (Deloitte, 2015). Karjaluoto, Jarvenpaa and Kauppi (2009) observed that the emergence of technology in financial institutions has enabled banks to use technology for banking service and use it as the main vehicle of selling their products and services.

The search for sustainable competitive advantages in the financial service industry has made banks to recognise the importance of differentiating themselves from other financial organisations through distribution channels (Agwu, 2012); and this has led to banks developing and using new alternative distribution channels to reach their customers (Rose, *et al.* 2005). For example, the United States of America (USA) in 1981 started online banking service in New York when home banking services with videotext system was offered by four of the major city banks through New TV monitor to access the banking system. Ononuga, (2015) noted that these banking services do not gain popularity because of the commercial failure of video text in US, except in UK where the Prestel system was used and in France where the use of video text was subsidized by the telecom providers.

The developments of IT in the banking sector has been no doubt, transformational and change how banking operations were previously done, opened new markets, new products/services and efficient delivery channels across the globe to fast track customers transactions and communication (Callado-Munoz, *et al.*, 2012; Inegbedion, 2018). However, the advent of this technology has affected core aspect of conventional banking services system dominated by offline services. In fact, ICT has greatly affected branch banking, and the exorbitant costs of establishment and has gradually welcomes the simple, speedy and lower cost banking (eg. Internet banking) mostly in the emerged countries, and now creeping into the emerging countries (Agwu, 2016). Similarly, developments in information technology has threatened political and social boundaries globally and removed the economic barrier between countries, thereby making bank products and services in the form of e-banking available to customers across the globe. Hence, this makes understanding how technology transformation led to the development of e-banking in Nigeria and how e-banking is practice globally important.

According to Driga and Isac (2014), the evolution of e-banking industry started in the early 1970s when banks began to look at e-banking services as an alternative to some of their traditional banking services. In another premise, Agwu (2012) noted that information technology (IT) revolution/transformation in financial industry distribution channels started in the 1980s with the introduction of Automatic Teller Machines (ATM) and the ATM networks, followed by telephone banking, cable television banking, and subsequently the introduction of

Personal Computers (PC) banking in the late 1980s and in the early 1990s. Driga and Isac, (2014) likewise stated that e-banking was first used in New York in 1981, when computer is used for banking services through the phone line, offered by major banks; Citibank, Chase Manhattan. Banks of Scotland in the United Kingdom first adopt and introduce e-banking services in 1983. Figure 2.1 below presents the early e-banking services before transformation to current E-banking.

Fig 2.1: E-banking services before transformation

Source: Driga and Isac (2014, p. 52)

Shannak (2013) stressed that viewing bank statements and online bill payment services were the basic e-banking services covered by the early e-banking. Agwu, (2014) noted that e-banking gain popularity since late 1990s into the beginning of the 21st century. However, Nigeria do not adopt the information technologies early compared to developed countries. The next section discusses e-banking and the Nigeria experience.

2.1.1 E banking: the Nigeria Experience

The emergence of information technology has forced Nigeria banks to change their banking strategies to capture and retain their customers (Monferrer-Tirado, *et al.*, 2016). The Nigerian banks changed their IT strategies by taking revolutionary approach to meet the e-banking needs of their customers and for larger share of the banking market (Agwu, 2017). Specifically, information technologies generally refer to electronic banking gained prominence between 2002 and 2007 in Nigeria (Agwu, 2012; Ononugo 2015), and have since come to stay. In the last few years, Nigerian banks adopted electronic telecommunication networks for delivering value added products and service, and has transformed to automated from manual systems, thereby facilitating the practice of inter-bank/inter-branch banking transactions (Ononuga, 2015). Ononugo (2015) further noted that the first electronic channel in Nigeria conventionally commenced in 1989 by Defunct Generale Bank of Nigeria (SGBN). Table 3 present the chronological development of e-banking in Nigeria, and figure 1 detailed the summary of the e-banking evolution.

According to Sanusi (2002) cited in Dogorawa (2005, p. 2) e-payment products commenced in Nigeria in 1996 when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) granted approval to All States Trust Bank to introduce a closed system electronic purse called ESCA This was followed in February 1997, with the introduction of a similar product called “Paycard”, by Diamond Bank. The card-based e-money products assumed an open platform with the authorisation in February 1998, of Smartcard Nigeria Plc, a company floated by a consortium of 19 banks to produce and manage cards called value card and issued by the member banks.

Table 2.1
Chronological development of core five E-banking distribution channels in Nigeria

Year	Electronic Banking	Literature evidence
1989	Automated Teller Machine (ATMs)	(Acha 2008; Ononuga, <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Agwu 2016; Orji, <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Early 1990’s	Tele-banking	(Acha 2008; Hilili, 2005)
Mid 1990’s	Internet Banking	Agwu 2016;)
1996	Electronic Fund Transfer	(Sanusi 2002; Kehinde 2014)
2001	Mobile Banking	(Acha 2008;)

Note: A visual timeline of e-banking evolution of the core e-banking channels in fig 2.2

Fig 2.2:
E-banking Evolution

Automated Teller Machine (ATMs): ATMs were the first e-banking service in Nigeria. Conventionally introduced as electronic distribution channel in 1989, and National Cash Registers (NCR) for the defunct Societe Generale Bank of Nigeria (SGBN) first used ATM same year. Many Nigerian banks installed the ATM in response to the changing nature of modern banking since the introduction (Onodugo, 2015). Until 2003, some banks began operating their own ATM fleets. Inter Switch, the only shared ATM network in Nigeria began operations same year with five United Bank for Africa and First Bank of Nigeria ATMs (Tope, 2010).

Tele-Banking: Tele-banking was introduced among some bank's corporate customers in the early 1990's. These corporate customers used their bank Intranet services through the dial-up Intranet software to transact business with their banks (Hilili, 2005, p. 70).

Electronic Fund Transfer: EFT was introduced in Nigeria in 1996 with the first electronic payment product known as ESCA followed by electronic money products called pay cards introduced for banking transactions in Nigeria (Sanusi, 2002).

Internet Banking: Commence in mid 1990s when Nigeria banks begun exploring internet technology potentials leading to the introduction to internet banking in Nigeria (Tarhini, *et al.*, 2015). As highlight by Abdulhakeem (2002) cited in Dogorawa (2005, p. 2) "many banks therefore launched their websites between 1998 and 2000 with a view to starting Internet banking. A consortium of more than 20 banks under the auspices of Gemcard Nigeria Limited obtained CBN approval in November 1999 to introduce the 'Smartpay' scheme. The CBN has additionally granted approval to a number of banks to introduce international money transfer products, telephone banking and on-line banking via the internet, though on a limited scale". Subsequently, other sophisticated e-banking products/services were introduced to better financial service delivery and more customers satisfaction. The CBN (2003) reports that Telephone Banking, Personal Computer Banking, Internet Banking, Cards and ATMs are now available in the Nigeria banking system (Kehinde, 2014).

Mobile Banking: Developments at home for example, the introduction of mobile telephone system in the Nigeria market in 2001 and access to personal computers (PC) and internet service enhanced the introduction of mobile banking in the country (Ononuoga, *et. al.* 2015).

2.1.2 Regulatory Challenges of E-banking

The conventional banking system which led to the introduction of electronic banking began in 1952 and the Nigeria banking sector has experienced lots of regulatory and institutional changes since then. The sector was controlled by only five banks of the 89 banks in operation before the 2004 banking sector reformation. Heavy challenges such as fraud and corruption, erosion in public confidence, poor and insufficient capital base, poor asset quality, and multiple branch systems, with a total of 89 bank branches accounting for about 3017 bank branches nationwide as of 2004. To resolve these problems the sector went through recapitalisation and consolidation exercise in 2004 initiated by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), aimed at reducing the number of banks in the country making them much stronger, reliable and to catch up with global developments (Ononugo, 2015; Agwu 2016).

Presently, no specific law regulating electronic banking in Nigeria aside the 2003 electronic guideline (Onodugo, 2015). The regulatory agencies in charge have tried to regulate the rapidly changing e-banking environment in the country with relevant regulations and institutional frameworks eg. Failed Banks (Recovery of Debts) and Malpractices in Banks Decree No.18 of 1994, and the Money Laundering Decree of 1995. However, inappropriate enforcement procedures made these regulations ineffective in checking the financial crimes in the industry. By the late 1990s, following the rise in computer usage and internet in Nigeria, almost all the banking industry regulations such as, Banks and Other Institutions Act of 1991 were lacking sufficient provisions to accept the emerging trend making the banks vulnerable and exposed to various risks such as; transaction, strategic, reputation and foreign exchange risks (Ononuga, 2015).

Nonetheless, the lack of a regulatory framework to regulate electronic banking practice in Nigeria, to protect banks and their customers from internet related risk equally causes slow growth of e-banking in the country. The United State of America (USA), for example, recognised e-banking potentials and the associated risks, thereby requires all banks to obtain a charter based on existing guidelines. USA also made laws governing commercial electronic(e)-transactions such as; the Uniform Commercial Code (UCC) and the Uniform Electronic Transaction Act (UETA). The UETA, ensures that electronic documents and contracts are acceptable as legitimate, and requires banks to report to regulatory authorities their bank websites (Acha, 2008). In United Kingdom (UK), monetary authorities adopted a draft electronic banking guide for supervising electronic banking, as no special law for e-banking. The Electronic Transactions Act 1999 guide e-banking practices and confers legal status of

electronic transactions in Australis (Acha, 2008), although no regulations specifically governing electronic banking in the country (Edghill and Bird 2019).

2.2 Concept of E-Banking (Electronic)

In the previous part, the banking sector transformation through technology- in global context and in Nigeria domain were thoroughly discussed including the regulatory challenges facing the Nigeria banking sector. This section examined the concept of e-banking, its benefits and challenges were thoroughly discussed.

E-banking is a term used for new age banking system (Izoho, *et al.*, 2012, its conceptualisation and definition varies amongst researchers depending on the context and perspective they have written from. Some refers to it as internet banking (Sujana *et al.*, 2009; Anouze and Alamro, 2020). Montazemi and Qahri-Saremi, (2015) and Takieddine and Sun, (2016) described it as online banking. According to some authors, it is mobile or telebanking banking (Alalwan, *et al.*, 2016; Oliveira, *et al.*, 2014; Teo, *et al.*, 2012), while Keivani, *et. al.* (2012) and Zheng and Yonghong, (2005) described it as virtual banking. Daniel, (1999) is of the view that e-banking encompasses different types of services through which bank customers can request information and carry out majority of their banking transactions using personal computers or other intelligent devices. In a recent research, e-banking is regarded as a concept that involves the design, development and implementation of financial services that happens on the internet (Anouze and Alamro, 2020). The term electronic or ‘e-banking’ includes all types of banking activities performed through electronic networks and means different things to different people. It is the most recent delivery channel of banking services which is used for both business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-customer (B2C) transactions (Mohammad, 2009). Keivani, *et. al.* (2012) perceived e-banking as an umbrella term for the process through which bank customers can carry out banking transaction electronically without visiting a brick and mortal organisation.

According to Edit (2008), it is a system through which transactions are done electronically using electronic gadgets like Automated Teller Machine (ATMs), Point of sale (POS) terminals, mobile phones, V-cards etc, handled by e-holders, bank customers and other stakeholders. Idowu (2011) maintained that e-banking is a means of transacting banking business via automated processes and electronic devices such as PCs, telephones, fax machines, card payments and other e-channels. Simply, it is a system of banking with an electronic communication network which permits online processing of the same day credit and debit

transfers of funds between member institutions of a clearing system. Table 2.2 summarizes the various e-banking definitions.

Table 2.2

Definitions of E-banking

Definitions	Literature Evidence
The use of personal computers (PCs), intelligent devices or electronic gadgets	(Daniel, 1999; Edit 2008)
Automated delivery of new and traditional banking products/services through electronic networks	(Singh, 2004; Pedro 2012; Siyanbola, 2013)
Recent delivery channels use for B2C and B2B transactions	(Mohammed, 2009; Pedro, 2012; Euta, 2012)
Provision of bank products and its information through new market space	(Akinyele and Olorunleke 2010; Izogo, <i>et.al.</i> , 2012)
Process through which banking transactions are done electronically without visiting the bank	(Keivani <i>et. al.</i> , 2012; Takieddine and Sun, 2016; Ayo, <i>et., al.</i> 2016)
Electronic Fund Transfer through electronic interactive communication channels	(Federal Trade Commission 2012; Siyanbola, 2013; Stoica, <i>et. al.</i> 2015)
The use of ATM, debit card, credit card with codes or personal identification numbers (PINs)	(Mohammed, 2009; Pedro 2012; Siyanbola, 2013)
An online banking or internet banking	(Elisha, 2010; Akinyele and Olohunke 2010; Izogo, <i>et. al.</i> , 2012; Montazemi and Qahri-Saremi, 2015; Takieddine and Sun, 2016; Anouze and Alamro, 2020)

According to the Federal Trade Commission (2012, p.1), “Electronic banking also known as an Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT), is the use of computer and electronic technology in place of checks and other paper transactions”. Electronic banking can be considered as a variety of the following platforms: internet banking (or online banking), telephone banking, TV-based banking, mobile phone banking and e-banking (or offline banking). Mohammed, (2009) mentioned that e-banking covers all the ways of banking business electronically. Pedro (2012) and Siyanbola (2013) describe e-banking as a direct delivery of both the new and the traditional form of banking services to customers and potential customers via an electronic, interactive medium. Gbadeyan and Gbonda (2011) emphasized that e-banking allows many banking transactions to be carried out electronically, as currency and bank notes are now converted to data that are then translated through telephone lines and satellite transponders usually otherwise referred to as an e-banking system.

Oyewole, *et al.*, (2013) and Ilu, *et al.*, (2014) assets that e-banking is regarded as the major shift in marketing practices that enables banks to offer effective and efficient value added-added products/services. Brodie, *et al.*, (2007) in their study on organisation and e-marketing penetration emphasised that e-banking has become an important medium to banking sales services; leading to a complete paradigm shift in their performance. Siyanbola (2013) further mentioned that e-banking has promoted globalisation in banking transactions for this reason,

banks now uses infrastructural facilities (internet) technology to enhance banking services. With e-banking banks can provide quality banking service that enables customers open account, deposit money and make payment completely on the internet (Takeddine and Sun, 2016).

Overall, electronic banking has been described as the provision of banking services to customers via internet technology (Takeddine and Sun, 2016; Anouze and Alamro, 2020). Other studies such as Karjaluoto, *et al.*, (2002); Samsudin, *et al.* (2009), among others argued that banks now offer their banking services via different electronic distribution technological channels like the telephone banking technology, internet technology, video banking technology, and WAP technology. Karjaluoto, *et al.* (2002) further indicated that internet technology is the main electronic distribution channel in the banking industry. Some authors (Anouze and Alamro, 2020; Takeddine and Sun, 2016; Akinyele and Olohunke 2010) described e-banking in more details and is defined as an online banking or internet banking that involves the provision of banking products like accessing accounts, transferring funds between accounts and offering an online financial service. In this study, e-banking is regarded as technology-based banking services (eg ATMs, telephone and online banking) performed through the internet

2.2.1 E-banking Benefits

The benefits associated with e-banking has increased its uptake in recent times and researchers have attributed reasons for its uptake to hinged on its benefits over the traditional branch banking system (Inegbedion, 2018; Anouze and Alamro, 2020), speed and convenience of service delivery compared to the manual banking system (Ling, *et al.* 2016), affordability of costs of services than traditional banking system (Mirza, *et al.*, 2009; Bojuwon, 2015; Agwu 2018), transformation of the financial banking systems in terms of the products/services, manner of packaging the delivery of these services/products (Elisha, 2010), and its anytime availability not limited to normal working hours compared to the traditional offerings (Supathanish, 2010). Existing literature established that the benefits of e-banking are numerous and highly significant (Maduku, 2014; Ononugo, 2015). Thus, the key benefits of e-banking are summarised in table 2.3.

Table 2.3
Benefits of E-banking

Definitions	Literature Evidence
Speedy delivery	(Pikkarainen, <i>et al.</i> , 2004; Elisha, 2010; Adeshina and Ayo 2010; Okoro 2014; Ononugo, 2015; Ling, <i>et. al.</i> 2016; Orji 2018),
Availability and accessibility	(Olatokun and Igbinedion 2009; Supertanish 2010; Fozia 2013; Ayo, <i>et. al.</i> , 2016; Orji 2018)
Reliability	(Lio and Cheung 2003; Fozia 2013; Ononugo, 2015; Ayo, <i>et. al.</i> , 2016)
Affordability/cost	(Parisa, 2006; Mirza, <i>et. al.</i> , 2009; Bojuwon, 2015; Agwu 2018)
Convenience shopping	(Adeshina and Ayo 2010; Tarhini, <i>et al</i> , 2015; Bajuwon 2015; Agwu 2017; Orji, 2018)
Better service	(Takeddine and Sun, 2016; Dootson, <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Ilu, <i>et. al.</i> , 2014; Oyewole, <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Baba 2012; Patsiotis, <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Arts, <i>et. al.</i> , 2011; Xue, Hitt and Harker 2007)
Customer retention and loyalty	(Xue, Hitt and Harker 2007).
Improve customer experience	(Greenspan, 2007; Patsiotis, <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Takeddine and Sun, 2016)
Traditional market chain transformation	(Chen, <i>et. al.</i> , 2006; Amrit 2007; Siyanbola 2013)
Competitive advantage	(Amrit, 2007; Bojuwon, 2015)

Source: Researcher generated from literature

E-banking adoption is also influenced by its ability to create business value, strengthen automaton process for best services for banking organizations and their customers and achieving satisfaction for its uptake. Customers uptake e-banking for conveniences, speed, safety, access to customers account from anywhere in the globe (Ononugo 2015), with no geographical barrier (Al-Hawari, 2015), 24-hours-a-day and 7-day-a-week service (Cheng *et al.*, 2006). Further to this, Anouze and Alamro, (2020) observed that the introduction of e-banking lead to electronically inclined financial services; and elimination of human-error (Basias, Themistocleous and Morabito, 2014). Whilst e-banking ensures user-friendly banking activities however, e-banking adopters must maintain highest security level and confidentiality (Anouze and Alamro, 2020).

Adopting e-banking, customers can make payments related to credit and credit cards, direct money payment and payment of utility bills (Orji, 2018), and customers can apply for mortgage and loans without necessarily visiting the banking hall, so, less bank visit is needed to bank for banking transactions (Inegbedion, 2018). However, banks equally benefit from e-banking adoption. With e-banking, bank maintains lower transaction costs because e-banking do not really need paperwork, have lesser staffs and lesser physical branches (Cheng, *et al.*, 2006). Overall, from the customer point of view, e-banking adoption significantly saves time with the automation of banking services, faster information access and easy maintenance of cash.

2.2.2 Challenges of Electronic Banking

As illustrated in previous section, e-banking has brought ample number of benefits to banks and customers. Despite the benefits, it still has series of weaknesses, shortcomings and risks. Presented and summarised in table 3 are e-banking hindrances highlighted from relevant literature;

Table 2.4:
Challenges of Electronic Banking

Challenges	Literature Evidence
Security and privacy	(Wai-Ching 2007; Adeshina and Ayo 2010; Siyanbola 2013; Okoro 2014; Tarhini, <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ikpefan <i>et. al.</i> , 2018; Inegbedion, <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Anouze and Alamro, 2020)
Infrastructure deficit	(Yonghong 2005; Chiemeka, <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Stephen 2011; Ikpefan, <i>et. al.</i> , 2018)
Technological challenges eg. costs, software, website and infrastructure	(Yap, <i>et. al.</i> 2010; Yonghong, 2005; Agwuet <i>al.</i> , 2014; Onodugo 2015)
Diminishes human connection	(The Economist 2015)
Legal and regulatory framework	(Acha 2008; Agwu <i>et. al.</i> 2014; Bojuwon 2015; Onodugo 2015)

Source: Researcher generated from literature

The automation of e-banking channels from brick to click banking has aggravated traditional banking risks and raised many threats to banks as well as their customers. Risks are considered crucial factors affecting e-banking uptake. E-banking associated risk further identified includes security risk, legal risks, strategic risk etc. Extant studies have shown that lack of security; trust, inadequate infrastructural facilities, for example, power supply and telecommunication have been highlighted as the major barriers of electronic banking in Nigeria (Tarhini *et. al.*, 2015; Ikpefan, *et. al.*, 2018). Yap, *et. al.* (2010) stressed that lack of website content update to make information available to e-banking users are often dilemma. Thus, it is imperative for banking organisations to understand and manage the factors that affect e-banking to overcome e-banking challenges (Montazemi and Qahri-Saremi, 2015).

The overall difference between e-banking system and traditional systems are illustrated in the table 2.5 below.

Table 2.5:

Differences between E-banking and Traditional Banking Systems

E-banking System	Traditional Banking System
Uses telecommunication networks and electronic system	Manual filling systems and old ledger cards are used
Computer, software, telecommunication networks and certain electronic devices are the main devices for e-banking transactions	Customers do not need to have access to software of electronic devices for banking transactions
E-banking gives room for customers to carry out important banking activities anywhere	Only banks personnel can carry out banking transactions for the customer and must be done within the banking hall
Little processes and less paper-based transactions.	Only paper-based transactions

Source: Researcher generated from the analysis of Chen *et. al* 2006; Malhortra and Singh 2007; Pedro 2012; Siyanbola 2013; Tarhini 2015; Agwu 2017.

2.3 Adoption of E-Banking (Electronic Banking)

Many studies exist on e-banking, but little has been done about e-banking adoption and its proliferation. Hence, this section presents an overview of information technology adoption, electronic channels including the core e-banking channels, products and services considered mostly used in Nigeria, the trend of the e-banking performance in Nigeria, the factors that influence their adoption and empirical review on e-banking in global and in Nigeria.

Technology in the form of e-banking products and service are adopted to meet users' needs and the reason for its adoption depends on how the users perceived it and associated benefits (Baba, 2012). The impacts of this technology are equally related to the degree at which society accepts and adopts the technologies (Tarhini, *et al.*, 2015). For example, the rapid growth of internet technologies had huge impact on how banks operate their business and how consumers conduct their banking activities (Lee, 2009). Adopting e-banking channels such as internet (online) banking, customers now have the options to perform banking activities such as paying bills, checking account information and transferring funds remotely anytime (Orji, 2018). Similarly, the cost minimising aspects, wider reach, higher competitiveness and higher long-term profits generation has indeed endeared its adoption by the banks as well as their customers.

According to Agwu (2014), the adoption of IT into banking activities has led to the proliferation and extension of electronic-based banking products as an alternative channel for routing banking services to customers. The newest delivery channels(e-banking) have promoted the medium of banking operations and, however, influenced banks service to customers (Driga and Isac 2014), making them important for banks survival (Mbama and Ezepue, 2018). Basias, Themistocleous, and Morabito, (2015) noted that the significant

benefits that e-banking offers lead banks to develop new e-banking channels and services. Research further suggests that customers adopt e-banking for self-service, freedom from time and place constraint, and reduced stress of queuing in banking hall (Pikkaranien, *et al.* 2004). Basias, Themistocleous and Morabito (2015) also claimed that banks adopt IT architectures to minimise technical complexity, manageable environment and to offer better e-banking service. For example, IT spending attributed to banks across Asia-Pacific, Europe and North America, Europe in 2012 increased to US\$173.3 billion and investment in transaction technologies and robust IT practices made e-banking service more effective (Basias, *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, e-banking spreads rapidly all over the world, European nation being at the top and with the highest e-banking adoption rates of about 83% excluding ATM. The Americas makes the second cluster with 77.2% adoption rate, and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CISs) have the third rate of adoption with 72.2%. The Arab states have an adoption rate of 51.5%. Asia Pacific region have 48.4% adoption rate and the Africa countries accounted for 28.2% adoption rate. When e-banking adoption in the developed economies is compared to the developing countries, it appear that the developing have lower adoption rate than the emerged economies. However, Asia and Pacific countries have lower rate than the Americas and CIS countries. SIA Pacific and African countries appears at the lower part of the list, as shown in Table 4, justifying the study decision to study banks from emerging economies such as Nigeria.

Table 2.6:
Regional e-banking adoption rate

Region	Percentage of e-banking adoption
Europe	82.5%
Americas	77.2%
CISs	72.2%
Arab states	51.6%
Asia and Pacific	48.4%
Africa	28.2%
Source: Statista (2019). www.statista.com	

2.3.1 Electronic Banking Channels/Products and Services

Electronic banking products have evolved due to techno-economic trends in business world. Financial institution all over the globe have adopted the automation of their services through ICT for efficient financial services. Electronic channels allow preparation, control and oversight of financial transactions between the bank and their customers. E-banking products and services includes familiar and relatively mature electronically based products (Ojeka and Ikpefan, 2011). Some of the common electronic banking channels are;

- (1). Home Banking. A banking system that involve conducting and carrying out banking transactions right from the home and not at the banking halls that allows customers access to their personal account information through a phone call (Driga and Isac, 2014). It relies heavily on a telephone line, a personal code generated to provide data access and customer password; customer can then transfer money within their account, check their account balances and carry out little banking transactions
- (2). PC Banking. A personal compute banking that allows bank customers to perform banking transactions at home from a personal system (computer) through a modem and financial software programme without visiting a bank. It offers customers the opportunity to perform series of retail banking activities such as money transfer between accounts, buy/sell mutual funds and securities, pay bills and check account balances once access is gained.
- (3). Mobile/Telephone Banking (MOB). A form of e-banking service that allows bank clients to execute various financial transactions through mobile or telephone. It relies heavily on Wireless Application Protocol (WAP) technology/browser installed to function appropriately and access banking information. In furtherance to this, Sharma (2011) mentioned that tele-banking is a voice processing technology banking provided by specialised software. The software recognises the caller's voice and respond back to the caller. According to Balachandher, *et al.*, (2001) the mobile banking is the delivery of financial services via telecommunication devices that enable bank customers to perform retail banking transactions by dealing a touch-tone telephone or mobile device, connected to the bank's an automated system by utilizing Automated Voice Response (AVR) technology. Similarly, Oliveira *et al.*, (2014) and Alalwan *et al.*, (2016) maintained that mobile banking is an interface where bank client can access banking information through mobile devices such as smartphones, tables and personal digital assistants (PDAs) at any point in time and place. Telephone/mobile banking enable customers to enquire financial transactions remotely, offer flexibility to banking industry and gives customers access to convenient banking services (Mohammadi, 2015). Mobile banking is represented by the number of mobile banking users in the sampled banks for this study. An increase in the number of mobile banking users depicts satisfactory customer service.
- (4). Internet Banking. This is also called on-line banking, web banking and virtual banking (Adepoju, Babalola and Onyeabor, 2011). It is an e-banking type that uses the internet as a channel to carry out banking activities (Ahasanul *et al.* 2009; Ojeka and Ikpefan, 2011).

Driga and Isac (2014) stressed that e-banking is a system that allows bank clients access to banks' products/services or perform banking transactions through PC using internet delivery channel. Internet banking enables banks to reduce their branch networks and downsized their employee and enable self-service channels for customers (Karjaluo *et al.*, 2003).

- (5). Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT). This is an online system that enable customers to transfer funds immediately from their bank accounts to merchant accounts at point of purchases. EFT increases banking performance due to the efficiency in transferring customers' shopping payment requirements without handling cheques and making cash withdrawals for shopping. It continued transaction for the bank even after banking hours, saves customers energy and time in getting to ATM or visiting a bank branches before withdrawing cash.
- (6). Point of Sale (POS). This is a terminal machine that accept credit or debit cards for payment of goods/services. The POS terminal allows a cardholder to have online access to funds and information in his/her bank account through debit/credit cards. POS system can include the ability to record and track customer orders, process credit and debit cards, connect to other systems in a network, and manage inventory. POS channel is represented in this study by number of bank customers that have use it for their banking transactions
- (7). ATM-Automated Teller Machine. ATM the most revolutionary of the e-banking channels. These are computer-enhanced self-vendor telecommunication machines that permit bank customers to have accessibility to cash and perform financial transactions around the clock, situated in public places and use without bank teller. The customer is identified at the ATM facility through a plastic card with a magnetic stripe, or a plastic smartcard with a chip that contains a unique card number and security information eg. end date (Sharma, 2011). The ATM has been the first e-product to be put in general use in the banking sector (Bank of England Quarterly Bulletin 1983). In UK for instance, the ATM with magnetic stripe plastic card were introduced in 1967 and 1969 beginning the era of self-service banking (Bartiz-Lazo and Wood 2002). Shoewu and Edeko (2011) asserted that ATM services are highly profitable for Nigeria banks, for this reason, these banks intentionally market the use of ATM cards, as the ATMs not in the banking hall are usually more profitable for banks in Nigeria because non-bank customers who uses the machine pay service charge. On this note, commercial banks with well spread ATMs machine across the country tend to have competitive advantage over other banks with lesser ATMs geographical coverage eg. GTB-Guaranty Trust Bank one of the sample use for this study and one of the largest commercial banks in Nigeria.

The POS and ATM requires Verve card or Mastercard to function for customers financial transaction. These cards are provided with a unique Personal Identification Number (PIN) for individual bank customer (Inegbedion, *et. al.*, 2019). However, among the five e-banking products considered in this study, ATM happens to be the first e-banking channel introduced in Nigeria in 1989 (Ononuga, *et. al.*, 2015; Agwu 2016; Orji *et. al.*, 2018). In furtherance of this, empirical evidence suggest that ATM is the most adopted, most patronised e-banking channel used in Nigeria (Okoro 2014; Inegbedion, *et al.*,2019). The reasons for this are attributed to ease of use, convenience, time savings, among others. This study therefore focusses on five e-banking channels of the seven highlighted above. These includes ATM, internet banking, POS, Mobile/Telephone banking and ETF. These are the core e-banking products and services considered the most to have implications on the adopters (Deloitte 2015; Ayodele 2014), and the most used for banking transactions in Nigeria (KPMG, 2013).

2.3.2 Trend Performance of E-Banking Channels in Nigeria

The trend performance of e-banking channels in Nigeria shows that ATM is the most preferred and most use channels (Figure 2.3). As shown in the figure, the value of ATM transactions rose from ₦375.5 billion naira in 2012 to ₦875.52 in 2018. Thereafter in 2013 ATM value decreases slightly to ₦295.5 billion but later rose significantly from ₦400.3 billion in 2014 to ₦433.70 billion in 2015, and further increases from ₦590.24billion in 2016 to ₦800.55 billion in 2017 and then to ₦875.52 billion in 2018. The reason for the increase in the usage of ATM channel was due to the increase in the number of banks offering ATM services (CBN, 2019).

Figure 2.3:

Performance of E-banking channels in Nigeria: 2012-2018

Source: Researcher's computation from CBN (2019) E-payment publication

POS increases from 2.6 billion in 2012 to 9.42 billion in 2013 and further increases from ₦20.8 billion in 2014 to ₦33.7 billion in 2015. Theafter, the value of POS transaction increases

significantly from ₦63.7 billion in 2016 to ₦146.3 billion in 2017, and then to ₦295.9 billion in 2018 (CBN, 2019).

The figure 1 shows that the value of internet transactions in figure 1 rose from ₦2.28 billion in 2012 to ₦2.90 billion in 2013, then rises to 5.57 billion in 2014. Thereafter, the value rose significantly from ₦7.98 billion in 2015 to ₦14.10 billion in 2016. Further to this, the internet transaction further increases sharply from ₦29.10 billion in 2017 to ₦50.82 billion in 2018.

As depicted in the figure, the value of mobile transactions rose from ₦2,29 billion in 2012 to ₦15.9983 billion in 2013. Thereafter, the value rose significantly from ₦27.74 in 2014 to ₦49.93 in 2015. Further to this, mobile transaction slightly increased from ₦47.05 billion in 2016 to ₦47.81 in 2018 and finally increased geometrically to ₦87.09 billion in 2018. The increase in the use of mobile banking was due to more banks offering mobile banking services, the increased in public confidence in electronic payment (CBN, 2019), and the reformation exercise in the banking sector.

Statistics in figure 1 revealed that EFT slightly rose from ₦28,94 billion in 2012 to ₦29.83 in 2014 and thereafter declined consistently from ₦29.69 in 2015 to ₦28,93 billion in 2016 and then to ₦29.75 billion in 2016. Further investigation of the statistic in the figure showed that the electronic fund transfer transaction rose significantly to ₦31.03 billion in 2017 after that fell sharply to ₦26.76 billion in 2018.

Consequently, through the explosive growth in the use of Information Communication Technologies (ICTs), Nigeria banks employed different channels such as internet technology, video banking technology, telephone banking, Automated Teller Machine (ATM), and WAP technology to deliver their e-banking services (Orji. *et al.* 2018). Yet, in Nigeria, there is still serious debate whether the e-banking innovations adoption rate have increases and perhaps contributes generally to Nigeria banking sector performance. This is because Nigeria's banking system is not efficiently providing its roles for customers and have not really performed optimally as expected towards their customers, in spite of the banking sector reforms in the areas of bank recapitalization and e-banking innovations adoptions (Nkoro and Uko, 2015; Orgi, *et al.* 2018). Therefore, there is a need to examine the adoption process towards e-banking products. Section 2.3.3 discusses the technology adoption process in the e-banking context.

2.3.3 Technology Adoption Process

Extant studies (Njuguna *et al.* 2012) emphasize the importance of regular analyses of bank customers' e-banking requirements to understand the factors determining e-banking adoption or usage. Kim and Crowston (2011) made a significant contribution in the area of technology adoption factors. Kim and Crowston (2011) further stressed that individual ICT use can be understood in three different stages: pre-adoption, adoption, and post-adoption, with action and decision happening at each of the stages (Montazemi and Qahri-Saremi, 2015). In this research, the same stages are employed to understand the process of e-banking adoption and usage. Thus, the study believes these sequence of stages matters in adoption of innovation. Importantly, the adoption process illustrated in Fig 2.4 must be understood as a dynamic behaviour of technology acceptance and use.

Figure 2.4: Technology Adoption Process

Source: Kim and Crowston, (2011, p. 3)

- * **Pre-adoption Stage;** this stage involves recognising a need, acquiring awareness or knowledge, forming initial attitude towards the technology and consider or propose the adoption (Damanpour and Schneider, 2006; Hameed, Counsell, and Swift, 2012). Looney, Akbulut and Poston (2008) states that begins with the customer awareness that result to mental examination, which may then lead to adoption of the technology or innovation. It is considered as the decision stage where the decision to adopt an innovation is considered and the idea is evaluated from financial, strategic and technical perspectives along with the resources required for its adoption and acquisition (Meyer and Goesm, 1988). The pre-adoption stage in this study is the first stage at which the consumer considers the e-banking channels in term of the benefits, challenges and consider to either uptake or refuse.
- * **Adoption Stage.** At the adoption stage, users may form an intension to use or an innovation (Kim and Crowston, 2011). This study deems that at this stage, customers may form an intention to adopt the e-banking service and products, and they eventually use it.

- * **Post Adoption Stage.** This stage consisting of activities relating to the acquisition, preparation for the use of the technology, performing a trial for confirmation and acceptance and continual use of the technology (innovation) by users (Rogers, 1995), an innovation is adopted, and usage is continuing (Kim and Crowston, 2011). In this study, the post adoption stage is considered as the stage which the e-banking adopters either continue to use the products and services, feel reluctant to use and decided to abandon it. Some promotions are needed at this stage to support this stage to maintain perceive value of usability since customers has already adopted the innovation (e-banking) services, factors that can facilitate adoption are needed for continual usage, for example, effective infrastructural technologies.

2.3.4 Factors that influence E-Banking Adoption

The major crucial influencing factors that affect customer willingness to use e-banking according to literature are categorised into psychological, sociological and economic factors (Inegbedion *et. al.*, 2019).

2.3.4.1 Psychological Factors:

- * *Personality:* personality influences consumer willingness to use e-banking. An individual person poses these special personalities and no two persons possess these same personalities. Thus, variations in a customer personality influences the customer's preference for e- banking.
- * *Perception about E-banking:* the perception of the bank customers about e-banking products affects and influences the uptake of e-banking channels for banking services and other transactions. So, e-banking perception is a function of personality
- * *Bank websites:* The banker's website to their customers should be very credible and with integrity. To attract customers' patronage websites must be able to communicate credibility and integrity (Constantinides, 2004), should be persuasive and with good quality (Sharma and Lijuan, 2015).
- * *Trust:* Trust is a very crucial element that matters most to customers in electronic banking environment. It includes the customer perceptions of how the bank website would meet its expectations, how rich the website's information is, and the website confidence level (Inegbedion, *et al.*, 2016). The consumer online trust drives consumer repurchase intension (Saleem *at. al.*, 2017). From the customers' point of view, trust in the e-banking entails

the customers' trust in the e-banking channels in terms of the security and the delivery channel security and service delivery.

2.3.4.2 Sociological factors:

- * *Social Class*: The customer social class significantly affects and influences the customer's purchase behaviour. Categorizing people using their wealth, income, education, occupation type as parameters is regarded as social class. Constantinides (2004) claimed that social class can also be categorised on the basis; the rich, the middle class and the poor. However, it is logical to believe that the more consumers are educated and the richer they are influence their e-banking uptake.
- * *Culture*: The consumers' or customers' culture equally determine the consumers tendency to uptake electronic banking because some of the customers cultures attached so much belief to using the e-banking hence they are influenced by this culture. Consumers culture influence their perception and prioritization about e-banking service (Bruschet *al.*, 2019).

2.3.4.3 Economic factors:

- * *Time*: Time is one of the major factors that influence the consumer using e-banking products and services. Time in terms of the transaction speed, helps saves time as such make it preferable to the traditional form of banking.
- * *Cost*: The cost of e-banking is also a significant factor that influences the consumer adopting one or all the e-banking channels. The cost of e-banking in term of the subscription cost for the internet, debit and credit cards cost and other e-banking products seem expensive compared to traditional banking thus making the e-banking channels/products and services appear expensive. Fundamentally, customers need to have access to the internet in order to use virtually all the e-banking services. However, the e-banking products cost, the ease of making financial transactions and the time saving aspects of the e-banking together significantly influence consumer willingness to use any of the e-banking channels and products/services.

2.4 Empirical Review

This section provides the empirical studies on e-banking across the world.

Several studies have been carried out on factors inhibiting e-banking adoption and acceptance. However, most of these studies in the banking industries have been conducted mostly in advanced countries (Gill, Bunker, and Seltsikas 2015; Mbama and Ezepue 2018). This area is underrepresented in the emerging economies such as Nigeria where banks are trying to improve

their e-banking system to better banks operations, reduce their costs and increase efficiency. Some studies have been conducted in emerging economies such as (Anouze and Alamro, 2020; Birbirs, *et al.* 2019; Xiao, *et al.* 2017; Tarhini, *et al.* 2015; Agwu, 2017; Abubakar and Rosmaini 2012; Bambore and Singla 2017; Dobdinga 2013; Dauda and Wahidi 2011) and they have been descriptive. Dobinga (2013) mentioned that there are limited studies on emerging economies on e-banking proliferation in term of customer service, loyalty and especially innovation technology adoption in the banking sector.

The prior studies on e-banking ranges from Mbama and Ezepe (2018) study in UK, Lichtenstein and Williamson (2006) research in Australia, other studies were carried out in USA, New Zealand, Sydney, Malaysia, South Africa, Cameroon, and others. Among the Nigerian e- banking researches were (Tarhini, *et al.* 2015; Agwu 2017). Unfortunately, these previous e-banking studies in various countries have produced mixed results on factors that inhibit e-banking adoption, these added to the problem of articulating the factors that affect adoption of electronic banking. Thus, studies on e-banking remain inconclusive within the limited available studies, however, so far, there are diverse conflicting results regarding factors affecting e-banking adoption and customer perception about e-banking channels. For example, while Tarhini,*et al.* (2015) found security, culture and religion to be very significant factor affecting e-banking adoption, Hoque (2013) found security to be marginally significant, attributed to the better education of the Singaporean e-banking users, which makes the security of e-banking adoption less significant in Singapore.

2.4.1 Evidence from Nigeria

This section provides some of the influential studies in Nigeria. Agwu (2017) claimed that studies on e-banking in Nigeria are limited and further argued that customers' adoption of e-banking innovation service is crucial for the development of the Nigeria banking sector (Agwu 2017), customers e-banking is unarguably under researched and needs further research (Olawepo 2013). Thus, the current study attempts to contribute by focusing on the banking sector of an emerging economy, Nigeria. Table 7 presents the previous literature examining e-banking adoption and the summary of their findings. The selection of all the studies mentioned in the table was based on the ground that; they are influential studies undertaken in Nigeria and their findings were considered imperative for the study.

Table 2.7

Some influential research conducted in the field of e-banking adoption

Authors	Major findings	Titles	Journal
Inegbedion <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Exposure to e-banking influence uptake	Exposure to and usage of e-banking channels: implication for bank customers' awareness and attitude to e-banking in Nigeria	Science and technology policy management journal
Inegbedion (2018)	Ease of use, internet knowledge and transaction nature influence e-banking adoption	Factors that influence customer attitude toward electronic banking in Nigeria	Journal of internet commerce
Agwu (2017)	Security, privacy and infrastructure (internet) influence electronic banking adoption	Analysis of the emergent issues in internet banking adoption in Nigeria	International journal of information, business and management
Tarhiniet <i>al.</i> (2015)	Security, culture and religion are influences uptake of e-banking	User adoption of online banking in Nigeria.	Internet banking and commerce journal
Bojuwon (2015)	Information insecurity, unreliability of the system structure cost causes resistance of adoption of internet channel	Patronage and resistance factors on internet banking usage in Nigeria	
Agwu (2017)	Security, privacy, infrastructure, income and education significantly affect adoption of e-banking	Empirical analysis of retail customers adoption of E-banking service in Nigeria	Internet banking and commerce journal
Awara and Anyadigbibe (2014)	Security, ease of use, accessibility and awareness of e-banking influence adoption.	Factors influencing banks' implementation and consumers' acceptance of e-banking of selected commercial banks in Calabar, Nigeria.	International journal of management studies and research
Agwu, Simon and Onwuka (2016)	Security, privacy, trust and lack of necessary infrastructural facilities affects adoption	Mobile Banking – Adoption and Challenges in Nigeria	International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences and Humanities Research
Agwu, <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Poor educational imbalance and lack of adequate policy framework affect e-banking adoption	Impediments to e-banking services marketing in developing economies – a case study of Nigeria banks	European Journal of Business and Social Sciences
Adeshina and Ayo (2010)	Network Security and system privacy affect e-banking usage	An empirical investigation of the level of users' acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria	Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce

Recent empirical investigations by scholars such as Agwu (2017); Bojuwon (2015); Tarhini, *et al.* (2015), Agu, Simon and Onwuka (2016) found security, privacy, trust and lack of necessary infrastructural facilities as factors affecting e-banking thereby causing low adoption levels of some e-banking channels. For example, Tarhini, *et al.* (2015), study the effect of online banking adoption in Nigeria. The study was carried out with thirty (30) people including banks customers, managers and students. The study identified security as the major hinderance, culture and religion are also identified as influencing factors for adoption and recommends further examination of culture and religion factors as influencing factors determining e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

Agu, Simon and Onwuka (2016) examined mobile banking services adoption in Nigeria. Two hundred bank customers and staff were used four Nigerian commercial banks. They adopted

survey research approach. The findings showed that the level of adoption of m-banking is still low among the middle age. Perceived voice-centric nature of the mobile phone, security issue and treats has been identified as the factor behind poor adoption of mobile-banking in Nigeria.

Adeshina and Ayo (2010) investigated users' acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria using two hundred and ninety-two (292) participants. A survey research design was adopted, and regression technic employed for data analysis. The findings of their study indicates that network security and security of the system in terms of privacy are major hindrance of usage. Further to this, the result indicate that ATM remains the most widely adopted e-banking channels among others.

Bojuwon (2015) explored patronage and resistance factors on internet banking usage using five Nigerian banks. One fifty-two (152) customers were used for the study. The finding of the study shows that information insecurity, unreliability of the system structure, safety and cost are factors behind customers resistance to using the internet.

Okoro (2014) examined the impact of e-banking instruments on the Nigeria economy efficiency. Secondary data was used, and multiple regression analysis was employed for data analysis. The findings revealed that significant relationship exist between ATM, POS, internet and the Nigeria economy efficiency. Findings further indicates that no relationship between mobile banking services and the Nigeria economy efficiency.

Agwu (2017) carried out a recent study on factors behind customers adoption of internet banking in Nigeria using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Twenty people were used for the study comprising bank customers, managers and students hence, the finding of the study revealed that security, privacy and infrastructure (internet) are significant factors hindering the adoption of internet banking. Furthermore, Agwu, *et al.* (2014) explore impediments of e-banking services using seven banks in Nigeria. Five hundred respondents were used for the study. Results showed that poor educational imbalance and lack of adequate policy framework to affect the e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

In sum, prior studies have not sufficiently integrated enough influencing factors to examine e-banking adoption. Instead of the insufficient factors used in previous studies, this research uses 14 key variables to provide a depth understanding of the factors influencing customers adopting e-banking. Besides, studies investigating the factors affecting e-banking in collaboration with Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) variables, Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) constructs and demographic characteristics have not yet be undertaken. As argued above, the

joint approach has not been carried out in previous E-banking studies. Therefore, this study strives to fill this gap with the employed conceptual model explained in the next section.

The benefits of using multiple constructs are highlighted below;

- It helps to provide more detailed understanding of the relationship between the factors
- It provides holistic perspective of the various constructs for better idea of the most influencing factors
- Using multiple constructs helps to unravel the most important variables that determine behavioral intention of e-banking users (Garg, *et al.*, 2014; Keisidou *et al.*, 2013).
- It helps to provide better understanding of the determinants of new technology adoption that is capable of explaining users behaviour across range of factors (Agwu, 2017).
- Multiple constructs framework can be very helpful not only for predicting new technology adoption but also perfect for providing explanation of the various factors that can help practitioners and researcher understand why an innovation may be accepted or unaccepted
- It helps to provide in detail the impacts of various variables on users intention and attitude towards technology adoption (Anouze and Alamro, 2020).
- Employing multiple constructs enables researchers to devise practically useful model that can help in providing explanatory modelling in theory building and theory testing (Shmueli and Koppius, 2010).
- Adopting multiple constructs can help reveal the varying impacts of factors that influence technology acceptance and usage (Anouze and Alamro, 2020).

2.5 Theoretical Framework

The literature relating to various aspects of e-banking adoption was reviewed in the previous section. This section discusses the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study, starting first with the theoretical framework which then leads to the development of the conceptual framework.

The theoretical framework is important for examining the theoretical underpinning the study. Theories make visualisation of complex social reality possible to explain why something happens (Neuman, 2006). Different socio-cognitive theories capable of predicting human behaviour have been established to predict human behaviour regarding the adoption of new technologies (Alomary and Woollard, 2015). Moreso, Information Communication Technology researchers have used the social psychology perspective to suggest behavioural

intention models serving as an important theoretical foundation for determining user adoption behaviour (Pavlou, 2003). However, the basic theories considered suitable to predict the intention to use a technology and aid the understanding of factors influencing new technologies according to literature are: Theories of Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1985), TAM-Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) and IDT-Innovation Diffusion Theory Roger (1995 (Vinkatesh, *et al.* 2003). These major theoretical models are often adopted to examine the factors that determine customers' behavioural intention to adopt an innovation (Yu, 2012), and have their respective attributes and claims (Alomary and Woollard, 2015). The study use some constructs of the Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDM) to supplement TAM for better insight of the factors that influence consumer behavioural intention towards adoption of e-banking in Nigeria.

⇒ **TPB- Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1985).** TPB is an extension of theory of Reasoned Action introduced to address the limitations of TRA in dealing with behaviour which the people do have volitional control indicating person's readiness to perform the behaviour. Although, TRA and TPB theories established that behaviour is directly related to behavioural intention (Shih and Fang, 2004). TRA was extended by another construct known as Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) that predict behavioural intention and control. PBC-Perceived Behavioural Control was included to explain the situation where people have no control over their behaviour. Essentially, the PBC was introduced so that it can help to predict human behaviour in a specific context. Nevertheless, PBC has been defined as the PE-perceived ease and, or difficulty of performing the behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), and is assumed to reflect on prior experience and the anticipated hindrances. Studies have found it to be more valid in human behaviour prediction and its efficiency in predicting consumer behaviour has been confirmed. For instance, Troung (2009) used PBC theory to explore the adoption of internet video services in France and confirmed it is a worthwhile model, effective for predicting technology adoption. Even though TPB has been found to be more valid, the flaws of the model made it not suitable for exploring the behavioural intention of bank customers in the Nigeria context. It is worthy to note that not all behaviours are subject to people volitional control, as non-motivational factors such as skills, money and time sometimes influenced the consumers behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

This study could also have adopted TPB to explain electronic(e)-banking adoption factors in the case study Nigeria but the inherent flaws of TPB serves as a challenge. TPB does not explain further other factors that can predict the actual usage of an innovation. On this premise,

TPB does not equally fit in to explore the concern of the study which centres on evaluation of the factors that could predict the behavioural change of bank customers changing from traditional banking system to electronic banking system.

⇒**TAM-Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989)**. TAM is an information communication technology theory propounded by Davis (1989), and an adaptation/extension of TRA (Tung *et al.*, 2014), specifically designed for modelling users’ acceptance of information communication system. The greatest barrier to Information Technology is users’ acceptance (Davis, 1989) such as the E-banking innovation channels: online banking, mobile banking etc. The TAM added two theoretical constructs (Figure 3), Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU); and proclaimed that both constructs are the prime determinants of user’s acceptance of any information technology. The technological acceptance model proposes that Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) predicts the acceptance of information technology (Tung, *et. al.*, 2014). Davis (1989) claimed that technology is adopted primarily because of its functions, and secondarily because of how it is hard/easy for the system to carry out these functions. This suggests that consumer adopt and use an innovation due to its function in terms of usefulness and its simplicity or otherwise.

Figure 2.5: Technological Acceptance Model.

Source: Davis (1989), User Technology Acceptance Model

Since its inception, the model has been tested with various applications in various studies and has become the most widely applied model of user acceptance and usage (Pikkarainen *et. al.*, 2004). Davis has used the model to research on users’ adoption of information technology and the model has been globally adopted for examining and predicting adoption of innovation technology (Chen, Li and Li, 2011). For example, the studies of Shaikh and Karjaluo, (2014) found TAM to account for 42% of the 55 studies they reviewed on adoption of mobile banking. According to Ramlugun and Issuree (2014) TAM model has been widely adopted and used for describing users’ acceptance of information system or new technologies; known as one of the

best models as it has been broadly tested and validated; with added advantage that it can easily be extended with other theoretical constructs (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). This has led to its adaptation and use by information technology researchers examining determinants of information systems and new technology adoption (Venkatesh et al. 2003).

The attitude of a user and the behavioural intention towards technology usage can be predicted by two internal variables- the Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use (Alharbi and Drew, 2014). In line with Theory of Reasoned Action and Theory of Planned behaviour, the TAM theory stressed that BI-Behavioural intention is the prime factor that determine the adoption behaviour. The attitude of a user and the behavioural intention towards technology usage can be predicted by two internal variables- the Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use (Alharbi and Drew, 2014). TAM has been adopted in many studies and it has been revealed that it has ability to explain consumer attitude towards adopting information system is better compared to theory of reasoned action and theory of planned behaviour (Malthieson, 1991).

As shown in figure 3, TAM posits that two special beliefs (PU) and PEOU generalisable in different settings are the primary relevance for a technology acceptance behaviour. The PU and PEOU according to TAM predict users' attitude and subsequent behavioural intention towards a given technology (Masrom, 2007). TAM assumes behaviour – the manifest, observable response in a given situation is volitional, and an individual readiness to perform the given behaviour indicates the behavioural intention (Ajzen, 2006), which makes it the main predictor of the actual behaviour. In TAM, intention is a function of attitude and PU- perceived usefulness. Attitude is the “degree of evaluative affect that an individual associate with using the target system” (Davis, 1993, p. 476). It indicates an individual feeling about a concept, which could be an entity that a person can attach feeling. Hence, attitude play a very crucial role in adopting a new technology decision (Davis *et. al.*, 1989). Attitude is defined as: (a) the attitude toward a specific object, and (b) the attitude toward a specific behaviour or action (Ajzen, 2006). The primary goal of the TAM model is to provide basis for tracing the impact of external factors on internal beliefs, intention, and attitudes. TAM was formulated in order to achieve these goals by identifying some fundamental factors identified by previous studies dealing with the cognitive and affective determinants for IT acceptance.

Pikkarainen, *et. al.*, (2004) noted that the TAM belief consumers engage in a behaviour because they have examined the benefits and expect to certainly get results. On this note, Chung and Paynter (2002) studies revealed that consumer do not adopt a technology for its own sake rather

adopt it because of the technology attributes that drive value, the utility derived from the combining the attributes and excluding the disutility i.e the sacrifices needed to use the technology. The PEOU directly or indirectly affects attitude through its effect on PU: “even if potential users believe that a given application is useful, they may at the same time believe that the systems are too hard to use and that performance benefits of usage are outweighed by the effort of using the application” (Davis 1989, p.320). However, PU and PEOU are influenced by external variables, such as perceived credibility (security and privacy), perceived risk, trust, quality of internet connection, experience etc. The constructs PU and PEOU of TAM form an end-user’s beliefs on a technology and therefore predict his or her attitude towards the technology, which in turn predicts its acceptance (Cheng *et al.*, 2006).

Many of the previous information system empirical studies researchers conducted their research employing TAM to examine the factors that determine consumer behavioural intention to use new technologies with the variables EU and PEOU variables and confirmed having a positive impact on consumer user’s adoption and intention (Konalingam, *et al.* 2017; Diatmika, *et al.* 2016; Al-Qeisi *et al.* 2014; Pikkarainen *et al.*, 2004). For example, the study of Pikkarainen *et al.*, (2004) empirical result found that a significant relationship exists between PU and PEOU as important criterial influencing electronic banking adoption.

However, despite the robustness of TAM, the model has also been found to possess some limitations in its application to consumer adoption of the electronic banking applications and several authors have extended TAM (Pikkarainen, *et al.*, 2004; Lee, 2009), supplemented it by combining it with other factors (Cheng, *et al.* 2006). Khan and Woolsey (2011) reported that the Technology Acceptance Model is too basic because only two constructs are considered. Therefore, Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness alone may not sufficiently determine the user’s intention to adopt electronic banking in a dynamic e-banking environment, thus there is need to examine additional factors that may better predict/influence the acceptance of electronic banking (Munirudeen, 2007; Adeshina and Ayo, 2010; Pikkarainen, *et al.* 2014). Hence, the study uses some constructs of the innovation diffusion theory to supplement TAM for better insight of the actors that influence consumer behavioural intention to adopt e-banking in Nigeria.

⇒**Diffusion of Innovation Theory (Rogers, 1995).** Diffusion of Innovations Theory is well known theory. DIT is a model developed to predict factors influencing adoption of information system (Rogers, 1995). Rodger’s DIT theory try to explain how new idea, new innovative process or product is adopted over time across society or population over time. Rogers

describes diffusion of innovations as: "... the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of social systems. It is a special type of communication, in that the messages are concerned with new ideas" (Rogers 1995, p. 5). Thus, to explain the rate of adoption of innovations Rogers recommends five measurement characteristics of innovations: (i)Relative Advantage, (ii)Compatibility, (ii)Complexity, (iv)Triability; and (iv)Observability.

However, Rogers postulated that five key beliefs characteristics influence innovations adoption and these characteristics can explain adoption rate of technology. Existing studies on Information Technology diffusion stressed the significant of perceived relative advantage to improving organisational performance and determinants of innovation adoption. The higher the perceived relative advantage, the faster the adoption (Rogers, 1995). The DIT emphasised that potential adopters examine an innovation based on innovation characteristics like relative advantage; compatibility; complexity (ease of use); trialability and observability. Research found all these characteristics to be significantly related to factors inhibiting or facilitating IT adoption rate, while the perceived complexity of an innovation is negatively related to its adoption rate (Rogers, 1995). Hogarth, *et. al.* (2008) used DIT and found that the more observable, compatible, simple, useful, and the more benefits of the technology, the more likely they are adopted by the consumers.

- * **Relative Advantage.** Rogers (1995) defined relative advantage as the extent to which an innovation is perceived as better than and providing more benefits than its nearest alternative. Relative advantage can be measured in financial terms; however, social status, comfort, and satisfaction are important factors as well. The greater the perceived relative advantage of a technology, the more its adoption (Rogers, 1995). Prior research found that the relative advantage of an innovation positively correlated with its adoption rate (Moore and Benbasat 1991; Lacovou, Benbasat and Dexter, 1995). Research suggests that users adopt a new technology when they perceive the relative advantage or usefulness of the new one over the predecessor (Rogers 2003; McCloskey 2006). In e-banking adoption context, affordability and convenience of the e-banking services to customers have been found to influence adoption (Lin, 2011). Thus, it appears that customers are more likely to adopt or use e-banking services when they perceive the advantages it offers.
- * **Complexity.** Complexity refers to "the degree to which an innovation is perceived as difficult to understand and use. New ideas that are simpler to understand are adopted faster than those requiring the adopter to develop new skills and understanding (Rogers, 1995).

The complexity of technology has a major effect on the adoption decision (Ha *et al.* 2012), and complexity is regarded as a strong inhibitor of intent to adopt innovation (Chwelos *et al.*, 2002). For example, m-banking researches has found complexity to negatively influence its uptake (Mallat 2007; Au and Kauffman 2008)

- * **Compatibility.** Perceive compatibility refers to the degree to which an innovation is perceived as relatively difficult to use and understand” (Rogers 1995: 242). An innovation might be perceived as technically or financially superior in accomplishing a given task, but it may not be adopted, if a potential adopter views it as irrelevant to its needs (Rogers, 1995:241). Lack of compatibility in information technology with individual needs may negatively affect the individual’s information technology use (McKenzie, 2001). For example, compatibility was shown to have a positive impact on e-mobile banking adoption (Dash and Bhusan 2014).
- * **Trialability.** Trialability is “the degree to which an innovation may be experimented with on a limited basis” (Rogers 1995:243). Trialability allows someone to ‘test drive’ an innovation before its adoption or use (Rogers, 1995). When innovation is open for trial before dully adopted by potential adopters then such innovation can have a significant impact on the potential adopters’ desire to accept the innovation as it can minimise the uncertainties related to its uptake (Rodgers, 1983).
- * **Observability:** Observability is regarded as the extent at which members of a social system can easily observe and communicate the benefits of an innovation (Rogers, 2003). Rodgers claim that the more innovation visibility and its benefits to members of a social system members; the more visible the benefits to others and more likely the innovation may be adopted. In e-banking context, observability is the ability to access banking services from any geographical location, at any time and without any delay, and feeling the impact of the e-banking transactions instantly. Through this exposure, the bank’s clients acquire e-banking knowledge about and the benefits and may facilitate adoption.

Shaikh and Karjaluo (2014) mentioned that DIT is the second most utilized model for researching IT adoption, 16% of empirical studies used DIT as theoretical research framework to investigate factors that promote or restrain IT adoption. Furthermore, Stephenson (2003) indicated that Rogers innovation characteristics is one of the viable innovation theories over the years, hence form one of the reasons for adopting this theory as one of the IT models for the study. Furthermore, the DIT has been specifically adopted in this study because scholars such as Ndubisi and Sinti (2006) and Eriksson, *et al.* (2008) consider the application of the DIT

as more relevant to the understanding of customers' intention to adopt e-banking services and customers' decision to continue or discontinue the use of the innovation. Adoption is defined as the decision to make full use of an innovation (Rogers, 2003).

In sum, previous studies have not sufficiently integrated TAM and DIT variables in E-banking research. Instead of the limited variables used in the previous studies, this research therefore utilises 14 suitable variables to provide greater insight on the factors influencing customers towards adoption of e-banking and their impacts upon customer satisfaction. Moreover, the study considered these variables as factors that affect an individual customer attitude and intention positively or negatively towards using the e-banking. As argued above, the joint approach has not been carried out in previous E-banking studies. The next section presents a holistic view of the conceptual framework of the study.

2.5.1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the critical review of existing literature on information technology theories, models, and the empirical evidence on the influencing factors of e-banking which has been studied in Nigeria and global contexts. To accomplish the objectives of the study, some constructs of the information technology (IT) models were integrated. Moreover, specific constructs of TAM and DIT models informed the contextual framework guiding this study and present the assertion behind the development of research questions. The Technology Acceptance Model and Diffusion of Innovation Theory constructs were chosen since intention and perception are both critical for consumer behavioral attitude towards e-banking. Therefore, the constructs selected from the TAM and DIT theories were integrated in the study to examine factors affecting customer behavioural intention are illustrated in Table 2.8, and the overall factors identified from empirical studies that affect e-banking adoption in Nigeria are illustrated in Fig 5. Furthermore, additional variables or factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria not used in the previous empirical studies such as culture and religion of the demographic characteristics are also integrated in the conceptual framework. Demographic characteristics are considered important factors influencing customers towards the adoption of e-banking.

Table 2.8
TAM-DIM selected constructs

Challenges	Constructs selected
Technology Acceptance Theory (TAM)	Perceived Usefulness (U); Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)
Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT)	Perceived Advantage/Complexity of Use

Figure 2.6.
Factors included in the conceptual model for E-Banking Adoption in Nigeria

Figure 2.6: *The Conceptual Framework Model*

* Perceived usefulness/perceived advantages: The perceived usefulness is the degree to which an individual customer belief that adopting e-banking services will better his banking experience and improve his banking transaction. The perceived usefulness/complexity of use together in turn determines the attitude toward e-banking usage that finally creates customers intention to adopt. This suggests that the ability of an adopter to learn managing the e-banking then, the ease it becomes for the user to perform e-banking basic functions which in turn leads to satisfaction.

* Perceived ease of use /complexity of use: this is defined as the degree to which the users of e-banking service beliefs that adopting the e-banking services would be free of effort thereby resulting to east of learning and using the e-banking (Davis *et. al.* 1989). The perceived ease of use to customers equally determines their attitude towards usage, which in turn creates the customers intention to use the e-banking. However, the perceived complexity that is, the difficulty of using e-banking influences the users' intention to adopt. Research suggest that the intention to adopt e-banking can be inhibited by the perceived ease of use and perceived complexity of use (Au and Kauffman 2008). With these beliefs, users may be inhibited to use

e-banking if they find it complex requiring more mental effort and time-consuming. A usable e-banking system is also associated with little difficulty in managing it. Thus, this has led to perceived ease of use or complexity to be regarded as a critical factor toward predicting intention to use a technology (Davis 1989; Teo *et al.* 2003)

* Perceived Trust: PT is regarded to as the willingness to be vulnerable to the actions of another individual to group of people; ability, benevolence and integrity are trust unique characteristics. It based on the expectation that the promise of other person can be relied upon and that, the person will act in a spirit of goodwill and in a benign fashion toward the trust in unforeseen circumstances (Mayer *et al.*, 1995). Trust is perhaps a crucial variable in an electronic environment. For example, online banking environment due to the higher perception of about the uncertainty and the risk involved, and the greater threat of likely inappropriate behaviours such as security failure making it possible for hackers stealing important private information (Suh and Han, 2002). Hence, the perceived trust will play a vital role in influencing customer attitude towards adopting the e-banking services or otherwise.

* Perceived Security: this attribute refers to the degree to which an individual adopter's belief in the security of the e-banking services strongly influence the customers behaviour towards adoption of its components, services and products. The security failure may cause the adopters or users of the e-banking services financial losses, as a result, customers are more likely to adopt e-banking services unless they have trust that the negative possibilities of the transaction on the internet will not occur, with this, it is more likely that the e-banking services will be adopted.

* Quality of Internet Connection: This construct refers to the degree at which the internet connection for e-banking services enables e-banking transaction completion. This is regarded as a very crucial component for online based transactions. Banking customers requires a good speedy internet connection to fast tract e-banking transactions since internet banking is considered the most adopted, prominent and patronised e-banking distribution channel in Nigeria. So, the way the customer perceived the internet quality for the e-banking distribution channels will affect their adoption and usage.

* Perceived Risk: regarded as the degree of risks in using an innovation (Ram and Sheth 1989). The degree to which the customers perceive occurs because of the doubt of inconsistency between users' judgment, real behaviour, and the information technology inability to deliver its expected outcome and its consequent loss (Koenig-Lewis 2010). The perception of risk is more important in e-banking adoption due to the privacy and security

threat prominent in e-banking environment (Al-Jabri and Sohail 2012). For example, users may fear that hackers are likely to access banks' accounts through loss/stolen PIN codes. Hence, the customers' perceived risk about e-banking service or distribution channels are more likely to affect their uptake and attitude towards adoption. This perceived risk can be in six types: financial, time, safety, confidentiality, performance and psychological (Awara and Anyadigbibe 2014).

2.5.2 Researches that Inform the Conceptual Framework Development

Table 2.9 summarises the list of authors whose work has helped in developing the conceptual model. The selection of these authors and their studies listed in the table was because they are authors that their research has impacted the development of this study conceptual framework significantly.

Table 2.9

Authors whose work has helped in the developing the Conceptual Framework

Authors	Titles	Journal	Findings
Inegbedion (2018)	Factors that influence customer attitude toward electronic banking in Nigeria	Journal of internet commerce	Ease of use, internet knowledge and transaction nature influence e-banking adoption
Tarhini <i>et al.</i> (2015)	User adoption of online banking in Nigeria.	Internet banking and commerce journal	Security, culture and religion are influences uptake of e-banking
Agwu (2017)	Analysis of the emergent issues in internet banking adoption in Nigeria	International journal of information, business and management	Security, privacy and infrastructure (internet) influence electronic banking adoption
Agwu, Simon and Onwuka (2016)	Mobile Banking – Adoption and Challenges in Nigeria	International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences and Humanities Research	Security, ease of use, accessibility and awareness of e-banking influence adoption.
Omotayo and Dahunsi (2015).	Factors Affecting Adoption of Point of Sale Terminals by Business Organisations in Nigeria	International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences	Perceived ease of use and social norms have significant relationship with POS adoption
Agwu (2017)	Empirical analysis of retail customers adoption of E-banking service in Nigeria	Internet banking and commerce journal	Security, privacy, infrastructure, income and education significantly affect adoption of e-banking
Agwu, <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Impediments to e-banking services marketing in developing economies – a case study of Nigeria banks	European Journal of Business and Social Sciences	Poor educational imbalance and lack of adequate policy framework affect e-banking adoption
Onyia and Tagg (2011)	Effect of demographic factors on bank customers attitudes and intension towards internet banking adoption in a major developing African country	Journal of Financial Service Marketing	gender, level of education, and employment status showed significant ability to influence Nigerian customers' attitude
Adeshina and Ayo (2010)	An empirical investigation of the level of users' acceptance of e-banking in Nigeria	Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce	Network security and system privacy affect e-banking usage

2.6 Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

Having discussed the theoretical and conceptual framework informing the study in the preceding section, this chapter aims to examine how customer relationship management influence e-banking adoption. In this part, the concept of customer relationship management will be discussed as an important tool necessary to improve e-banking adoption. The reason behind this discussion is to develop better understanding of the relationship between CRM in the context of e-banking.

Customer relationship management (CRM) is a concept that has undergone varying conceptual metamorphosis. CRM is a term used for customer relationship management, and researchers vary greatly in respect to their conceptualization of CRM depending on their context of usage. Hamidi and Safareeyeh (2019) stated that authors used different definitions for CRM and depending on the context; tactical and narrower definitions are used at one end, and strategic and wider definitions used at the other end. Some authors perceive it as processes (Nguyen, Sherif and Newby, 2007; Keramati *et al.*, 2010), while some refers to CRM to mean strategies (Chalmeta, 2006; Payne and Frow, 2005), or internal factors (Alt and Puschmann, 2006; King and Burgess, 2008). Chen and Ching (2004) suggest that CRM can best be defined as a process that uses technologies to find, analyse and share information for the better insight of the consumer needs and creation of insightful relationships. Storr, *et al.* (2009) further defined CRM as a combination of technology and business processes that enables organizations to understand various aspects of their customers much better. Despite the discrepancies in literature regarding CRM conceptualisation, the most important thing about the definitions is that they share the same goal of better relationship. Thus, the researcher has decided to ignore the discrepancies surrounding the definitions and use any of the authors definition to support CRM discussion as an important tool to promote e-banking adoption.

According to Rigby and Bilodeau, (2015) CRM have continued to be the number one most critical management tool by usage. The ability of any financial institutions to create and maintain customer relationship management (CRM) is a key determinant which strongly impact e-banking service and in turn boost customer confidence in the service provider. According to Zhao (2015) it is important for banks to provide quality service to customers and understand customer needs through CRM to increase customer satisfaction, maintain and build strong customer relationship. The paradigm shifts in business environment characterised with increased competition and advancement in IT has motivated organisations to utilize CRM as a core business strategy for customer satisfaction, loyalty, retention and increase profit (Diffley

et al., 2018; Santouridis and Tsachtani, 2015). Organisations not excluding the banking institutions are creating, offering and delivering values to customers by adopting collaborative CRM approach that can help organisations achieve better insight of customers' need and design quality service that meet their expectations (Vargo and Lusch, 2008).

Banks are using various channels to deliver efficiency, value addition, consistency, customization and personalization services. Banking organisations are changing to customer-centric approach from an account-centric one by leveraging customer relationship management technologies and related processes necessary to manage the relationship to create positive relationship (Sivaraks, *et al.*, 2011), which can improve e-banking adoption. Furthermore, the emergence of new collaborative technologies and channels otherwise known as CRM 2.0 (Greenberg, 2010), necessitates banks to engage in continuous interactions with customers at every stage of their relationship spectrum resulting into deeper collaboration and improved understanding of needs (Payne, *et al.*, 2008). Hidayanti, *et al.*, (2018) and Cambra-Fierro *et al.*, (2017) noted that CRM technologies along with customers has led to continuous dialogue, ease of access, collaborative learning value creation.

Kotler and Keller (2011) further argued that in today's digital age organisations must be customer-centric (render superior service) to customers and adept in (CRM) to succeed in long-term. Similarly, Woodcock *et al.* (2011), states that the electronic banking era is a new opportunity for commercial institutions to create online relationships with consumers through their chosen channels, and stay in touch with them, when they are playing, travelling and working. Customer relationship management is the methods, technologies, and the e-commerce abilities used by banks for managing bank-customers relationship (Stone and Woodcock, 2001 cited in Hamidi and Safareeyeh, 2019). On this premise, it is therefore important for banking institutions to adopt CRM to understand how to facilitate the customers to use and adapt to new e-banking products and services, as CRM remains an important strategic tool that can help improve customers' e-banking product adoption.

2.6.1 Customer Satisfaction- Key Determinants of Electronic Banking

In the previous part, the concept of customer relationship management was discussed, and it was shown that CRM is a very significant tool to build bank-customer relationship, and a critical factor that can impact e-banking service usage. This part investigated customer satisfaction as key determinant of e-banking services and products. Customer satisfaction is regarded as key determinant factors in e-banking and banks use different medium toward customizing products and services to meet customer needs (Cabanillas *et al.*, 2013). Customer

satisfaction is regarded as a fundamental determinant of long-term consumer behaviour (Paulo, Tiago and Farisa 2019). From cumulative satisfaction perspective, it is considered as the overall experience with interface, product and services (Jun and Palacios 2016). Managers use customer satisfaction as customer-oriented metrics due to its generic nature and its measurability for products and services (Gupta and Zeithml, 2006). In this respect, it can be considered as a key factor for e-banking usage.

To understand how customer satisfaction is a key determinant of e-banking, the researcher looked at the various definition of CS to help in understanding customer satisfaction as an impediment factor to e-banking usage according to literature.

Number of varying definitions have been proposed for customer satisfaction but linked to customers' loyalty (Fornell, 1992). Customer satisfaction is building and maintaining strong customer relationship (Blattberg, *et. al*, 2009). According to Kotler and Keller (2011), customer satisfaction is the feedback of before-purchase evaluation of a particular service/product's quality and compared with the expectation of the prior-purchasing stage. Customer satisfaction can be described as the relationship between the perceived value (PV) of service and the expected value (EV) by customers. Customer is said to be regarded as a satisfied customer when the perceived value of services matches customer perceived expected value. Moreso, customer satisfaction is perceived as "the extent to which a product's perceived performance matches a buyer's expectation" (Kotler and Armstrong 2013, p. 37).

Majority of the researchers concludes that customer satisfaction refers to the attitude or evaluation formed by a customer comparing pre-purchase expectations of what they would receive from the product or service to their subjective perceptions of the performance they receive (Hamound, *et al*. 2018). Measures of overall customer satisfaction typically capture consumer expectations towards the service provided, as well how service received inform their ideal (Soderlund, 2006). In line with these definitions, and as far as this study is concerned, customer satisfaction is regarded as customer attitude exhibited in response to adopting any of the E-banking services and products or channels.

According to literature customer satisfaction is a critical factor that determine e-banking adoption as CS hold the potential to increase e-banking usage (Cabanillas *et al.*, 2013). The ease of use of use, the communication and the support offer by banks to ensure positive customer experience add value to customer which in turn lead or determine their decision to adopt or ignore e-banking. Literature on CS established that CS is key determinant of a technology adoption where service quality is superior. Therefore, to better understand how

customer satisfaction is a key determinant factor of e-banking this study consider the relationship between customer satisfaction and e-banking service quality in the next section for broader perspective.

2.6.2 Customer Satisfaction and E-Banking Service Quality

In the previous section, the concept of customer satisfaction was briefly explained, and it was shown that customer satisfaction is an important concept in electronic banking context. This section will examine the relationship between customer satisfaction and usage of e-banking services. One of the main objectives of this research is to examine the most patronised or used channels. The reason for this it to determine the extent to which the e-banking service quality offered through various channels would influence adoption.

Quality service is the root of customers' satisfaction and result in customers' behavioural outcomes (Yavas, Benkenstein, and Stuhldreier, 2014). E-service quality is the efficiency and effectiveness purchased by customers of electronic services (Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Malhotra 2002). Ranaweera and Neely (2003) confirmed that E-service quality is the first step of customers' satisfaction. Broadly speaking, feeling of satisfaction arises when customers compare their perception of actual product/service performance with expectations (Oliver 1980 cited in Hammoud, *et al.*, 2018). Piyathananan, *et al.*, (2015) highlighted that customer satisfaction has become guiding principle for banks, as they continuously initiate different processes to provide superior customer value. According to Chu, Lee and Yu (2012) to ensure customer satisfaction in banking context, e-service quality is fundamental. Premium service is needed to achieve high customer satisfaction level that often result in a favourable behavioural intention.

Many studies such as Hammoud (2018); Asiyambi and Ishola (2018) and Blut, *et al.* (2015) point out to the relationship between e-service quality and customer satisfaction. For example, Hammoud (2018) established that E-banking service quality has positive impact on the degree of customer satisfaction. According to Blut, *et al.* (2015) strong relationship exist between e-service quality, customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. Indeed, Tsao, Hsieh and Lin (2016) also conclude that e-service quality has significant effects on customer perceived value, which in turn has positive influence on their satisfaction. A recent study Asiyambi and Ishola (2018) also demonstrated that the degree of banks customers satisfaction increases as E-Banking service usage increases. Hence, the specific e-banking service quality dimensions that the study consider having influence on e-banking usage are identified in the next section.

2.6.3 Dimensions of E-Banking Services Affecting Customer Satisfaction

The pioneering studies of consumer service quality Parasuraman *et al.* (2005) developed updated version of the traditional SERVQUAL model called Electronic Service Quality (E-SQUAL) comprising four dimensions; reliability, efficiency, privacy and responsiveness considered as factors that strongly affects consumers perceptions of service quality in e-banking context. Therefore, this study used these four dimensions as the electronic banking service quality that influence or affect a-banking adoption. Table 2.10 presents the literature evidence of the electronic service quality dimensions.

Dimensions	Definitions and literature evidence
Reliability	(e.g. Santos 2003; Hussien, 2013; Rehman 2012; Zafar, Zaheer and Rehman 2011; Hammoud, <i>et al.</i> 2018.
Efficiency	(e.g. Parasuraman <i>et al.</i> , 2005; Santos 2003; Khadem and Mousavi 2013)
Privacy and security	Perceived risk, fraud, cyber-attack (e.g. Parasuraman <i>et al.</i> 2005; Akinci <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Jayawardhena 2004; Jun and Palacios, 2016; Hammoud, <i>et al.</i> 2018)
Responsiveness and communication	Timely response, complaints, prompt service (e.g. Zeithaml, Parasuraman, and Malhotra 2001; Tahira <i>et al.</i> 2012; Amin, 2016; Ayo <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Hammoud, <i>et al.</i> 2018; Tabash 2019)
Ease of Use (EoU)	Hassle-free, flexible and simple, convenience, accessibility; user-friendly (e.g. Garg <i>et al.</i> 2014; Jun and Palacios, 2016; Hammoud, <i>et al.</i> 2018; Tabash, <i>et al.</i> 2019)

Table 2.10
Past studies on E-service dimension affecting customer satisfaction

Reliability: Reliability is the first e-service quality dimension proposed by Parasuraman *et al.* (2005) and Santos (2003). It is regarded as “the ability of the service provider to perform the promised services accurately and consistently” (Parasuraman *et al.*, 2005, p. 23). The reliability is one of the strong factors that have significant relationship with overall service quality as confirmed by researchers (Tabash, *et al.* 2019), ranked the most significant e-banking service quality dimensions (Hussien, 2013). In electronic service context, the consistency in offering quality services (Pakdil *et al.*, 2012), the accuracy in delivering promised services and availability of error-free services (Saccani *et al.*, 2014) have direct influence on consumers to patronise, stay or leave a service provider which then impact customers’ satisfaction positively or negatively. Processing transaction in a timely manner and providing accurate e-banking service cost are core factors which also contribute to the success of adopting an e-banking service or otherwise, and which can equally result to retaining customers (Shankar and Kumari, 2016).

Efficiency: This is the next e-service dimension that impact customer satisfaction. Easy accessibility free of struggle for any service is admired by customers and would be perceived as a determining factor for service quality. Efficiency is one of the dimensions proposed by Parasuraman *et al.* (2005) and Santos (2003) to measuring E-services quality. This described as speed of accessing and using the e-banking services. Speed in performing E-Banking services is a determining factor of customer satisfaction (Parasuraman, *et al.* 2005). In the e-banking world, there is no face-to-face (direct) interactions between the provider of service (banks) and the customers which creates raise concerns for the privacy and security when performing financial transactions on the internet or website (Al-Hawari, 2014). According to Thaichon, *et al.*, (2014) and Shankar and Kumari, (2016) if e-service providers keep personal information of customers safe and ensure safe transactions, customers will tend to trust them, while this will help generate positive customer response that will also promote customer satisfaction.

Privacy and Security: This dimension is one of the main e-services quality dimensions identified by Hammoud, *et al.* (2018); Parasuraman *et al.* (2005) and Santos (2003), it is refer to as “the degree to which customers believe that the site is safe from intrusion and that personal information shared over the platform is protected” (Hussien and AbdEl Aziz, 2013, p. 561). Security and privacy are considered as an important dimension that positively or negatively impacts customer satisfaction in technology-based service. Jayawardhena (2004) stated that banks should ensure the security and privacy of customer information to gain their trust. With respect to privacy and security, Datta, (2010) and Hamound, *et al.* (2018) further identified that elements such as confidentiality maintenance, insuring good level of security for the customer’s information and refraining from sharing customers’ personal information are important.

Responsiveness; Responsiveness is the fourth major dimensions of service quality (Parasuraman, and Malhotra 2001). Responsiveness is the readiness to support and help customers, and provide them a rapid service (Tabash, 2019). Responsiveness is identified as an important e-service quality dimension in e-banking context (Tahira *et al.*2012). Some researchers such as Hamound, *et al.* (2018) and Tabash *et al.*, (2019) found responsiveness very important for overall service quality and customer’s satisfaction. Their research suggests that the service provider ability to provide effective information to customers to be able to provide online warranties and prevent any inconveniencies would influence customers decision to use e-banking service. In addition, the problem-solving services of the e-service providers reflect their responsiveness to customers problem and their transaction process quality. Responsiveness is assured by ensuring availability and accessibility of e-banking service

offerings in a timely manner and providing interactive decision support tools that enables financial transaction through the internet (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2002) Furthermore, the service support given to resolve customers complaints and the speedy response if they encounter a problem while using e-banking services will impact their satisfaction. For example, when banks update their websites, their customers tend to seek technical support (Thaichon *et al.*, 2014), where quick and efficient response is provided to the customer by the online customer care support team then customers tend to trust the e-service providers (Quach *et al.*, 2016). In turn, customers will be satisfied and remain loyal to them. This experience can then affect customer experience and satisfaction positively or otherwise.

Ease of Use (EoU); EoU is the key dimensions of e-service quality (Kassimand Abdullah, 2010; Tabash *et al.* 2019). It is among the new dimension suggested for measuring e-service dimension proposed in for technology-related service (see table above). EoU is found as a strong service quality measurement dimension (Yang *et al.*, 2004; Hammoud, *et al.* 2018). Four items depict ease of use of bank e-service quality, easy access to the bank website online; user-friendly bank website; easy navigation of bank website and easy way on the bank website (Kassimand Abdullah, 2010).

In all, customer satisfaction play is a key significant factor that determine e-banking adoption and the service quality of the e-banking services impact customers experience. This study provides that customers will evaluate the e-banking service quality of each of the dimensions identified; reliability, efficiency, privacy and security, and responsiveness to determine whether they are adopting or rejecting an e-banking product and service. Conversely, satisfied customers tend to maintain a sustainable relationship with e-service provider by regularly purchasing its products and services (Kashif *et al.* 2015), and lower perceived e-service quality leads to higher dissatisfaction which hinder the relationship between e-banking providers and customers, and in turn affect e-banking service usage.

2.7 CONCLUSION

This chapter presented a critical review of literature on e-banking adoption. First, technology and global banking transformation including the Nigeria experience were provided to understand how technology has transformed the Nigeria banking section and the regulatory challenges facing the e-banking practices in the banking sector. The second section provided the concept and definition of e-banking including the benefits and challenges of e-banking adoption.

In the next section, e-banking adoption rate including the various channels were provided and compared to ascertain the rate of penetration of e-banking globally and in Nigeria. ATM, Internet Banking, Telephone Banking, Electronic Fund transfer, POS, PC banking and home banking in section 2.3.1 were all discussed in detailed. The trend performance of e-banking channels was also provided in section 2.3.2 to ascertain the most patronised of the E-banking channels, products and services. The literature review provided evidence that the ATM is the most patronised e-banking in Nigeria. Also, that security, privacy, infrastructure, cost, ease of use, accessibility, culture, religion and lack of regulatory framework are factors affecting e-banking in Nigeria.

In the fourth section, the theoretical review was provided to determine the theories underpinning the study. This led to proposed theoretical model for the study using some constructs of the TAM (Davies, 1989) and IDT (Rogers, 1995). Furthermore, has demonstrated through the literature review that some constructs of TAM, IDT and demographic factors could be integrated to form a conceptual framework for examining e-banking adoption and customer satisfaction in the Nigeria banking sector. The last section presented Customer Relationship Management (CRM) to show that CRM is a critical factor that can impact e-banking adoption.

In sum, the researcher has been able to examine the literature that traces the development and influences affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. It becomes apparent from the literature review that this chapter has enhanced the understanding of e-banking in the global and in Nigeria context which is one of the major concerns of this research. Therefore, the next chapter presents the methodological approach adopted to fill out the gap of lack of studies examining factors affecting e-banking adoption using TAM and DIT identified in the literature review above.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter detailed the methodological approach of the research in line with the previous literature review and present the practices that the researcher used to investigate this study to attain a justifiable outcome for the research questions. The chapter begins by providing the purpose of the research. The research design and methods employed to gather information for the research were discussed. The chapter goes on to evaluate various research philosophy leading to the choice of pragmatism and justification for the choice of pragmatism for the research provided. There is a discussion of the research approach, the research methods, the sample selection, data collection and how the research is analysed, including the study limitations, followed by a chapter summary.

3.1.1 Research Purpose

This chapter detailed the methodological approach of the research. The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that affect customers towards E-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector and recommend future e-banking strategies that can be applied across the Nigerian banking sector. The thesis research problem as provided in section 1.2 (Chapter One), and the research questions formulated within the scope of the thesis are:

- Research Question One: What are the influences affecting the development of e-banking adoption in Nigeria?
- Research Question Two: What factors are currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector?
- Research Question Three: What are the customers most patronized e-banking channels in Nigeria?
- Research Question Four: How can e-banking adoption rate be improved in the Nigeria banking sector?

The research purpose was determined through the research questions highlighted above. The type of research; explanatory, exploratory, co-relational and descriptive is known from the nature of the research questions (Kumar, 2005). The specific purpose of this thesis is to examine factors that influence customers' attitude towards e-banking adoption. The literature review clearly indicates that E-banking studies in less developed countries are lacking and not

sufficiently research. This enables this mixed-method research with exploratory and descriptive purposes. Section 3.2 below discussed the research design and methodology for the study.

3.2 Research Design and Methodology

This section discussed the research design employed for this research. Research design is defined as the plan of the study, serving as the overall strategic framework for data collection procedure, research questions and execution of research strategy (Durheim, 2004). For Yin (2011), the research design is the blueprint of research or steps and procedures undertaken by the researcher to address the research questions. According to Yin, (2003) it is a logical sequence that connects the empirical data to a study’s initial research question and ultimately to its conclusion. Thus, this research adopted Sanders *et al.* (2009) research process “onion” to give direction to the study and guide the investigator in the process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting data. The onion encompasses different layers serving as the basis for the philosophical approach; the research approach adopted; the research strategies employed; the research's choices; the research timeline; and the research techniques and procedures. Figure 3.1 present an overview of the research design for this study, and the rest of this section discusses other important components of the research design.

Figure 3.1
Research Design

Source: Researcher’s Composition

3.3 Research Philosophy

There are various research philosophies considered when undertaking a research. The development of the research background, research knowledge and the research nature are known as the research philosophy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2008). According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, (2009) the research philosophy adopted contains important assumptions about a social reality, the assumptions underpin the research strategy and the methods chosen as part of the strategy. Research philosophy is fundamental for the researcher because it has impact on the choice of methodology and the data collection methods (Collis and Hussey, 2003), it shows the beliefs of the researcher on a social reality (Creswell, 2009). In this section, the research philosophy underpinning this study was presented and the most appropriate philosophical stance suggested appropriate for this study was explained in the next section.

Research philosophy, worldviews or paradigm underpinning a research are positivism; realism; interpretivism; and pragmatism (see table 3.1), characterized according to their methodological assumptions. Considering the various philosophies including their beliefs, this research adopted the pragmatist philosophy. This research philosophy helped the researcher to clarify the research designs to ascertain the data type needed; enable this study to know how to source and interpret data; and helped the researcher to adopt and generate appropriate research design that was outside the researcher's experience.

Table 3.1

The fundamental belief and characteristics of the research paradigms.

Fundamental beliefs	Research Paradigms			
	Positivism	Realism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
<i>Ontology</i> : the position of the nature of reality	External, objective and independent of social actors	Objective. Exist independently of human thoughts and beliefs or knowledge of their existence but is interpreted through social conditioning (critical realist)	Socially constructed, subjective, may change, multiple	External multiple, view chosen to best ensure answering of research questions
<i>Epistemology</i> : the view on what constitutes acceptable knowledge	Only observable phenomena can provide credible data, fact. Focus on causality and law-like generalizations, reducing phenomena to simplest elements	Only observable phenomena can provide credible data and facts. Focus on explaining within a context or contexts	Subjective meanings and social phenomena. Focus upon the details of situation, the reality behind these details, subjective meanings motivating actions	Either or both observable phenomena and subjective meanings can provide acceptable knowledge dependent upon the research question. Focus on practical applied research, integrating different perspectives to help interpret the data
<i>Axiology</i> : the role of values in research and the researcher's strand (stance)	Value-free and etic Research is undertaken in a value-free way, the researcher is	Value-laden and etic Research is value laden; the researcher is biased by world views, cultural	Value-bond and emic Research is value bond, the researcher is part of what is being researched, cannot be	Value-bond and etic-emic Research is values play a large role in interpreting results, the researcher

	independent of the data and maintains an objective stance	experiences and upbringing.	separated hence will be subjective	adopt both objective and subjective points of view
<i>Research Methodology</i> : the model behind the research process	Larger sample size, mostly Quantitative method, but can use qualitative	Quantitative or Qualitative method	Small sample size, depth investigations but Qualitative method	Quantitative and Qualitative method (mixed or multiple method)

Source: Guba and Lincoln (2005), Hallebone and Priest (2009), Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2015).

The choice of either Epistemology, Ontology or Axiology guided research approach and the differences between them influenced how the researcher conduct the research process (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Ontology is the view of how one perceives a reality, distinguishes between objectivism and subjectivism and answer the question ‘what is’. Epistemology is a philosophy branch that concerns the beliefs on the way of generating, understanding and using the knowledge that are deemed to be accepted and valid in a study, and answer questions ‘how’ and ‘what’ (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Positivism is related to quantitative methods, interpretivism related to qualitative research, pragmatism linked to qualitative and quantitative method, and realism related to qualitative or quantitative method. The Axiology is one of the major branches of research philosophy that relies so much on value to make judgements. This researcher adopted the Epistemology belief to identify the most suitable research philosophy for this study. Essentially, the adoption of the epistemology paradigm to this study necessitates the discussion of possible approach- pragmatism within epistemology in order to justify the chosen research method for this thesis. The pragmatism philosophical approach choice is explained in sub-section 3.3.1 below.

3.3.1 Pragmatism

Pragmatism philosophy believes that a research philosophy should be view as a continuum, and not an option that stands in opposite positions. The pragmatist argued that objectivist and subjectivist perspectives are not mutually exclusive, thus mixture of ontology, epistemology and axiology approach should be used for better understanding of the social reality. Pragmatist advocates for what work best to address the research problem (Wahyuni, 2012). Pragmatism is beyond a philosophical position but a set of philosophical tools for answering research questions and orientates itself towards solving real world problem (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Pragmatism is not committed to any single system of philosophy and reality. Researchers have freedom of choice to choose their research methodologies including the research procedures and techniques that best meet the purpose of the research (Creswell 2014). On this note, this study embraced the pragmatism philosophy, as this philosophy allowed the use of mixed method both quantitative and qualitative data for better understanding of the social

phenomenon (reality). The mixed method approach provides the researcher the opportunity to examine the perception of individual banks customer on e-banking thereby making the researcher gained deep knowledge of the subject matter.

From the nature of reality (ontology) and nature of knowledge (epistemology), investigating e-banking adoption has its strand in the pragmatism philosophical approach. This is because exploring the factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria can best be understandable a large sample size, using both objective and subjective point of view and using quantitative and qualitative data through a mixed method. Therefore, the positivist one-way observation and measurement approach was not adopted in this study because the bank customer's perception towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria cannot be disregarded, condemned or ignored. For this reason, a mixed methodological approach of the pragmatist is therefore suggested as the most suitable philosophical approach for this study.

3.3.2 Justification for choice of Pragmatism

This research study has chosen the pragmatist philosophical stance. As discussed above, the study of this nature on investigation of e-banking adoption cannot fit in to the positivist methodological stance because the focus of this study is not exploring the numeric (number) of customers that have accepted E-banking but an investigation of the bank customers' perception regarding adoption factors. The pragmatism was considered suitable for this research because it allows multiple data sources.

In addition, the pragmatists applies different approach to investigate a social reality, for this reason, and with the nature of this study, the study can perfectly fit into this philosophical stance using both the objective and subjective approach and the mixed methodology approach of the pragmatist because it accurately capture the aims and objectives of the research. Furthermore, the pragmatism approach has also been chosen as it was very useful for this study, it enabled this research to link theory with practice through survey strategy. An approach adopted by this research to capture the following objectives demanded by this study:

- The utilization of primary source to explore the development and influences affecting e-banking development in Nigeria
- The application of mixed methods for investigation into the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria in 2 banking locations.
- The incorporation of individual bank customer's perception towards the adoption of e-banking products/services.

- Analysis of the data collected to discover key findings about banking customers' e-banking experiences in Nigeria.

3.4 Research Approach

Research approaches are plans and the procedures for research that span the steps from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This plan involves several decisions, and they need to be taken in the order in which they make sense (Cresswell, 2008). The research approach enables the researcher to take a more informed decision about the research design; help researcher to identify the research strategies and choices that will work and those that will not; and it enables adaptability of the research design to cater for constraints (Easterby-Smith *et. al.*, 2008). This study employed both deductive and inductive approaches, as this this approach has its position in the pragmatism philosophy (Creswell, 2013; Saunders *et. al.* 2015). Details of the research approach employed was explained in the next sub-section.

3.4.1 Deductive Approach

The deductive approach is a process by which one arrives at a reasonable conclusion by consideration of known facts (Sekaran, 2003), involves developing a theory that is subjected to a rigorous test (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Deductive denotes reasoning from the particular to the general (Gulati, 2009). This study employed deductive approach in which theory and research questions are developed, and research strategy was developed due to the necessity of answering the research questions regarding factors affecting and influencing customers towards e-banking adoption constructed in the conceptual framework. The researcher has been able to use deductive approach to identify the gaps in knowledge.

3.4.2 Inductive Approach

In inductive research one observes certain phenomena and based on the observations certain conclusions are reached (Sekaran, 2003). This approach involves moving from individual observation to statements of general patterns or laws; this is referred to as moving from the specific to the general (Collis and Hussey, 2003). According to Gill and Johnson (2002, p. 43) "it is possible to construct a continuum of research methods that allows us to differentiate between different methods in terms of the various logics they bring to bear in conducting research. That is, we can discriminate between different methods in terms of their relative emphasis upon deduction or induction, their degree of structure, the kinds of data they generate and the forms of explanation they create". This study essentially used inductive approach to collect data and theory was developed from the data analysis. The Inductive approach

employed enabled the researcher to use open-ended questions to ask general questions from the participants, and the participants shaped the response possibilities.

3.5 Research Strategy – Survey

Different strategies can be employed in researching about a research whether exploratory, descriptive and, or explanatory research (Yin, 2003). The research strategies are known as the different ways of collecting and analyzing an empirical evidence of the research area. They are regarded as the roadmap towards achieving the goals of a research and answering the research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). It includes experiment, survey, case study, action research, grounded theory, ethnography, and archival research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009; Creswell 2012). No research strategy is inherently superior or inferior to any other they all have their approach to collecting and analyzing empirical data, hence each one has its own strength and weaknesses. The survey strategy allows variety of methods for recruiting participants, collecting data and use various instrumentation methods (Singleton and Straits, 2009). This study employed survey strategy for the research because of the explorative-descriptive nature of this thesis, and the most common strategy for business and management studies (Saunders *et. al.* 2015). The studies of Xiao (2017) and Agwu (2014) have used this survey approach in their research.

Furthermore, the thesis adopted survey strategy because it helps the researcher to gain in-depth understanding of the research area through survey questionnaire and interview questions, help to provide this study with deep understanding of the bank customers about influencing factors inhibiting e-banking uptake. Survey research is a viable approach for research that have the benefits of helping to explore and describe constructs/variables such as those highlighted in the conceptual framework of this thesis.

3.6 Research Choices- Mixed Research Methods

The research choices could be mono methods, mixed methods, or multi-methods is very important for a research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). According to Creswell, (2008) the approach to inquiry that incorporates both qualitative and quantitative forms is mixed methods, it entails philosophical assumptions, the use of qualitative and quantitative approaches and mixing both approaches in a study. This study employed convergent parallel mixed method (qualitative and quantitative approaches) to understand the research problem better and give room for triangulating data sources i.e process of finding convergence of both qualitative and quantitative methods (Creswell, 1998; Jick, 1979). The Mixed methods was

necessary because neither the quantitative nor qualitative method was sufficient by themselves to capture the research area in detail.

Rather than using the single method, the two methods was appropriately integrated to fit into the research area thereby promoting triangulation of data used. Thus, the mixed method was suitable for the research as it gives rigor and breadth to the research area and provides confirmatory evidences for data obtained. In addition, the researcher considered the mixed method research as the most suitable research because it offers the researcher the ability to use survey strategy to gather the primary data of the study quantitatively and qualitatively as stated;

1. Data collection from 250 Nigerian bank retail customers through survey questionnaire. The use of a survey questionnaire is considered suitable for sample size (Mathers, Fox and Hunn, 2009). These customers perception on the factors affecting and influencing their adoption of e-banking using some of the characteristics of Rogers Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) and Davies Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).
2. The integration of data collection via in-depth interviews of 10 e-banking users that uses e-banking products/services. The qualitative method was employed to provide in-depth insight about e-banking users' perspective about e-banking in Nigeria. Vital issues including the rationale for the adoption, the available e-banking channels, customers/users' level of patronage, security issue among others were discussed. The qualitative method also provides in-depth insights about the motives, needs, value and satisfaction level and behaviour of the respondents.

In sum, this research study used the convergent parallel mixed methods to investigate e-banking adoption by the Nigerian bank customers (*see* Fig 3.2). The convergent parallel mixed-method allows the researcher to conduct the quantitative and qualitative aspect of the research concurrently, analyse their results independently and interpret their results together (Creswell and Pablo-Clark, 2011). The study adopted the CPMM because the primary aim of this research work was to conduct an independent empirical investigation of e-banking adoption in Nigeria using mixed methods.

Figure 3.2:
Convergent Mixed Method Adopted

Having presented the convergent mixed method of the study, table 3.2 below shows clearer picture of practical convergence mixed method integrated and utilized in this the study.

Table 3.2:

Visual Model Convergent Parallel Mixed Methods Utilized

	Steps	Procedure	Product
Step 1	Quantitative Data Collection	*Cross-Sectional survey questionnaire (n = 250)	* Numeric data
	Quantitative Data Analysis and Result	* Data Screening * Frequencies * Reliability Analysis * Correlation Analysis * SPSS Quantitative software V 22	* Descriptive Statistics
Step 2	Qualitative Data Collection	*In-depth face-to-face interview (n = 10) * Through developed interview questions	* Interview transcript * Documentation
	Qualitative Data Analysis and Result	*Coding and thematic analysis *Within and Across case developed *Cross thematic * Power and Rener (2003) approach	*Themes and code development * Similar and different themes categorization
Step 3	Compare, contrast and relate quantitative and qualitative results	*Content area identified in QUAN and QUAL data set identified * Results differences and similarities identified * Result similarities incorporated/merged together	
Step 4	Interpretation of merged results	*QUNT and QUAL result interpreted separately * discussion of extent and ways QUAN and QUAL results converge, diverge and relate to produce complete understanding *Conclusion drawn * Recommendation * Implications * Future research	

Source: (Creswell and Pablo-Clark 2011; Cook and Kamalodeen, 2019).

3.6.1 Benefits of Parallel Mixed-Method Research Design

The benefits of a parallel mixed-method research design are:

- Parallel mixed-methods enables the researcher to converge or merge the quantitative and qualitative data to derive a holistic inquiry of the research question (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2015).
- Offers the researcher opportunity to conduct the quantitative and qualitative components of the study concurrently or simultaneously in the same phase of the research process, analyzes the two elements independently and interprets the results together (Creswell and Pablo-Clark, 2011).
- Enables the triangulation of different data methods by directly comparing the quantitative statistical results and the qualitative findings for corroboration and validation of their results.
- It prioritise methods of data independently and keep data analysis independently
- Helps to establish the convergence, divergence, contradiction or relationships between two data sources (Creswell and Pablo-Clark, 2011).

3.7 Research Ethics

Ethics are considered significant in a research process, and issues relating to protection of the participants are important (Marshall and Rossman, 2006). Ethics are philosophical system of beliefs and values (Swetnam and Swetnam, 2009). The integrity of a research is proportional to the ethical issues that are involved in the research (Bryman, 2016). The ethical issues in the research are privacy, confidentiality, anonymity, risk of harm and voluntary participation.

Essentially, this research was conducted in line with University of West of the Scotland Ethics Guidelines. The researcher applied and completed a research ethic form (see appendix D) prior to commencing this study to promote ethical practice in conducting academic research. The ethical form was filled by the researcher, signed by the research and the lead supervisor of this study before it was finally submitted to the University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee for approval. The researcher stated in the ethical form that the study will cause no distress-physical or psychological for the participants and their rights, feelings and welfare will be protected, and approval for the research was granted (Appendix E). The researcher employed proper safeguards to protect and ensure the rights of the participants. All collected information about participants were kept confidential and stored in a personal computer protected by passwords. Participants have the right to suspend or withdraw their participation at any time without giving reasons. To sum up, it can be concluded that this research has complied with

the ethical principles regarding this type of study as the ethical form was approved. The details of the access and participation of respondents are provided in sub-section 3.7.1 below.

3.7.1 Access and Participation

The researcher through the bank managers gained access to the respondents. The managers act on behalf of the researcher to get the list of customers that uses one form of e-banking products or the other and their phone numbers. They were asked for permission to take part in the study. Those that expressed their interest were sent consent letter through the bank managers' email. By so doing, the inconvenience of seeking participants directly by the researcher was completely avoided and the sample collection randomness was ensured to a larger extent. In all, approximately 192 access was gained through these managers. The researcher at the point of data collection seeks for additional 58 bank customers to make up the 250 respondents needed for the study. They were contacted face-to-face right in the banking hall to take part in the study. Consent letters were given, signed and returned to the researcher on the spot. The researcher was able to get the consent of the 58 additional customers because in Nigeria customers can easily be approached in the bank to seek participation once the researcher has necessary evidence for the research.

The questionnaires were distributed in the banking hall of the two banks selected for the study Guaranteed Trust Bank and First City Monument Bank, located in two geographical locations in Nigeria: Lagos and Ogun State. However, 74 (29.6%) of the questionnaire distributed were not appropriately filled, and the respondents are either not meet the qualified age for participation or not user of e-banking services and products. Thus, the total number of usable questionnaires dully filled amounted to 176 (70.4%).

3.8 Pilot Study

Prior to conducting the actual research, a pilot study was conducted to ensure the quality of the research instruments adopted for the study. A pilot study of the questionnaire is suggested very important (Pals, 2003). Pilot studies are “small-scale version/trial run perform in preparation for the main study (Polit *et al.* 2001). This study conducted a pilot study prior to the commencement of the actual study with twelve (12) participants in ratio 10:2 for pre-testing the instruments so that the participants do not have problem while answering the questions and no problem while recording the data. Participants in the pilot study were the banks customers who are users of e-banking products and services, who reside in Lagos and Ogun states, Nigeria. The pilot study data analysis yielded similar themes with the actual research.

After analyzing the pilot sample, the researcher revised the questionnaire and interview questions, rewrite the statements and change complicated statements to simpler statements to avoid vagueness, redirect the statements to serve as one issue and remove any conjunctions that may lead to misunderstanding. The exact changes made in the research instruments after conducting the pilot study are; changing some constructs in the first section of the questionnaire that were abbreviated such as PEOS (Perceived Ease of Use), PU (Perceived Usefulness); and changing some of the e-banking channels in section 3 such as POS, EFT to include their full meaning; including introductory letter (Appendix B) serving as a yard stick to take part in the study. The changes had positive impact on the instruments turning them to usable instruments finally used for the study. Thereafter, after the data analysis, the main study took place with face-to-face questionnaire administration and interviews. The investigator was able to meet and observe people in real life thereby informing the real research in large extent. Section 3.9 below covers the data sources and data collection technique of this thesis.

3.9 Data Sources and Data Collection Techniques and Procedure

Data can be sourced or collected in the form of primary and secondary data (Wahyuni, 2012). Data collection involves identifying and selecting individuals for a study, obtaining their permission to study them, and gathering information by asking people questions or observing their behaviors (Creswell, 2012). This study employed primary sources to collect data through well-structured questionnaires completed by banks customers and well-structured interviews to provide answer to the research questions. The study used questionnaire to generate data through questionnaires completed by two-fifty (250) customers of the two banks: GTB and FCMB banks who are e-banking users or those that have discontinued usage. The survey questionnaire alone was not sufficient by itself to provide suitable outcome for this research. As a result, interview was used to complement the questionnaire and add credibility to the research outcome.

The second source of data for this thesis was interviews conducted for participants in Lagos and Ogun, Nigeria based on the rigorous literature review carried out in chapter two- the literature review chapter of the thesis. The purpose of the interview was to gather data regarding influences affecting e-banking development in Nigeria (Research Question 1); and gather data relating to factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria (Question 2).

The data collection started with the recruitment of participants who met the research criteria. Participants needs to be e-banking users who are GTB or FCMB customers and who live in Lagos or Ogun state in Nigeria. All candidates considered suitable for the study were invited

to take part in the research. Participant information sheet detailed the research purpose and the conditions of the interview (Appendices A2) and the consent form (Appendix A3) were sent to participants who had expressed their interest to be part of the study. The consent forms were signed and email back through the bank managers. The questionnaire was distributed for the participants right in the banking hall during the break time and majority of the interviews was conducted face-to-face at locations that were considered convenient for the participants: banking hall, home and over the telephone. Each questionnaire lasted for 15 minutes and the interview took approximately 30- 45min.

The questionnaires and interviews were conducted in March 2019. Suitable themes that emerged in the interview conducted were used to explore and examine the area relevant to the research topic. The interview data were recorded via telephone-recording a method considered most convenient for the researcher at the time of the interview.

3.9.1 Questionnaire

This research carefully designed a well-structured questionnaire following the literature review in chapter two of this thesis. The literature review helped in extracting important points needed for the questionnaire to achieve the objective of the research. The questionnaire was divided into three sections A, B and C (*see* appendix B). Section ‘A’ was the main body of the questionnaire, it contains 23 statement and sought to investigate the factors influencing e-banking adoption from respondents. Section ‘B’ was part of the main questionnaire, it includes six closed-ended and one open-ended questions and sought to investigate the most patronized e-banking channels to achieve a realistic result relating to the research questions.

Specifically, questions in section ‘A’ and ‘B’ are required to be answered in line with Five (5) Likert Scale of SA (Strongly Agreed), A (Agreed), SD (Strongly Disagreed), D (Disagreed) and Undecided (U) was used for the closed-ended questions. Essentially, items in these sections were systematically formulated based on the research objectives and research, and prior e-banking studies. Specifically, section ‘C’ was designed to provide demographic data including genders, age, income, marital status, educational level, culture and religion of the respondents. The questionnaire was administered to individual bank customers through the approval of the bank managers.

3.9.2 Interviews

A semi-structured face-to-face interview with customers of Guaranteed Trust Bank and First City Monument Bank was conducted to ascertain the individual customer’s perception on

factors affecting and the most patronized e-banking channels. The in-depth semi-structured interview was conducted among 10 participants and helped to build rapport and dialogue among the researcher and the respondents. Semi-structure interview method was adopted for the thesis because one of the research objectives was to know factors that makes e-banking users to use or discontinue usage.

An interview schedule was designed and used to ask questions from the participants. The interview schedule serves as a guide for the interview and contained questions that requires answer for the research. The interview schedule was piloted and amended in the pilot study phase. The interview schedule comprises 12 open-ended questions, copy of the interview schedule used for the participants can be found in Appendix D. The participants were recruited through the help of the bank managers who supported the researcher with necessary assistance needed for the success of this research. Copies of the research approval letter from the bank managers (see Appendix E1 and E2) of this study. The participant recruited for the interview were users of one or more e-banking products and services and were asked questions in such a way that enabled the participants to express themselves. All interviews were conducted in English and conducted in the participants house, eateries or office in Lagos and Ogun state, Nigeria.

3.9.3 Data Collection Instruments Summary

A mixed method approach has been employed in this thesis to provide answer to the research questions stated in chapter one (sub-section 1.3.3) of study. Collecting data through the mixed method has helped to adds rigor, breadth and depth to this study and provided corroborative evidence to the data obtained. Table 3.3 below outlined the summary of the data collection techniques that was employed to address the research objectives of this research.

Table 3.3:
Data collection instrument summary

S/N	Data collection technique	Area captured in the objectives
1.	The Survey Questionnaire	This was used to: Examine individual customers perception on e-banking including its services and channels
2.	Semi-structured interview	This was used to: investigate the issues influencing customers adopting e-banking and development of e-banking

Author generated

Section 3.10 below covers the sampling technique and sampling size of this thesis.

3.10 Sampling Technique

Sampling techniques are regarded as the methods used to select representative from a population under study (William, 2016). According to Kumar, (2005) sampling technique in social research are three; random/probability sampling, non-random/probability sampling, and mixed sampling methods. Considering the various sampling techniques mentioned above, this study employed random and purposely sampling methods. This reasons for the blend of the random sampling also known as probability sampling and purposive sampling technique used for this study are due to the following:

- * there were 22 commercial banks operating in Nigeria to the best of the researcher's knowledge as at the time of this research. From this population, 2 branches of this banks namely; FCMB and GTB in Lagos and Ogun, all have their headquarters in Lagos State, the economic capital of Nigeria was randomly selected for the study. Furthermore, these two banks which are tier 1 banks were purposely selected from the 8 tier 1 banks with international authoritarian because they are big in size with large capital base, customer size and have the best e-banking practice among their counterparts.
- * selection of the individual bank customers that participated in the study were opportune to take part because only individual retail bank customers between 16 and 66 years who maintained a regular account with the new generation commercial banks participated in the study as long as they are adopter of one form of electronic banking or the other.
- * the purposive sampling technique employed guided the researcher in selecting the intended sample size needed for this research. The intended sample size of 250 was selected because experienced researchers will consider a sample size of between 200 and 1000 for a population of 10,000 and more (Sathye, 1999; Alreck and Settle 1995). Since the Nigeria banking customers are more than 10,000, thus target sample size of 250 was considered suitable to be a representative of the Nigerian population. Five (5) customers from each bank was proposed and form part of the population for in-depth and holistic knowledge about the research area and clearer picture of vital issues

3.11 Data Analysis

Data analysis is regarded as the process of applying statistical procedure to data that has been collected to draw meaningful conclusion (Bryman, 2016). To answer the research question of this study, collected data were analyzed statistically and descriptively. Specifically, the study used descriptive statistical analysis to analyze quantitative data. Descriptive statistics according

to Argyrous (1997:15) is the “the numerical and graphical techniques for organizing, presenting and analyzing data”. This study performed this form of analysis using Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS) version 22. Thematic content analysis was also adopted to analyse the qualitative data gathered from interviews. In order to ensure accurate analysis, the process employed towards analyzing the data are presented in section 3.11.1 below.

3.11.1 Quantitative Data Analysis Processes

As shown in section 3.6 of this chapter, this study employed the convergent parallel mixed method, which involved using the quantitative and qualitative research methods jointly in a parallel manner. Thus, the process towards analyzing each of the methods are explained below: *Quantitative Data Analysis Process*. The process of analyzing quantitative data is perceived as a way of using statistical techniques to reduce data collected in order to interpret the information accurately (Bryman, 2016). So, following the face-to-face survey questionnaire administration, the following steps are performed for the data preparation. These steps are considered essential for analyzing quantitative data.

1. *Sorting and screening filled questionnaires*. All collected questionnaires considered duly filled by the respondents were carefully checked to ensure that only those appropriately filled were selected and used for the research. Conversely, those questionnaires that were having one error or the other on the vital part of the questionnaire such as not indicating using one e-banking products and services; and not indicating their response on age, education, among others were identified and removed.
2. *Grouping*. At this stage, verified questionnaire were grouped based on the responses of the respondents from each of the two banks Guaranteed Trust Bank and First City Monument Banks and total number of verified questionnaires were counted, recorded and invalid questionnaire data were disregarded (Figure 3.3).
3. *Data Coding*. The verified questionnaire was carefully coded for the raw data collected. Coding is ascribing specific code to responses gathered (Creswell, 2013). The close-ended responses gathered were coded, and open-ended responses were categorized and after that coded. Each of the questions on the questionnaire was labelled with numbers. Question 1 was labelled with figure 1 up to the last question on the questionnaire labelled 24. The total number of variables to be entered into SPSS for analysis amounted to 24 due to the last question in the questionnaire that was labelled 24.
4. *Data Entry*. This is the last stage of the data analysis procedure. A total number of 24 variables with a total number of 176 responses i.e cases gathered from each participant

were entered into Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS). The 176 cases (responses) were entered into rows amounting to 176, and the 24 items representing the questions were entered in the column section of the SPSS data editor. In all, a total number of 880 cases were generated from the 24 variables entered.

Figure 3.3: Summary of Survey Data

Descriptive Statistics

The study performed descriptive statistical analysis on all the variables or constructs used for the study through Pearson's correlation coefficient (a parametric test) used for investigating correlation levels between constructs. Specifically, a T-test analysis detailing the mean, standard deviation, T-value of all the variables was conducted in a bid to examine the factors that are influencing and affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Conversely, this research conducted a validity and reliability test to check the quality of the data used for the study. Specifically, an exploratory factor analysis was conducted on all e-banking variables to determine the validity of the variables. KMO and Bartlett test was performed on the variables before performing the factor analysis. The reason for this is to determine the sampling adequacy of the variable before the factor analysis. Further detail of the validity and reliability test performed is presented in section 3.11.2 below.

3.11.2: Construct Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability are recognised as important for data quality in any research whether quantitative or qualitative, each of the items represent a vital element that is important in ensuring rigour, robustness and data quality (Heale and Twycross, 2015). A construct validity was performed through Exploratory Factor Analysis to determine the degree at which the variables reflects the latent construct they are meant to measure (Hair, *et al.* 2006). All items

with at least loading of 0.5 and with an eigenvalue equal or greater than 1 are accepted for the construct validity (Habing, 2003).

A reliability analysis was also conducted to check the consistency of the research data employed for this study measure what it intends to measure. According to Bryman, (2016) reliability is the consistency of a measure. The researcher therefore carried out a reliability test on all the variables used for the analysis through Cronbach Alpha test, a test performed to test the internal consistency of the scale. A Cronbach alpha value within or above the recommended threshold of 0.70 are acceptable and considered to show a construct reliability that indicates the reliability of the instrument. The stability of a measure shows the stability and consistence of the instrument adopted to measure a concept. Correlation analysis was also performed to determine the relationship that exist between the variables used for the analysis if they are well correlated.

3.11.3 Qualitative Data Analysis Process.

Analyzing qualitative data involves preparing and organizing the data purposely for analysis and its entails three essential steps including transcribing, coding, and analysis (Creswell, 2013). Thematic content analysis was adopted to extract key themes from the interview. Thus, the qualitative analysis of this study gone through the steps below;

1. **Data Transcription.** The qualitative data collected from participants were carefully transcribed verbatim and word-to-word from the phone recording to a typed copy in Microsoft word. The transcription- word-to-word was read-and re-read thereby helping the researcher to familiarized herself with the data.
2. **Data Categorization (coding);** at this stage, the researcher carefully coded the full transcription copy based on the concept and themes that emerged from the transcription. According to Gibbs (2007) data coding is how data collected is to be analyzed. All coding was manually done as the researcher read and re-read the transcription text before ascribing codes to the themes. This approach was considered suitable for this researcher as it widens the researcher's knowledge in the process of exploring the various ideas that emerged from the interview.
3. **Data Analysis;** Thematic data analysis was employed for analyzing the basic themes that emerged from the transcription. According to Harding (2013) qualitative analysis can be analyzed using various approaches such as Narrative analysis which includes interactional analysis, thematic analysis, and structural analysis. However, the research adopted the

Powell-Taylor and Renner, 2003) thematic analysis approach for analyzing the qualitative data done manually without using qualitative analysis software. All data generated from the interviews was saved in Microsoft word and processed on a classification basis. The key findings from the data analysis are presented in data analysis and result chapter of this study. The snapshot of the qualitative data process is presented in figure 3.4 below:

Figure 3.4: Qualitative data analysis process used for this research

Source: Author generated

3.12 Limitations of the Study

Limitations are the constraints largely beyond the control of the study and which can affect the outcome of the research (Marilyn and Jim, 2013). This limits the extent to which the study can go and may affect the result and conclusion of the research. The research aimed to broaden the scope of the study, but some constraints limit the effort such as lack of time, meeting the participants, geographical distance between Lagos and Ogun States which made movement very difficult and the inability to interview the bank officials.

The major limitations identified for the study is that the research is limited to bank customers in two banks of Nigeria, which impacted the result of the study to some extent and limits generalizing the results. Also, the study was conducted specifically for the banking sector hence the result might not be useful outside the banking sector. In addition, only 2 of the current 22 commercial banks was used for the study, thereby paving the way for further investigation of the research area. Further studies would investigate other banks of the 22 existing commercial banks in Nigeria.

3.13 Research Timeline

The research has been conducted for three years; the Gantt chart below show the time frame to complete the research.

3.14 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the researcher established the philosophical stance of the research; the tenet of this research was based on the pragmatist perspectives that allow the use of mixed research methods. The chapter also reported the selected research design- a convergent parallel mixed method adopted, showing the two methods used in the mixed-method research design approach adopted. The approach of the research was clearly stated with the details of the plans and procedures of the research stating the research design and strategy, the purpose and the details of the method of data collection, analysis and interpretation. This chapter further justified the decision behind each approach, methods and techniques. Interview and questionnaire were used for primary data collection from bank customers. Furthermore, the chapter presents the ethical issues considered in the study such as informed consent; no harm to participants; no deception and no invasion of privacy; and complying with the UWS ethical guidelines. The study's limitations were presented, including the major limitations that affect the generalization of the research outcome. The next chapter is the supplementary chapter of this thesis.

CHAPTER FOUR

BACKGROUND INFORMATION INTO BANKING IN NIGERIA

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides supplementary information about the study. First, information about the country of study and background review on the Nigeria banking industry which includes the structure of the Nigeria commercial banks, the Nigeria banking reforms that led to the development of e-banking adoption, and the Political, Economic, Socio, Technological and Legal (PESTEL) analysis of the Nigeria banking environment were discussed. Next, this chapter presents additional justification and rationale for the choice of the two banks: Guaranteed Trust Bank (GTB) and First City Monument Bank (FCMB) used for the study out of the 22 commercial banks currently in Nigeria. Thereafter, a comparative analysis of e-banking practices of the two banks were provided in this chapter. This chapter goes on to discuss how the internet rate penetration in Nigeria serves as an enabling factor for GTB and FCMB banks adopting e-service channels and services. This chapter ends by providing a summary of the chapter and establishing how the technological infrastructure utilized by banks affects and influences e-banking products and services adoption in the Nigeria banking environment.

The next section presents information about the country of study, Nigeria.

4.2 Overview of the country of study

The importance of this section lies in providing a brief overview of the country of study from which then presents the Nigeria banking industry which form the focus of the study.

Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and multi-cultural society with around three hundred ethnic groups and many different languages (Erhagbe, 2012). The country uniqueness amongst the African countries is not just because of its multiculturalism but due to her unity in diversity characterized in her multi-ethnic society as a country (Osimen, Balogun and Adenegan, 2013). It is located in West Africa with its coast on the Gulf of Guinea and regarded as the most populous African country. According to Anukam, (2007), Nigeria shares land borders with the Republic of Benin and Cameroon in the west; in the east and the North, shared border with

Chad, also shared border with the Niger Republic. As presented in 4.1 below, the country has 36 states divided into six geo-political zones and Abuja as its Federal Capital Territory.

Figure 4.1: Map of Nigeria

Source: Gayawan and Turra, 2015

Currently, Nigeria operates a democratic system of government under the leadership of President Muhammed Buhari. As of 2019, the estimated population of the country is over 200.96 million based on the United Nations estimates (World Population Prospects, 2019). This figure is equivalent to 2.64% of the total world population however forecasts suggest continuous increase (Worldometers, 2020). Table 4.1 below presents general information about the country of study.

Table 4.1: Snapshot of Nigeria

Location	Western Africa, bordering the Gulf of Guinea, between Benin and Cameroon
Capital	Abuja - Officially transferred from Lagos to Abuja on 12 December 1991
Administrative divisions	36 states and 1 Federal Capital Territory. (Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, , Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nassarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Rivers, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara)
Population	200.96 million (2019 estimate)
Land area	923, 768 sq km (356,669 sq miles)
GDP per capita	₦806,219 (USD2,244.0)
Population density	82.2 per km
Population growth rate	4.8%
Literacy level	69%
Rural population	48.1%
Urban population	51.9 %

Life expectancy	
Monetary Unit	Naira
Language	English (official), Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo (Ibo), Fulani
Ethnicity/race	Heterogeneous
Religion	Muslim 50%, Christian 40%, indigenous beliefs 10%
Gained independence from	Great Britain
Date of independence	October 1, 1960
Republic declared	October 1, 1963
Number of states	36 plus the Federal Capital Territory
Local Government Areas	774
Natural resources	Natural gas, petroleum, tin, iron ore, coal, limestone, niobium, lead, zinc, arable land

Source: Author generated

The UN reports claimed that 104,282,822 (51.9%) of the population are residents of urban areas. Available statistics reported age dependency ratio of 46.9% while the working population age estimated as 53.1% (Trading Economics, 2016). This suggests that a larger percentage of the country's population falls within the working-age group. Arguably, the Nigeria age structure can generate a substantial growth if appropriately positioned to achieve a 'demographic dividend' (World Economic Forum, 2014). World Bank (2012) also report that Nigeria is rich in mineral resources ranging from petroleum, coal, tin, bauxite, iron ore, etc. In furtherance to these, the country can boast of several mineral deposits in various states, though, its concentration for years has been on oil (CBN, 2010). Conversely, there are multiple agricultural resources in Nigeria, groundnut pyramids in the North, the west is full of cocoa plantations and the East has oil palm products, Nigeria also boasts of healthy rivers full of fishes and other aquatic animals.

Despite these wealth and opulence, the country has not been in best shape as 40% of its population still live far below the poverty line (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019), infrastructural facilities such as electricity, roads, school, hospital, water are still lacking and short in supply (Eze 2009; Gbadeyan and Akinyosoye-Gbonda, 2011). The major causes of these problems are attributed to lack of economic blueprints (Obafemi 2006), corruption since after gaining independence in 1960 (Nwankwo 2003), and educational inequalities (Agwu, 2014). Further evidence suggests that in 2019 approximately 35% (60 million) Nigerians are not educated according to the (ThisDay, 2020), as such joint effort of the stakeholders are required to address this menace as education is critical to national development.

The World Bank Report (2013) states that in 2013 the statistics of the unemployed working age population doubled the 12% recorded in 2006 and significantly changed to 24% by the year 2011. Majority of the Nigerians that are employed are works in low paying jobs, performed tasks that are below their educational qualifications and works in the informal sector to survive. According to Nwude (2013) the National Bureau of Statistics found 60.9% of Nigerians living in poverty in 2012, surviving on 1.50US dollar daily. Simona (2020) stated that the current national minimum wage of ₦30,000.00 (\$77.0) a month is insufficient for necessities of life thus far below what can be referred to as a living wage.

Section 4.3 below presents background review of the structure of the Nigeria banking industry.

4.3. Background Review

The structure of the sector that forms the focus of the study is presented in the following subsections.

4.3.1 Nigeria Banking Industry Structure

The Nigerian banking industry is regulated by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Nigeria banking industry has been sheltered by the regulations and policies made by the Nigerian governments. The major players in the industry are the 21 commercial banks comprising nine tier 1 banks; ten tier 2 national banks and two tier 3 regional banks (CBN, 2018). Tiers are size of banks in relation to other banks. Tier 1 banks are banks with strong financial strengths that have the authorization to function as international banks, as they have enough capital to cover their unexpected losses. The tier 2 and 3 banks represent banks with a license to operate national and regional banks (CBN, 2019). Table 4.1 below detailed the structure of 21 license commercial banks in Nigeria including their names.

However, the current structure of financial institutions in Nigeria, especially the banks, has significantly changed the industry by bringing many significant changes in the sector. These significant changes heralded by depth competition compelled banks to show zeal towards information technology and customers' satisfaction through efficient delivery of quality services (Oluwagbemi *et al.*, 2011). The uniqueness of these significant changes was the deliberate attempt on the part of the banks to outperform peers in banking operations by developing different business models leading to customers' sophistication in terms of

enlightenment, interest, expectation and convenience (Olayinka and Aminu, 2008). Table 4.2 present the current structure of Nigeria commercial banks.

Table 4.2:
Structure of Nigeria Commercial Banks- 21 banks (2018).

No	Tier 1 (International Banks)	Tier 2 (National Banks)	Tier 3 (Regional Banks)
1	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	10. Citibank Nigeria Limited	20. Providus Bank Plc
2	Access Bank Plc	11. Eco Bank Nigeria Plc	21. Suntrust Bank Nigeria Plc
3	First City Monument Bank Plc	12. Keystone Bank	
4	Union Bank of Nigeria Plc	13. Wema Bank Plc	
5	United Bank for Africa Plc	14. Stanbic IBTC bank Plc	
6	First Bank of Nigeria Plc	15. Standard Chartered Bank Plc	
7	Zenith Bank Plc	16. Sterling Bank Plc	
8.	Fidelity Bank Plc	17. Unity Bank Plc	
9.	Diamond Bank Plc	18. Heritage Bank Limited	
		19. Polaris Bank Plc	

Source: CBN (2018).

Access Bank Plc acquired Diamond Bank Plc in early 2019, thus, reduced total number of international banks to 8. The current total number of commercial banks is 22 following the issuance of license to Titan Trust Bank Limited to operate as National bank and Globus Nigeria Plc to operate as regional bank. The total number of branches was 5,450 at December 2019 (CBN, 2019). Table 4.3 details the current structure of the license commercial banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.3:
Current Structure of Nigeria Commercial Bank-22 banks Updated (2019).

No	Tier 1 (International Banks) = 8	Tier 2 (National Banks) = 11	Tier 3 (Regional Banks) = 3
1	Guaranty Trust Bank Plc	9. Citibank Nigeria Limited	20. Providus Bank Plc
2	Access Bank Plc	10. Eco Bank Nigeria Plc	21. Suntrust Bank Nigeria Plc
3	First City Monument Bank Plc	11. Keystone Bank	22. Globus Nigeria Plc
4	Union Bank of Nigeria Plc	12. Wema Bank Plc	
5	United Bank for Africa Plc	13. Polaris Bank Plc	
6	First Bank of Nigeria Plc	14. Stanbic IBTC bank Plc	
7	Zenith Bank Plc	15. Standard Chartered Bank Plc	
8.	Fidelity Bank Plc	16. Sterling Bank Plc	
		17. Unity Bank Plc	
		18. Heritage Bank Limited	
		19. Titan Trust Bank Limited	

Source: CBN (2019)

4.3.2 Nigeria Banking Industry Reforms and the Development of E-banking Adoption

It is important to understand the reasons that necessitate the introduction of e-banking in the Nigeria banking sector. Thus, the importance of this section lies in presenting the reforms that led to the development of e-banking adoption in the industry.

The Nigeria banking industry has been restructured to withstand the demands of today economy and to ensure banks adopt new electronic practices. Governmental regulations over the years have accelerated growth and generated a wheel of progress in this sector to propel economic growth (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2012; Uduak and Ubong *et al.*, 2015). The banking sector undergone some economic reforms that shaped the industry which resulted into the emergence of E-banking (Figure 4.1). The major aim was to make Nigerian banks vibrant and resilient, clothed with efficiency and financial strength to absorb possible shocks, thereby instilling public confidence as well as global relevance (Soludo, 2004). For example, the liberalization of the telecommunication sector before the 2004 banking reform by the Nigerian government (Afigbo *et al.* 2007). This era thus, generated the prospect for major technological innovations in the Nigeria banking industry. Through the use of information technology (IT), banks now use different electronic banking channels like internet banking, video banking, mobile banking, Automated Teller Machines, Point of Sales (POS) to deliver their services (Adesina and Ayo 2010; Aliyu and Tasmin, 2012; Anthony *et. al* 2018). The banking industry at this phase became more technology-based as opposed to the traditional banking that was not competitive where customers must step into the banking hall for banking transactions. In particular, the Nigeria bank reformation exercise in June 2004 accompanied with the introduction of Guideline on e-banking in 2003 by the Central Bank of Nigeria enormously engaged the use of information technology as a platform for efficient and effective banking services (Adeshina and Ayo, 2010).

According to Adeyemi, (2006), the Central bank of Nigeria's Governor Prof. Charles Soludo (2004), designed banking sector reform to ensure a diversified, strong and reliable banking industry. The reforms are designed to enable the banking system to develop the required resilience to support the economic development of the nation by efficiently performing its functions as the fulcrum of financial intermediation (Lemo, 2005). This reform afforded depositors confidence to freely deposits money by eliminating the barriers (low depositor's confidence, low capital base, overdependence on public sector deposit, weak corporate governance) that hitherto existed in banks and position banks to play active developmental roles in the Nigerian economy, and become major players in the sub-regional, regional and

global financial markets (Adeyemi. 2006). Conversely, the current structure of industry has changed the industry remarkable resulting into significant changes in the sector. These significant changes heralded by depth competition compelled banks to show zeal towards innovative products/services and customers' satisfaction through efficient delivery of quality services (Oluwagbemi, *et. al* 2011).

Figure 4.2:
Snapshot of Nigeria Banking Industry Pre and Post E-Banking

Sources: Author generated from the analysis of Balogun 2007; Soludo, 2004; Adeshina and Ayo 2010; Inegbedion 2018; Anthony *et al.* 2018.

Discussion; the chronological picture of reforms that brought about e-banking development in the Nigeria banking sector are provided below;

1851-1951: This is the era of free banking; an era of unregulated banking practices characterised with CBN inability to govern and manage banking processes adequately affect the industry. Governance and internal processes were unstructured, and this compromised the CBN's ability to supervise the industry. Corporate governance at the CBN was laissez-faire. Issues concerning the stability of the financial sector and economic development were not comprehensively addressed at the CBN Board meetings. The CBN was not organized to monitor, analyse adequately the economic issues and the risks inherent in the financial sector. There is no overarching architecture to manage the risks in the banking system, the management information system available for risks analysis was inefficient (Sanusi, 2010).

1959-1986: Nigeria banking regulation and supervision started between 1959-1986. This was the period when the need for prudential change in the Nigerian banking sector became imperative because of unethical and potentially fraudulent business practices inherent in the banking sector including the lack of adequate corporate governance and insolvency (Soludo 2006). Further to this, is the involvement of some banks in alleged unethical practices for instance, poor loan quality was prevalent among the Nigerian banks (Sanusi, 2010)

1987-1993: this was the period when banks shifted their operation from tallies, registers and paper-oriented methods to technological based system. 1994-1998 mark the beginning of another restructuring period due to deep financial distress in the banking sector. It was noted that about 21% of the stakeholders' funds were granted as loans as opposed to about 2% obtainable in countries such as America and Europe (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2012). The reform was introduced to enhance financial strength of bank and promote economic development.

1994-1998: another banking sector reform took place in this period. This was the period where there was distress in the banking sector. The Central Bank of Nigeria reported that over 66 banks in Nigeria were distressed and some were terminally distressed by 1993 (CBN, 2007). The CBN (2007) further notes that the distress in the Nigeria banking sector was due to the complexity of the inter-related problems such as capital inadequacy; ownership structure/political interference; poor management and inhibitive political environment that had affected the industry for a very long time

1999-2003: This was the era of universal banking and the period when the guideline on electronic banking (E-banking) was introduced by Central Bank of Nigeria (Oni and Ayo, 2003).

2004-2008: This was the period when E-banking intensified; banks invested in e-banking infrastructure and increase adoption of e-banking products. This was the exert period when e-banking started in Nigeria. Conversely, this was the period of revolution in the banking sector where bank paid up capital was increased from ₦2billion to ₦25billion. This therefore led to liquidation of weak banks that were unable to find merger partners. This era brought revolutionary changes in the banking operations in Nigeria and intense competition among the banks. The banks that were able to survive, that could find merger partners were regarded as 'mega' banks and they introduced new products/services, repackaged the existing ones and came up with effective service delivery strategies through investment in ICT (Sanni, 2009). Moreso, the 2004 consolidation policy was introduced during between this period to enable banks to serve as a catalyst to enhancing financial stability and economic growth in the country

(Sanusi, 2011, Ibrahim *et al.* 2012). Consolidation policy served as a regulatory framework which the Nigerian government used to safeguard the banking industry. According to Nnanna, (2004), consolidation will enhance synergy, improve efficiency, induce investor focus and trigger productivity and welfare. Basically, Nigeria telecommunication sector liberalization which occur before the banking sector reform of 2004 created an enabling environment for the introduction of electronic banking system in Nigeria as the country telecommunication industry was liberalized in 2001 (Osibanjo and Nnorom, 2008).

4.3.3 PESTEL Analysis- the Nigeria Banking Environment

Nigeria banks faces numbers of challenges from within the Nigeria business environment. The external influences on the banking industry is classified: political, economic, technological and social factors according Jayawardhene and Foley (2000). The external factors are usually beyond the firm’s control that may constitute threats to the organization (NetMBA, 2007). Hence, PESTEL analysis was found suitable for this study as it helps reveal the threats to e-banking adoption and give recommendations that could help to fast-track its acceptance. The PESTEL analysis of the Nigeria banking industry is provided in table 4.4 below

Table 4.4:
PESTEL Analysis

Political	Economic AND Social
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) regulate Nigeria Banks • 21 commercial banks presently • 47 years of military government • Consumer Protection Council Act 1992 • Unstructured governance and management processes of CBN • Consolidation policy 2004 • Minimum capital base raised to ₦25billion, (\$155Million). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth in national oil revenue • Inflation increased to 12.5% • Disposable income and barning power of consumer decreased • 61.3million people in work
Technology	Environment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Identification Number (PIN) • Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) • over 50 million users of telephone banking • Internet-banking • Automated Teller Machine (ATM) • Electronic transfer • Electronic Mail • Bankers Automated Clearing Services • Internet network facilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intense competition level • First bank cost base advantage • Government change the competitive market • Reduced paper transaction <p>Legal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CBN Act 2007 • Bank and other Financial Institutions Act, 1999 • Companies and Allied Matters Act, 1990 • Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation Act, 1988 • Failed Banks (Recovery of Debts) & Financial Malpractices in Banks Act, 1994 • Anti Money Laundering Act, 1955,

Source: Iyayi, 2004; Oluwagbemi *et.al*, 2011; Ibrahim *et al.* 2012; Igbinedon 2018

1. Political

Nigeria has been operating under military dictatorship governments characterized by economic depression, lack of vision, fraud and inadequate infrastructural development until 1999 (Iyayi, 2004, Ezeoha, 2006b). The year 1999 marked the beginning of democratic government after a long year of an uninterrupted military government. The military government ruled for 47 years since Nigeria independence. Researchers noted that the increase in customers' rights through Legislation (e.g. Consumer Protection Council Act 1992) had impacted the kind of value that now being placed on customers, as such they (customers) are considered vital to the success of any business (Jayawardhene and Foley, 2000). Jayawardhene and Foley (2000) further noted that banks needs to adopt innovations that are not only tailored towards customers' demands but also to gain their loyalty in the competitive market for banks to remain relevant and productive.

The Nigeria banking system has been sheltered by the regulations and policies made by the governments. Nigeria banks have been able to comply with government policy, especially the CBN minimum capital directive. They employed different strategies like Right issues for existing shareholders and capitalization of profits; Public offers through the capital market and/or private placement; Mergers and acquisitions to ensure compliance with CBN directives (Adeyemi, 2006). Nigeria banks also formulate their defence strategies besides any governmental restrictions and limitations. Nigeria banks (GTB, FCMB) actively undergone growth through expansion in other parts of Europe to beat the competition.

Moreover, the consolidation policy (2004) stipulated by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) mandated a new capital base for Nigerian commercial banks (Barros and Caporale, 2012), to make the sector realize its objectives in advancing the economy (CBN, 2006). The capital base for the total number of 89 banks operating at the time of this reform has increased from 2Billion Naira (about \$12Million) to 25Billion Naira (about \$155Million). The CBN gave Nigerian banks 18 months window to implement this policy (Okafor, 2012). The general assessment of these banks influenced this decision of the CBN, as the results, according to Soludo (2006) indicated that Nigerian banks have a low capital base. The result of which has led to over-

reliance on public sector deposits as well as foreign exchange trading; weak corporate governance; and in the real sense tend towards insolvency and illiquidity.

2. Economic and Social

Agriculture was regarded as the primary revenue source for the government before the oil boom era (Adedipe, 2004), However, in the mid-1970s the Nigeria economy depends largely on oil (CBN, 2007), was placed among major exporters of petroleum and ranked amongst the richest countries in the globe (IMF, 2012). The heavy dependency of the Nigeria economy on oil revenues resulted to the poor economy, importation of items that could have been locally produced, high crime rates, cycle crimes and lack of jobs (Vaughan, *et al.*, 2014). Although, it has been reported that in the last five years the current government have helped reduce the importation level to encourage the local producers, but the result has not been substantial (Arigor, Nyambi and Obuo, 2015).

However, the Nigerian economy has registered robust growth in recent years, and the banking industry is directly related to the growth of the economy. The growth of national oil revenues, vital for Government finances, is not seen as the key engine to future banking success. Rather, it is the continued growth of the middle class, and the antecedent boom in personal lending, mortgages, credit cards and long-term products generate much of the future potential. The growth of the middle class in the major Nigerian cities has meant that banks, once the exclusive preserve of the wealthy, are now becoming more accessible to ordinary consumers.

Nigeria journey to economic growth, technological development and civilization begin in 1999 (Ezeoha, 2006). E-banking service and products are still gaining acceptance with only Automated Trading Machine (ATM) services rated highest for acceptance and usage, among others (Nwankwo, 2006). Nigeria economy is largely cash-oriented with more than 65% of its fund (cash) outside the banking sector in contrary to developed economy UK (4%) and US (9%) of their money in circulation (Ovia 2002; Ojo 2004). The cash-oriented economy of Nigeria is characterized by a culture of holding cash physically, low educational level, ignorance, poor security consciousness and lack of appreciation of e-payment benefits (Agwu, 2017). Yaqub *et al.* (2013) also reported Nigeria economy to be extremely cash-based. However, with the government's recent efforts to fast track electronic payment development in Nigeria, the cash in circulation has reduced drastically (CBN Report, 2017), thereby promoting

e-banking products and services. Figure 4.3 below presents the trend and percentage of the cash in circulation to GDP.

Figure 4.3

Source: CBN Annual Report, 2017

The figure 4.3 above shows that currency in circulation reduced drastically i.e holding cash physically reduced between 2013 and 2017, except in 2016 that reports a slight increase in physical cash. In sum, this shows that the e-banking products and services through e-payments have begun to gain acceptance and usage in Nigeria.

Conversely, household economic situation report showed that 32.0% in 2006 as against 30.9% in 2005 of households in rural and urban Nigeria were worse-off. In general, two-thirds of the households in Nigeria are poor, and this represents 68.8%. Poverty was more pronounced in rural areas (65.5%), while in the urban areas, it was 56.8% (Ayo, 2008). Also, consumers' bargaining power and disposable income have decreased due to inflation at 12.5% (CBN, 2018) and unemployment at 18.8% (Trading Economics, 2018). This is a threat to consumer banking. The inflation rate from year 2013 to 2017 is present in figure 4.4 below;

Figure 4.4: Inflation Rate

Source: CBN Report, 2017.

The inflation rate was very low in 2013 and 2014 after that from the year 2015 inflation rate from 2016 increased significantly. It trended up to 18.5% in 2016. The increment was attributed to the rise in transportation cost and food supply reduction resulting from incessant herdsmen/farmers' crisis. However, inflation decreased to 15.4% in 2017, from 18.5% in 2016 due to the economic policies, and banking reforms introduced in 2004 (CBN, 2017).

3. Technology

There was little or no significant record of technological development in Nigeria 39 years after independence in 2009 according to Ayo and Adebisi, (2008). However, a commendable growth in technology, for example, telephone banking moving from a teledensity of 0.73 to 37.05 in 2001 to October 2007. There are over 50 million users of telephone banking in the country. Hence, Nigeria currently rated the fastest growing telecoms industry in Africa (Nigeria2Day, 2007). A report by the National Space Research and Development Agency revealed that only about 21 Percent of Nigerians out of 170 million actively use the internet. KPMG review for 2013 estimates the value of daily e-funds transfers in Nigeria at N80 billion, number of ATM deployed at 11,700, the number of cards issued at 26 million and the number of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) deployed at 117,000, numbers of cards issues at 26 million and the number of Point of Sales (POS) terminals at 170000 (KPMG, 2013).

The adoption of e-banking services has been regarded as one of the important means of achieving a competitive edge. The earliest technology employed by the Nigerian banks for banking services were office automation devices ranging from telex, facsimile and telephones. They remained the primary ICT employed for banking business transactions for many years until the 1980s when personal computer gained popularity (Agwu, 2013). Arguably, the most revolutionary e-banking innovation across the world and Nigeria has been the ATM and other electronic cards.

Specifically, the major banking electronic devices that were found to be in operation in Nigeria as at this moment include GSM Banking, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), Point of Sales (POS) Funds Transfer, On-Line Banking, Electronic Mail, Bankers Automated Clearing Services and internet network facilities (Antony *et, al.* 2018). The GSM banking is enabling phone transaction which allows access into the account as long as phone and service support the operation in question. ATM is cash enabling dispense through the use of PIN; aside from this, bills can also be settled and solve the problem of a long queue in the banking hall. Fund transfer is now made easier through the use of information technology, and funds can be

transferred across the globe without any problem or delay as long as adequate information about the receiver is correct. Online banking affords the customer ample opportunities to make payment for goods and services without actual contact with physical cash also transaction of any kind can be performed electronically. It is the electronic mail that made communication between different branches of banks in a different location to be possible. Confirmation of cheque payment is equally facilitated by the electronic mail, and the bankers automated clearing services which is in the area of cheque processing. It uses magnetic ink character reader (MICR) to fast track cheque processing (coding, reading and sorting) and request for cheque book and draft payment are also facilitated by this electronic device (Agboola, 2003, Amedu, 2005 and Oluwagbemi, 2011). It is worth noting that the majority of these electronic devices are internet-based activities.

In response to the demands for quick, efficient and reliable services, Nigeria banks are increasingly deploying technology as a means of generating insights into customers' behavioural patterns and preferences (customer perspective). Banking perspective; well-developed outsourcing support functions (technology and operations/processes) are increasingly being used to provide services and manage costs e.g. Automated Teller Machine networks, Cards processing, Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT), bill presentment and Payments, Software Development, Call centre facilities/operations and Network management).

4. Environmental

The most striking environmental factor affecting Nigeria banks is the increasing competition within this sector. The consolidation of banks has created a basis for much stronger competition, and at the same time, the larger, older banks still have some competitive advantages, particularly on cost grounds due to their scale. For instance,

“First Bank has balance sheet size and the cost of funds (advantage) because First bank is a 100-year-old bank. They have customers that have deposited their money there for years so there is no cost to lend money. They can lend rates and pricing that other banks cannot offer. If I can give you money at 15% they could probably do 12% because of their cost base advantage”. (Adebowale Owolabi, Manager Commercial Banking Group- Automobile Division, GTBank, 2006, p. 7).

This levelling of the competitive playing field due to consolidation is being felt throughout the Nigeria banking world. Consolidation, acquisition and reaching a sustainable size are the strategies been deployed by most major competitors:

What the government did was really change the competitive market. For instance, First bank really had the size prior to the legislation, now every major bank is about our size so we had to craft a plan so that we can maintain our competitive edge. (Jacob, Ajekigbe, MD of First Bank, 2008). According to Jacobs's market analysis what seems to be emerging in the Nigeria banking market are

three categories of bank; the top 10 players, the middle 7 and the bottom 8 who may struggle to survive in the mid-term.

According to Adeyemi (2010), different banks employ different banking applications software to gain a competitive edge in the Nigeria banking sector. The challenge here is that some of these ICT packages are not compatible and banks have already incurred huge costs in the acquisition of these technologies, this increases the cost of consolidation as the entire bank have to work under one IT platform. Arguably, this can pose significant challenges for the adoption of e-banking for customers.

5. Legal

The Nigeria Banking Sector is one of the most regulated industries in Nigeria (Rahman and Rahman, 2013). The primary legislation for the regulation of banks in Nigeria is the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) which, with the Central Bank of Nigeria (Establishment) Act 2007 (CBN Act), gives the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) powers to supervise and regulate banks and other financial institutions in Nigeria. Other relevant legislation includes the:

- Companies and Allied Matters Act (Cap 59, Laws of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1990 (CAMA), which regulates companies generally.
- Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation Act 1988, which is responsible for insuring all deposit liabilities of licensed banks.
- Foreign Exchange (Monitoring and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act, which established the Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market and provides the regulatory framework for foreign exchange transactions in Nigeria.

4.4 Justification for the Choice of Banks for this Research

Guaranteed Trust Bank and FCMB bank have been purposely chosen because both banks are new generation banks which received several awards and rated AA as one of the best banks in Nigeria and coupled with the fact that they are modern and have the capability to be effective in electronic banking innovations. Agboola (2003) noted that new generation banks appeared to be more effective in using information communication technology to enhance performance. For example, FCMB is utilising all avenue to ensure e-banking services are made relevant to their customers' needs (Adam, 2017). Particularly, a few banks set themselves apart in Nigeria banking environment, Guaranteed Trust Bank was one of those banks showing strong organic growth while maintaining very low-cost customer-focused strategy (Bankole, 2015), this made Guaranteed Trust Bank one of the top 3 among Nigerian banks, despite very new in the market

(Financial Intelligence, 2015). Table 4.5 below detailed the strengths, including the address of the two banks used for the sample.

Table 4.5:
Sample Banks' Strengths

Banks	GTB	FCMB
Head office	Plot 635, Akin Adesola Street Victoria Island, Lagos State.	Primrose Tower 17A, Tinubu street, Lagos Island, Lagos
Branches	231	206
No of employees	12,000+ worldwide	3,893
No of customers	8million	7.1million
No of ATMs	1165	770
Sine		

Source: GTB; FCMB

- **Guaranteed Trust Bank (GTB)**

GTB is a leading Nigeria bank that is highly profitable, and AA rated bank in Nigeria. It is the most respected bank, especially in the area of commercial banking, with a sound reputation for customer service, ethical conduct, professionalism and innovations. In 1989, two professional bankers in Lagos Tayo Aderinokun and Fola Adeola were extremely disillusioned with the quality of banking in Nigeria coupled with poor customer service, poor professionalism and questionable ethics in Nigeria banking system. Both raised money obtained license and established GTB in 1990. They insisted all employees uphold the highest ethical and professional standards, a compelling proposition in the market at that time. This made GTBank attractive to multinational companies, and many commercial companies thus changed the way banking was done in Nigeria. All GTB managers were personally trained by the founders and given extensive mentoring in customer service, ethics and professional technical tools needed for the bank's performance for the first decade of its existence. The combination of effective operations implemented by the team of talented, motivated professionals and a unique market positioning of the bank yielded rapid growth for GTB bank (Maklan and Knox 2009), and the growth has been very profitable till date.

Most importantly, the e-banking practice in GTB bank is second to none. GTB is using innovative technology to drive inclusivity, to bank the unbanked customers and highly committed to the socially responsible banking system (Agbaje, 2018). Effective innovation technology has been adopted to achieve customer insights and improve their customer service. In 2015, the EMEA Finance Magazine reported that GTB has been recognised as Africa's most Innovative Bank (EMEA, 2015). GTB as the most innovate bank demonstrates its commitment

towards adopting cutting edge technology to deliver excellent services to diverse African communities. Hence was awarded for its contributions towards developing African social banking market using social media and virtual channels for banking services.

However, as a leader in innovation, GTBank customers have benefited tremendously from innovative products and service creation, especially in the electronic aspect of banking designed to meet their customers' needs. The bank remains the first bank to introduce electronic notification system - Guaranty Trust Electronic Notification System (GeNS) - which notifies customers about all transactions on their accounts via their phones and e-mail (On-Line Real Time). The E-banking products and services portfolio of the bank includes:

- Automated Teller Machine (ATM)
- Mobile/SMS banking
- Internet banking
- Pont-of-Sale (POS)
- Guaranty Trust Electronic Notification System (GeNS)
- GT Automated Payment System
- Cash collection implants
- Bitwize Format
- GT Swift Mailer
- e-Card Tracker
- Statement by email
- Smart Kids/Students Savings account

In all, GTB Bank promise to aggressively pursuing innovative solutions that create sustainable value for all their customers and stakeholders while maintaining a high standard in service delivery.

- **First City Monument Bank (FCMB)**

First City Monument Bank (FCMB) is a universal banking institution with an experienced management team and significant international shareholdings, FCMB is headquartered in Lagos, Nigeria. In 1977 FCMB was established and emerged from City Security Ltd. In 1982, the bank was licensed as First City Merchant Bank, becoming the first local bank in Nigeria to be established without government support. FCMB became a public limited company in 2004 and its shares was listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) accounted for about 5% of the total assets in the banking industry.

FCMB as a strong brand in Nigeria, has its branch network across the country and has unique financial products and services. The product and service offerings cover three core areas: retail

banking, investment banking, and transaction banking; and other areas including corporate finance and advisory, financial markets and lending, transaction services.

FCMB emerged as one of the most dynamics and leading banks in Nigeria. Its success has been recognized with various industry awards nationally and internationally. Recently, the bank was awarded Excellence in Customer Experience Enhancement 2019 by Finnovex West Africa, a financial technology company that examines how technology is changing banking and payment services; Best Bank in Small and Medium Enterprise financing 2018 awarded by Business Day Banking and Financial Institutions; and Euromoney 2008 award for the Best Equity House in Nigeria.

FCMB bank has continued to expand its banking channels by offering world-class e-banking products and services that align with its customers' lifestyles. FCMB is known for providing seamless and convenient alternative banking channels such as Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Point of Sales, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), among others. The Bank has continuously deployed cutting-edge technology that is highly impactful products and services for its customers, thereby improving their experience. In 2017, the Guardian news reported that the organizers of the New Age Banking Summit recognized FCMB with Excellence Award in Alternate Channel Banking (The Guardian, 2017). In furtherance to this, UMS Conferences added that FCMB has continuously demonstrated excellent performance in e-banking and e-payments offerings.

FCMB continues to differentiate itself through its outstanding performance in e-banking services, making banking more exciting and rewarding for its existing and potential customers. The feat FCMB achieved was inspired by its quest to ensure all segments of the population, particularly the under-banked and unbanked adopt the mainstream banking services (Adam, 2017).

4.4.1 Comparative Analysis of E-Banking Practice in GTB and FCMB Banks

The Nigeria banking sector deregulation in 1986 opened a platform for e-banking as “new generation banks” of which GTB and FCMB are part of them. They realised that applying various forms of technologies embraced in a developed country would greatly benefit their banking services (Asiegbu, Nwakanma and Etus 2015; Adenuga and Ilupeju 2012). To this effect, Nigerian banks had to invest in information and communication technology and adopted electronic and communication channels in order to enhance their mode of operation (Inegbedion 2018; Anthony, *et al.* 2018; Adepoju and Alhassan, 2010). The two banks have similarities in their e-banking products and services such as ATM, internet banking, mobile

banking, Point of sales (POS) etc. For example, the two banks ATM machine was introduced in 2004 when Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) mandated all commercial banks in Nigeria to install ATM in strategic areas and their bank premises to serve their customers as part of the reform policy, so as to achieve cashless economy and ensure the efficiency of bank services in the country (Mohammed and Dada 2014). Although the Societe Generale Bank first introduce ATM in Nigeria, followed by First Bank Nigeria Plc in 1991 (Agboola, 2003).

In line with Adepoju and Alhassan, (2010) and Inegbedion *et al.*, (2018), the role of electronic banking is important for banks in Nigeria to survive the competition in the post-consolidation era. Asiegbu, Nwakanma and Etus (2015) further mentioned that Nigerian banks adopted e-banking services to generate insights about their customer behavioural patterns, improve customers' satisfaction through convenient banking, survive and maintain existing market share, achieve sustainable development and to remain globally recognised. Based on these, the GTB and FCMB banks have expanded the scope of their e-banking products and services available to customers. As such, products and services, for example, mobile banking, debit cards, electronic fund transfer (EFT), online banking, ATM and POS are now available (Siyanbola, 2013). The internet usage penetration percentage in Nigeria has depicted in table 4.6 below also contributed to the enabling factor for the GTB and FCMB banks adopting the new e-service channels and products and services.

Table 4.6:
Internet Penetration Rate in Nigeria

Year	Internet users	Penetration (% of population)	Total Population
2019*	126,078,999	61.2%	200,963,599
2018*	112,065,740	57.2%	195,874,683
2017	98,391,456	51.5%	190,873,244
2016	86,219,965	46.1 %	186,987,563
2015	82,094,998	45.1 %	182,201,962
2014	75,746,751	42.7 %	177,475,986
2013	65,670,276	38 %	172,816,517
2012	55,182,852	32.8 %	168,240,403
2011	46,560,001	28.4 %	163,770,669
2010	38,261,938	24 %	159,424,742
2009	31,041,429	20%	155,207,145

Source: National Communication Commission www.ncc.gov.ng/ (assessed 12.9.20)

The table above indicates the scenario regarding internet penetration in Nigeria. Onyeukwu and Osuagwu (2016) noted that new technology adoption such as the internet is an important tool for Nigerian banks to survive in the turbulent business environment, and the number internet users are also crucial to e-banking adoption level. Hence, internet trend in the above table indicated that adoption and usage of the internet increased significantly from 2009-2019 thus brought a great change in the Nigeria banking environment. The significant increases

intensified the spread and adoption of internet used for e-banking services and products in Nigeria, thereby serving as enabling factors for GTB and FCMB adopting electronic banking services for their customers.

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter presents supplementary information about the research. It provides explicitly fruitful insights on the country of study and the background review of the structure of the Nigeria banking industry including the various reforms adopted to reposition the Nigeria banking sector, the particular reform that triggered the adoption e-banking innovations after the consolidation and recapitalisation exercises in Nigeria that helped to strengthened financial services automated products that informed this study. This chapter further analysed the Nigeria banking business environment and established the factors posing significant challenges in the industry. Additional justifications were presented on the choice of the Tier 1 new generation banks: Guaranteed Trust Bank (GTB) and First City Monument Bank (FCMB) used in this study, including a comparative analysis of the e-banking adoption practice. Overall, this chapter established that technological infrastructure utilised by banks affects and influences e-banking products and services adoption in the Nigeria banking environment. Data analysis and results phase of this thesis is presented in the next chapter.

CHAPTER FIVE

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1 Introduction

The preceding chapter, chapter four provides the background information into Banking in Nigeria and established the main influences affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria. The purpose of this chapter is to report the activities related to the quantitative and qualitative phase of this study such as data collection, analysis and discussing the empirical findings of the survey questionnaire and interview to achieve the overall aim of this thesis, which is to provide recommendations to promote e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector. Building on the literature review in chapter two and the various activities undergone in the methodology chapter, this chapter aims to analyse and present the result of this research. To achieve the stated aim, this chapter therefore, comprises two parts.

The first part of this chapter, section 5.2 presents the descriptive analysis and result of the first phase quantitative (survey questionnaire). This section then led to sub-section 5.2.1 where the demographic characteristic of the respondents with respect to e-banking adoption were analysed. Sub-section 5.2.2 then provided the respondents perception about e-banking adoption from the context of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) as detailed in sub-section 2.4.1 of the literature review chapter. Next, is another important section, sub-section 5.2.3 where the most adopted E-Banking channel was analysed and presented. This then led to sub-section 5.2.4 where the research questions were statistically analysed using T-test. Section 5.2.5 then provided the Exploratory Factor Analysis establishing the validity of the constructs via KMO and Bartlett test. Section 5.2.6 established reliability of the constructs through Cronbach Alpha. This section further led to correlation analysis in section 5.2.7 where the relationship between the variables was established. The first part then ends with the overall key findings from the quantitative (questionnaire) phase.

The second part of this chapter goes on to present and analyse the result of the qualitative phase of the study starting with section 5.4. This section contains 3 important sub-sections. Sub-section 5.4.1 presented the gender and age of the participants representing the demographic profile of the participants considered important for the qualitative phase. Sub-section 5.4.2 reports the data collection and analysis process for the qualitative phase as stated in section 3.11.2 of the methodology chapter. Section 5.4.3 discussed the key findings of the qualitative data in line with the main/basic themes identified. This led to section 5.6 where the comparative

analysis of quantitative and qualitative results and findings were incorporated and compared to identify the key findings. Section 5.7 present the overall summary of the findings from the quantitative and qualitative findings. Section 5.1.1 below provides a brief description of the sample of the study.

5.1.1 Description of the Sample

As stated in section 3.6 the methodology chapter, two Nigerian Tier 1 commercial banks; FCMB and GTB were used in this research. This represents 9.1% of the tier 1 commercial banks in the Nigeria banking industry, and two fifty questionnaires (250) were distributed to the respondents for the research. One hundred and seventy-six (176) questionnaires representing a 70.4% response rate were duly completed and returned. A total of ten (10) interviews 5 from each bank were conducted with customers of the banks for the study. To supplement the information obtained from the questionnaire, the researcher had rigorous discussion with the bank customers to obtain detailed information regarding the e-banking channels and the customers perception on their efficiency and quality. Section 5.2 below presents the descriptive analysis of the quantitative phase of the study.

5.2 Descriptive Analysis- Quantitative (Questionnaire)

The primary objective of this section is to present the results and findings of the data analysis in the quantitative phase of the thesis. Hence, this part analyses the data collected through survey questionnaire in line with the responses brought by the research questions for better insight of the customers investigated in the study. Particularly, this chapter attempts to integrate the perception of customers on e-banking adoption in the literature review with the survey findings. More importantly, the importance of this section lies in testing the theoretical model proposed on the factors that affect e-banking adoption in Nigeria stated in section 2.4.1 of the literature chapter. Descriptive statistical analyses of section A, B and C items of the survey instrument were analysed in this section. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used, and T-test method of data analysis was used to test the degree of relationship between the research questions as stated in chapter 3, the methodology chapter of the thesis. Discussion of findings from the respondents provides a full picture of the customers investigated in this thesis. Sub-section 5.2.1 below started with the descriptive analysis of the demographic characteristics associated with the quantitative phase of the study.

5.2.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents (Customers)

The descriptive demographic analysis of the respondents who participated in the research are presented in this section, this includes respondents' gender, age, marital status, income, education, occupation, income, religion and culture. This type of analysis provides a simple description of the main attributes of the collected data and forms the basis of any quantitative study (Trochim and Donnelly, 2001). Frequency analysis were used to distribute the demographic data accordingly to the respondents. This section therefore, presents the descriptive analysis of the demographic questions in section C of the survey instrument (questionnaire). Table 5.1 below presents the overall summary of the descriptive analysis of demographic characteristic of the survey instrument.

Table 5.1: Demographic Profile of Respondents					
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	95	53.7	54.0	54.0
	Female	81	45.8	46.0	100.0
Age	16-25 Years	27	15.3	15.3	15.3
	26-35 Years	41	23.2	23.2	23.2
	36-45 Years	54	30.5	30.5	30.5
	46-55 Years	25	14.1	14.1	14.1
	56-65 Years	21	11.9	11.9	11.9
	Over 66 Years	8	4.5	4.5	100.0
Marital Status	Single	51	28.8	29.0	29.1
	Married	86	48.6	48.9	77.8
	Others	39	22.0	22.2	100.0
Educational Level	High School/College	56	31.6	31.8	31.8
	Diploma/HND	31	17.5	17.6	49.4
	First University Degree	53	29.9	30.1	79.5
	Postgraduate Degree	36	20.3	20.5	100.0
Occupation	Public Servant	37	20.9	21.0	21.0
	Self Employed	57	32.2	32.4	53.4
	Professionals	37	20.9	21.0	74.4
	Others	45	25.4	25.6	100.0
Income	Less than ₦30,000/£60	79	44.6	44.9	44.9
	₦60,000/£120	70	39.5	39.8	84.7
	Over ₦60,000/£120	27	15.3	15.3	100.0
Religion	Islam	89	50.3	50.6	50.6
	Christianity	78	44.1	44.3	94.9
	Traditional	9	5.1	5.1	100.0
Culture	Yoruba culture- South	59	33.3	33.5	33.5
	Hausa-Fulani- North	19	10.7	10.8	44.3
	Igbo Culture- East	56	31.6	31.8	68.2
	Edo-Benin- South-South	42	23.7	23.9	100.0

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

The analysis on gender in table 5.1 above shows that a total of 95 male and 81 females given a total of 176 participated in the survey. This shows that 95 (53.7%) are male and 81(45.8%) are females, although, their number are almost equal. The survey data further reveals that majority of respondents were male (53.7%), meaning that larger percentage of male participated in the

study compared to the female participants. This might be due to the slight difference between male and female number inherent in the Nigeria population (World Population Review, 2020). This finding is in line with prior research findings, indicating that male users of e-banking are many compared to female counterparts' users in Nigeria (Igbenedion *et. al.* 2018), although, both genders were adopter of one e-banking products or the other. This result is also in consistency with the findings of Agwu (2016) who revealed that gender do not influence e-banking uptake in Nigeria. Overall, this results therefore suggest that majority of the respondent were males reflecting the highest adopter of e-banking services in Nigeria to be male.

With respect to age, the data analysis shows that 15.3% of the total respondents are between the age 16-25 years. 23.2% of the respondents are of age category 26-35 years. Respondents between age category 36-45 years are 30.5%. While 14.1% are respondents between age category of 46-55 years. 11.9% of the respondents are of age category 56-65 years, and age category above 66+ years are 8% of the total respondents. The overall findings in respect to the respondents' age reveal that age 36-45 years (30.5%) was the largest group, 26-35 years are the second largest group (23.2%), followed by 16-25 years group (with 15.3%), and the other three groups totally accounted for 30.7% slightly below 31% of the sample. This result is not surprising at all as recent statistics indicated that 15-64 years, approximately 54% is the largest group in Nigeria (Statistica, 2019), indicating relatively working age population. This therefore suggests that most of the respondents are matured enough to give vital information needed for the research without being biased. This result is also evidenced by the interview findings which revealed that people within this age bracket are major adopter of e-banking services. The result is also evidenced by the interview findings which revealed that people within this age bracket are major adopter of e-banking services.

In terms of marital status, the result clearly indicated that that 51(28.8%) of the total respondents are single, 86(48.6%) are married while 39(22%) of the respondents belongs to other marital status. The respondents who are married and who are bank customers almost doubled the single respondents who are also bank customers. To this end, the bank should take cognizance of designing e-banking services that are suitable for the married family more than the single customers. Furthermore, the result further revealed that majority of the respondents were married with 86 frequency representing 48.6% which was the highest among other variable recoded. This implies that the married are more likely to use e-banking in Nigeria, though, both the married and single uses e-banking in Nigeria. This finding is in line with Adekoya (2006) who confirmed marital status as a prominent demographic factor with a strong

effect on e-banking adoption, but in contrary to Agwu, (2016) and who confirmed that marital status do not influence e-banking adoption in Nigeria. In sum, the result therefore suggests that the respondents are matured, emotionally stable and can make reliable decisions on e-banking usage as only 39 frequency representing (22%) were others (either divorced, widow).

With respect to educational qualification, the result clearly shows that 56(31.6%) of the respondents have high school or college education. 31 (17.5%) of the have Diploma or H.N.D education, 53(29.9%) have First University Degree and 36(20.3%) of the total respondents have Post Graduate degree/education. The findings from the data analysis revealed that respondents with First degree are dominant in the research with 29.9%, followed by 36(20.3%) representing people who have a postgraduate degree in terms of Master or Ph.D. Further findings indicated that respondents whose educational level were first university degree and above were more inclined towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria. This finding is in line with the research findings by Hoque (2013); Oyeleye, Sanni and Shittu (2015); Agwu (2014) who confirm that highly educated persons are more likely to use e-banking as they have better information and knowledge on e-banking products and services. Moreover, this finding support Izogo, *et. al.* (2012) who demonstrated that educational level significantly influences e-banking adoption. The finding also indicated that majority of the bank's customers are literate and well-educated which further indicated that participants in the study were very informed which made them understand e-banking adoption in the context of customer satisfaction. Conversely, the educational qualification of the respondents also implies they possess enough education that can enable them provides objective and useful answers to the questionnaire items

In terms of respondents' occupation, the data indicated that 37 frequency representing 20.9% were public servant. 57(32.2%) were self-employed, 45(25.4%) were doing other occupation. 37(20.9%) of the respondents engaged in professional occupations. The results also revealed that the top occupation among the participants in the study were self-employed whose frequency were 57(32.2), next to that were public servant 37(20.9%) and professional occupation 37(20.9%). The findings also revealed that majority of the respondents were fully working in one job or other, for example, teachers, business owners and engineers, and among others. The implication of this is that the respondents with an occupation, with a source of income, are more likely to afford the cost of e-banking. This is in line with the research findings by Kolodinsk, Hogarth and Hilgerr (2004) which revealed that regular income earners are likely to afford the cost of e-banking. This, therefore suggested that all the respondents were fit and capable to make vital contributions towards the research.

On the income question, the data shows that household income of the respondents varied. Majority of the respondents earn ₦30,000/£60. Next to that were those that earn ₦60,000/£120 and the least are those respondents that earn above ₦60,000/£120 per month representing 27(17.3%) of the total. The findings revealed that only 27 (15.3%) of the respondents are high-income earners. On this note, figure 5.1 (appendix) presents the trend of the bank customers income who participated in the study. Hence, the overall findings from the result indicated that those with income of between N30,000/60 – N60,000/120 per month are dominants adopters of e-banking in Nigeria. This implies that lower income earners are more likely not to use e-banking than the higher earners in the Nigeria banking context. The result further indicates that income is a significant factor that affect customers' e-banking uptake in the Nigeria banking industry. This result is supported with the findings of Onyia and Tagg, (2011); Lassar, Manolis, and Lassar, (2005) which revealed that income is a strong predictor of e-banking uptake in developed and developing countries. The histogram shows that the first two high categories of income earners were close to each other and both made over half of the sample. The least in the sample is the lowest income earners who are most likely not able to afford using e-banking services. This, therefore, suggests that the income of the bank customers in terms of their salary can significantly affect e-banking adoption.

Regarding the religion question, the result indicated that the frequency of the highest respondents whose religion dominate the research are Islam 89(50.3%), followed by Christianity 78(44.1%). With the lowest as traditional religion 9 (5.1%). This finding reflects the wider national population of Nigeria and as such not surprising. The implications of this result in the research is that the religion of the respondents determines their adoption for e-banking products and services. This result also indicates that religion is a critical factor that influences e-banking uptake in the Nigeria banking industry. Despite being a strong determinant of e-banking adoption in Nigeria it has received scant attention from studies, only Tarhini, *et. al.* (2015) has studied this variable in their study.

The data analysis on the last question on culture shows that the respondents with the top culture frequency is Yoruba 59 (33.3%), followed by the Igbo culture 56(31.6%), Hausa-Fulani 19 (10.7%) and the least respondents is Edo-Benin culture 42(23.7%). This figure is not surprising, this might be due to the geographical location where the research was conducted, the research was conducted among the respondents who reside in Lagos and Ogun States in the southern part of Nigeria. More importantly, this is also an indication that there is diversity among the respondents and reflecting the wider diversity of culture in Nigeria. So, the implication of this

on the research is that culture is a significant factor in Nigeria banking environment that determines whether customer adopt one e-banking services or another. The studies of Agwu (2017) and Agwu *et. al.* (2014) validate this finding that culture is a strong determinant of e-banking uptake in Nigeria.

In furtherance to the demographic data analysis and result related to the bank customers, the survey instrument also analysed the data related to perception of the respondents regarding factors affecting and influencing e-banking adoption as stated in research question 2. Section 5.2.2 below presents the descriptive statistical analysis of section A of the survey instrument on customers perception about e-banking.

5.2.2 Respondents Perception About E-Banking Adoption

This section structured explicitly to explain the respondent’s perception on e-banking adoption based on the relative advantage/perceived usefulness and complexity of use/perceived ease of use constructs of Technology Acceptance Model (Davis 1989) and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (Rogers 1995) which were the main theoretical underpinning the study. These constructs were intended to examine the factors affecting respondents adopting e-banking services. According to Rogers (1995) these constructs will influence adoption of a given technology or innovation such as e-banking services. Based on these constructs, the following items were used to examine the factors influencing and affecting e-banking adoption. Table 5.2 presents the results of the data analysis.

Table 5.2: Factors influencing and affecting e-banking adoption

<i>Perceived Advantage/Perceived Usefulness</i>						
SN	Items	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Strongly Disagreed	Disagreed	Undecided
1	E-banking make it easier for me to carry out my e-banking transaction	92(51.7%)	45(25.6%)	13(7.4%)	11(6.3%)	15(8.5%)
2	Using E-banking services safe time	91(51.7%)	42(23.9%)	16(9.1%)	17(9.7%)	10(5.7%)
3	I do not see value in using e-banking	92(52.3%)	47(26.7%)	15(8.5%)	12(6.8%)	10(5.7%)
4	E-banking is a convenient banking platform	93(52.8%)	46(26.1%)	16(9.1%)	14(8.0%)	7(4.0%)
5	I may not be able to use traditional banking any longer if I switch to e-banking	54(30.7%)	40(22.7%)	45(25.6%)	27(15.3%)	10(5.7%)
6	More time and efforts are required for necessary information needed to adopt e-banking services.	90(50.6%)	59(33.1%)	5(2.8%)	10(5.7%)	12(6.8%)
7	Adopting the e-banking service and products has really enhance my relationship with the bank	50(28.4%)	42(23.9%)	39(22.2%)	30(19%)	15(8.5%)

Complexity/Perceived Ease of Use of E-banking						
8	E-banking is more difficult to use	22(12.5%)	14(7.9%)	73(41.4%)	64(36.4%)	3(1.7%)
9	Learning how to use E-banking services are easy for me	76(43.1%)	62(36.0%)	18(10.2%)	13(7.3%)	7(3.9%)
Customer Perception about Cost of E-Banking Adoption						
10	Switching cost for adopting e-banking is too expensive	67(38.0%)	64(37.2%)	21(12.2%)	16(9.3%)	4(2.3%)
11	The hidden charges involved in E-banking services make adoption difficult.	60(34.0%)	48(27.2%)	32(36.9%)	28(32.9%)	7(2.8%)
12	Exorbitant transactions charges make me not to adopt all e-banking services.	75(43.6%)	71(40.3%)	13(7.3%)	15(8.5%)	2(1.1%)
Bank Customers Perception on Security and Risk of E-Banking						
13	I am afraid to adopt the e-banking services because of lack of security of the system	61(35.4%)	59(34.3%)	17(9.6%)	21(11.9%)	14(7.9%)
14	Lack of trust in the system makes me not to adopt the service	72(40.9%)	64(36.3%)	21(11.9%)	13(7.4%)	6(3.4%)
15	I cannot use the e-banking services because of fraud	63(35.8%)	61(34.7%)	29(16.5%)	19(10.8%)	4(2.3%)
16	Lack of user protection law makes it difficult for me to use e-banking	82(46.5%)	71(40.3%)	13(7.4%)	10(5.7%)	-
17	Unavailable power supply makes me not to adopt e-banking services	77(43.7%)	75(42.6%)	12(6.8%)	9(5.1%)	3(1.7%)
18	E-banking is not consistent with my cultural and religious belief	7.3(38.9%)	29(16.4%)	56(31.8%)	40(22.7%)	13(7.4%)

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

The result shown in table 5.2 above shows respondents' perception on relative advantage/usefulness of adopting e-banking services in terms of the efficiency, convenience, timing and control of their financial transactions. On a general note, the result of the descriptive analysis shows that a significant number of the respondents had positive perception on the effectiveness of e-banking products/services and that e-banking have higher advantage/usefulness compared to traditional banking as 84.7% (59.7% +25%) agreed and rated effectiveness of e-banking services; 12% (4.5% + 12%) disagreed and 5.1% of the respondents are of the undecided opinion. Overall, a greater percentage of the respondents responded positively on item 1-3 testifying their opinion that e-banking is very effective. Although, 79% (52.3% + 26.7%) of the respondents are of the strongly agreed and agreed opinion and claimed that e-banking does not have extra value attached to them. This is contrary to the 15.3% (8.5% + 6.8%) of the respondents who strongly disagreed and disagreed that using e-banking do add value to them.

The convenience factor of item 5 was higher rated over other items/factors as 78.9% (52.8% + 26.1%) of the respondents claimed that e-banking is convenient. This is then followed by the item on the e-banking instant access to respondents account transactions. Significant numbers of the respondents 75.6% (51.7% + 23.9%) noted that adopting e-banking makes it easy to

carry out e-banking transactions giving them absolute control of their e-banking transactions. However, 13.7% (7.4% + 6.3%) strongly disagree and disagreed the statement that e-banking services make carrying out their banking transactions easy. Thus, this denotes that despite its widely acceptability, its advantages over traditional banking, a significant number of the respondents still have a diverse opinion on the extent to which e-banking allows them to control their account. This may therefore affect the overall adoption of e-banking channels or service. Overall, the result of the perceived advantage/perceived usefulness indicates that these constructs influence e-banking adoption in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with studies of (Inegbedion, *et al* 2018; Xiao, *et. al* 2017; and Tobin 2012) which found perceived advantage/usefulness as significant factors that influence customers towards e-banking adoption, but in contrary to the result of Gounaris and Koritos (2008) and Altun (2009) which revealed that perceived advantage/perceived ease of use do not determine customers' e-banking uptake.

With respect to complexity/perceived ease of use of e-banking. The analysis above shows a significant number of the respondents 77.7% (41.4% + 36.4%) sees e-banking as a very simple and not rigid banking channels. Nevertheless, very little of the respondents 20.4% (12.5% + 7.9%) hold contrary view. Thus, the result findings clearly indicate that more than half of the respondents affirm to the strongly agree or agree opinion, meaning that e-banking enhances banking transactions easily and not difficult to learn its applications. On this note, therefore, it is expected from the result that the adoption of e-banking should be high. Also, the above result further suggests that complexity and perceived ease of use are impediments for e-banking uptake in Nigeria. Inegbedion *et al.* (2018) are of the same view, as they claimed that the complexity of use has a significant impact and influences innovation adoption. This result also validated the view of Bambore and Singla (2017) who claimed that perceive ease of use influences e-banking adoption.

In addition, in terms of customers perception about cost of e-banking adoption. Three major items were included in the questionnaire to examine the cost of E-banking adoption. These items examined the respondents' perceptions regarding e-banking adoption charges, including its hidden cost. However, based on the result of cost e-banking adoption result presented above, it is evident that large percentage of the respondents 74.3% (38.0% + 36.3%) believe that changing from traditional/manual banking to e-banking services attract additional charges that are hidden from the customers and such charges are extremely expensive. This could have been a major factor hindering the adoption of e-banking. Although, participants with the views that, the hidden charges involve in e-banking services makes adoption difficult are just slightly less than those with the view that switching costs for e-banking is expensive. The perception of e-

banking adoption cost, including the hidden cost, makes banking difficult for some banking customers. The result of the hidden cost indicates that a very large number of the respondents 61.2% (34.0% + 27.2%) are of the view that the hidden charges causes e-banking adoption difficulty for them. While, 83.9% (43.6% + 40.3%) are of the view that the exorbitant transaction charges are hindering adopting all the e-banking services compared to the 15.8% (7.3% + 8.5%) who are of the contrary strongly disagreed or disagreed opinion. In all, this result suggests that a significant number of the respondents are of the opinion that the cost of e-banking is a strong determinant for e-banking service adoption. This finding is in parallel with previous research finding, indicating that cost of e-banking is a critical factor for e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking environment (Inegbedion, *et al.* 2019; Agwu *et al.* 2014).

With regards to customers perception on security and risk of e-banking. From the analysis of customer perception on security and risk in table 5.4.4 above. It was discovered that 69.7% (35.4% +34.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed that they are afraid of adopting e-banking services due to the perceived lack of security in the system. This confirms to the findings of Agwu 2017; Ogunloworo and Oladele 2014; that privacy and security are the basic threats hindering e-banking adoption. On this note, this suggests that poor security is a recurrent phenomenon in Nigeria. So far, however, very few respondents, 21.5% (9.6% + 11.9%) strongly disagreed and disagreed that they are afraid of adopting e-banking due to security issues. Also, item 2 result on lack of trust in the system indicates that 40.9% and 36.3% of the total respondents strongly agreed and agreed that lack of trust in the Nigeria banking system makes them not to adopt e-banking. Whilst 11.9% and 7.4% of the strongly disagreed and disagreed that the lack of trust in the system is the reason behind their not adopting e-banking services. Considering their various responses, it, therefore, means that a lack of trust in the system is most likely one of the factors causing low adoption of e-banking in Nigeria.

Furthermore, 35.7% and 34.7% of the total respondents were of the strongly agreed and agreed opinion respectively meaning that they do not use e-banking services due to fraud. 16.5% and 10.8% of the respondents are of the strongly disagreed and disagreed option. While only 2.3% of the respondents are of the undecided option. Considering the strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed option. It, therefore, suggests that customers were not adopting e-banking services due to fraud prominent in the system. From item 4 above, 46.5% strongly agreed, 40.3% agreed that the lack of user protection law in Nigeria causes them not to adopt e-banking services; 7.4% and 5.7% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the item. Therefore, one can safely conclude that lack of protecting law regulating users of e-

banking in Nigeria does not make adoption easy for the customers. In addition, 43.7% and 42.6% of the respondents are of strongly agreed and agreed option respectively. 6.8% and 5.1% are of the strongly disagreed and disagreed opinion, while 1.7% of the respondents are of the undecided option. From the strongly agreed and agreed options, it will be safer to conclude that the unavailable power supply in Nigeria causes low adoption rate. This consolidates the poor connectivity of Nigeria banks when customers use e-banking platform services.

Also, the result on culture and religion belief shown in table 5.4.5 above indicates that 38.9% strongly agreed, 16.4% agreed that e-banking is not consistent with their cultural and religious belief. This indicates that cultural and religious belief are contributory factors to be-banking adoption in Nigeria. 31.8% and 22.7% were of the strongly disagreed and disagreed option to the question. Although, the strongly disagreed and disagreed options were in the contrary opinion that e-banking is not consistent with their cultural and religious belief.

5.2.3 E-Banking Adoption Level

This section presents the adoption level of the various e-banking mechanism or products and services which the respondents used for their financial transaction and the mostly used. The descriptive analysis of the mostly used e-banking channels is illustrated in table 5.3 below.

Table 5.3: Adoption Level of the Various E-Banking Channels						
SN	Items	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Strongly Disagreed	Disagreed	Undecided
1	I often use all E-banking channels	37(21.0%)	28(15.9%)	48(27.2%)	51(30.2%)	12(6.8%)
2	I always use the ATM for my banking transaction everyday	68(38.6%)	70(39.7%)	15(8.5%)	18(4.5%)	5(2.8%)
3	I use Internet banking on daily basis	22(12.5%)	16(9.0%)	74(42.0%)	63(35.7%)	1(0.5%)
4	I always use the mobile banking for my banking transaction	23(13.0%)	39(22.1%)	57(32.3%)	49(27.8%)	8(4.5%)
5	I use the POS everyday	38(21.5%)	25(14.2%)	53(30.1%)	48(27.2%)	12(6.8%)
6	I use EFTs services	19(10.7%)	11(6.25%)	73(41.4%)	64(36.3%)	9(5.1%)

Source: Field Survey, (2019)

Table 5.3 above on analysis of adoption of various e-banking indicates that a significant number of participants 27.2% and 30.2% strongly disagree or disagreed that they use all e-banking channels often. While 21% and 15.9% of the participants indicated that they use all the e-banking channels regularly. Following the analysis, it was evident that 38.6% strongly agree, 39.7% agreed they always use the ATM for their daily banking transaction. While 8.5% and 4.5% of the participants strongly disagreed and disagreed that they always use the ATM for their daily banking, only 0.8% of the participants were of undecided option. The significant percentage of the respondents who use the ATM always for their banking transactions are with the stance of Adeshina and Ayo (2010); Agwu (2014) and Asiegbu, Nwakanma and Etus

(2015) who disclosed in their studies that ATM is the most adopted. In contrary to the ATM been the most adopted and widely use among the e-banking channels. The analysis further shows that internet banking has significant percentage of the respondents, 42.0% strongly disagreed and 35% disagreed that they use internet banking on daily basis. While few percentages of the respondents 25.5% and 9.0% of the revealed they use the internet channel on daily basis.

The analysis on mobile banking shows that significant percentage of the respondents 32.3% and 27.8% strongly disagreed and disagreed that they use the mobile banking always for their banking transaction. While a very few percentages of the respondents acknowledge they use internet banking always for their banking transaction. The result on POS revealed that 30.1% of the respondents strongly disagreed, 27.2% disagreed that they use point-of-sales (POS) every day for their transactions. While 21.5% strongly agreed; 14.2% agreed they use POS every day, and 6.8% of the respondents were of the undecided option on the usage of POS. Finally, the result on Electronic Fund Transfers (EFTs) revealed that significant percentage of the respondents 41.4% and 36.3% strongly disagreed or disagreed they use the EFTs services. While 10.7% and 6.25% of the total respondents strongly agreed or agreed that they use EFTs services; and 5.1% of the respondents were of the undecided opinion on the usage of EFTs.

In addition to the e-banking adoption level by the bank customers, the survey also explored and analysed the most used e-banking channel used for bank transaction. Table 5.4 below presents the summary of the mostly used e-banking among the five channels or products and services used by the respondents.

Table 5.4: The most used e-banking channel		
1	ATM	68(38.6%)
2	Mobile banking	38(21.5%)
3	Internet Banking	23(13.0%)
4	POS	22(12.5%)
5	EFTs	19(10.7%)

According to the analysis above, the findings revealed that 38.6% of the respondents used the ATM for their banking transactions, 21.5% of the respondents used Mobile banking. In addition, 13.0% of the respondents claimed to have used internet banking. 21.5% of the respondents used Point of Sales, while 10.7% of the respondent used electronic fund transfer (EFTs). Figure 5.1 below present the details of the result of most adopted and with most usage of the e-banking. The findings revealed that an ATM is the most adopted of the electronic banking channels with the most usage. This finding further aligns with the findings of Agwu,

et. al. (2014) who carried out study on impediments to e-banking services marketing in developing economies in Nigeria and found ATM as the most adopted. This finding also fit and in consistent with the findings of Ayo, Adebayo and Oni (2010) who confirm ATM as the mostly utilized e-banking channel in Nigeria.

Figure 5.1: E-Banking Channel Mostly Used for Banking Transactions

Source: Generated from Field Survey, 2019

5.2.4 Statistically Testing the Research Questions

It is pertinent to understand all the variables employed in an observed sample to ensure the most influential of them are use (Krzywinski *et al.*, 2016). The statistical test enables the test of the significance of the research questions. So, selecting the appropriate variables for the purpose of testing an observed sample is not an easy decision (Zhang *et al.*, 2015). This section therefore presents the statistical test of the constructs used for e-banking adoption in the table 5.5, table 5.6 and table 5.7 included in the analysis to understand the effect of the selected variables on the result of the proposed e-banking model.

However, the study can rather become complicated due to the big numbers of variables involved in the study (Habing, 2003), and the complexity of this variables could also make some measure different aspect of the same variable. Hence, the study only used directly related variables. As a result, Table 5.5 below present the mean and standard deviations of all constructs used in the questionnaire using T-Test. The result shows moderates and a high mean value of all the variables. The highest means of the various constructs were 2.5284 (adopting the e-banking service and products has really enhanced my relationship with the bank); 3.0682 (E-banking is more difficult to use); 2.2898 (The hidden charges involved in E-banking

services make adoption difficult); 2.2955 (I am afraid to adopt the e-banking services because of lack of security of the system); 3.1875 I always use the ATM for my banking transaction every day whilst the lowest mean of all the variables was 1.7216 (Lack of user protection law makes it difficult for me to use e-banking). Overall, evidence from table 5.5. indicate that a larger number of the respondents were of the view that adopting E-banking saves time, enhance customer-bank relationship and increases customers' satisfaction.

Table 5.5:
T-Test Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	DF	Sig. (2-Tailed)
<i>Perceived Usefulness/ Perceived Advantage</i>					
E-banking make it easier for me to carry out my e-banking transaction	1.9318	1.27208	20.147	175	.000
Using E-banking services save time	1.9375	1.22897	20.915	175	.000
I do not see value in using e-banking	1.8580	1.16484	21.160	175	.000
E-banking is a convenient banking platform	1.8409	1.13022	21.609	175	.000
I may not be able to use traditional banking any longer if I switch to e-banking	2.4261	1.23066	26.154	175	.000
More time and efforts are required for necessary information needed to adopt e-banking services.	1.8352	1.16673	20.868	175	.000
Adopting the e-banking service and products has really enhance my relationship with the bank	2.5284	1.29583	25.885	175	.000
<i>Complexity of Use/ Perceived Ease of Use (CU/PEOU)</i>					
E-banking is more difficult to use	3.0682	1.00621	40.453	175	.000
Learning how to use e-banking services are easy for me	1.9375	1.09103	23.559	175	.000
<i>Cost of E-Banking Adoption</i>					
Switching cost for adopting e-banking is too expensive	2.0057	1.06098	25.079	175	.000
The hidden charges involved in E-banking services make adoption difficult.	2.2898	1.21001	25.105	175	.000
Exorbitant transactions charges make me not to adopt all e-banking services.	1.8523	.96261	25.528	175	.000
<i>Security and Risk</i>					
I am afraid to adopt the e-banking services because of lack of security of the system	2.2955	1.32802	22.931	175	.000
Lack of trust in the system makes me not to adopt the service	1.9602	1.06562	24.404	175	.000
I cannot use the e-banking services because of fraud	2.0909	1.07583	25.784	175	.000
Lack of user protection law makes it difficult for me to use e-banking	1.7216	.83275	27.427	175	.000
Unavailable power supply makes me not to adopt E-banking services	1.7841	.90647	26.111	175	.000
E-banking is not consistent with my cultural and religious belief	2.2955	1.33232	22.857	175	.000
<i>E-Banking Adoption Level</i>					
I often use all e-banking channels and it increases my satisfaction	2.8466	1.24409	30.355	175	.000
I always use the ATM for my banking transaction everyday	3.1875	1.01647	41.602	175	.000
I use Internet banking on daily basis	3.0284	.98809	40.660	175	.000
I always use mobile banking for my banking transaction	2.8864	1.09473	34.978	175	.000
I use the POS everyday	2.8352	1.23802	30.382	175	.000
I use EFTs services	1.9886	1.06898	24.680	175	.000

5.2.5 Exploratory Factor Analysis – Validity Test

An exploratory factor analysis is used for examining the relationship between observed variables that has been measured through some questions or a set of items (Beavers *et al.* 2013). To ensure the variables does not measure what it ought not to measure or measure different aspect of the same variable. Therefore, an exploratory factor analysis was performed on the 24 items/constructs to confirm the construct validity of the e-banking model in section 2.4.1 of the literature chapter. Importantly, the purpose for performing the exploratory factors analysis on the constructs was to explain the variance in the utilized variables regarding latent factors and for gaining clear view of the data so that the output can be used in subsequent analysis (Rietveld and Van, 1993). The criteria employed for factors analysis was in twofold, only factors whose the eigenvalue were equal to 1 or greater than 1 were selected (Habing, 2003), but more importantly the factors structure should be useful meaningful and conceptually sound (Pett, *et al.* 2003).

All the variables influencing and affecting e-banking adoption were factor analysed including the e-banking adoption level variables. The KMO sample adequacy test confirmed there was significant correlation between the variables to proceed for factor analysis. Correspondingly, the chi-square value of the Bartlett test of Sphericity equally indicated that all items included were significant. Table 5.6 presents the result of the KMO and Bartlett test used for factor analysis.

Table 5.6:

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.951	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10820.935
	df	276
	Sig.	.000

Source: Researcher generated

The KMO and Bartlett test led to the performance of exploratory factor analysis. Only variables with at least loading of 0.5 and factors with a reliability threshold of 0.6 were included in the analysis (Hair, *et al.* 2006). In all, 24 variables were factor analysed and all together yielded satisfactory variance of 92.10%. The details of the output of the exploratory factor

analysis performed for the 24 items of the measurement scale using principal components analysis is presented in table 5.7 below.

Table 5.7: Exploratory Factor Analysis				
Variables/Factors	Communality	Eigen Values	% of Variance	Cumulative %
<i>Perceived Usefulness/Perceived Advantage</i>				
E-banking make it easier for me to carry out my e-banking transaction	0.956	20.304	84.600	84.600
Using E-banking services safe time	0.951	1.802	7.509	92.109
I do not see value in using e-banking	0.962		1.881	93.991
E-banking is a convenient banking platform	0.954		1.380	95.371
I may not be able to use traditional banking any longer if I switch to e-banking	0.946		0.877	96.248
More time and efforts are required for necessary information needed to adopt e-banking services.	0.941		0.819	97.067
Adopting the e-banking service and products has really enhance my relationship with the bank	0.945		0.515	97.582
<i>Complexity of Use/ Perceived Ease of Use (CU/PEOU)</i>				
E-banking is more difficult to use	0.941		0.472	98.054
Learning how to use e-banking services are easy for me	0.963		0.319	98.373
<i>Cost of E-Banking Adoption</i>				
Switching cost for adopting e-banking is too expensive	.857		0.287	98.660
The hidden charges involved in E-banking services make adoption difficult.	.812		0.228	98.889
Exorbitant transactions charges make me not to adopt E-banking	.860		0.194	99.083
<i>Security and Risk</i>				
I am afraid to adopt the e-banking services because of lack of security of the system	.939		0.165	99.248
Lack of trust in the system makes me not to adopt the service	.833		0.128	99.376
I cannot use the e-banking services because of fraud	.932		0.114	99.490
Lack of user protection law makes it difficult for me to use e-banking	.916		0.101	99.591
Unavailable power supply makes me not to adopt E-banking services	.900		0.095	99.686
E-banking is not consistent with my cultural and religious belief	.948		0.073	99.760
<i>E-Banking Adoption Level</i>				
I often use all e-banking channels and it increases my satisfaction	.944		0.063	99.823
I always use the ATM for my banking transaction everyday	.949		0.048	99.871
I use Internet banking on daily basis	.881		0.038	99.909
I always use mobile banking for my banking transaction	.939		0.034	99.943
I use the POS everyday	.939		0.032	99.975
I use EFTs services	.900		0.025	100.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

5.2.6 Reliability Analysis

Reliability is assessing the degree of consistency between multiple measurements of a variable. Cronbach's Alpha test was conducted for all the constructs to examine the internal consistency

of the entire scale (Pallant, 2004). According to Hair *et. al.* (2004), a Cronbach alpha value equal or greater than to 0.7 is acceptable and considered to be reliable for the factors. The Cronbach's Alpha value (Table 5.8) for all the constructs ranges from 0.81 to 0.99. This is above the standard guideline of 0.70 and therefore suggest that the scales can be used for analysis as all the constructs had Cronbach's alpha satisfactory value which is above the standard guideline of 0.70 indicating a good reliability of all the constructs/measures. Thus, the constructs are reliable.

Table 5.8:
Reliability Test

Constructs/Measures	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Perceived Advantage/ Perceived Usefulness (PA/PU)	7	.990
Complexity of Use/Perceived Ease of Use (CU/PEOU)	2	.816
Cost of E-Banking Adoption	3	.958
Security and Risk	6	.976
E-Banking Adoption Level	6	.963

5.2.7 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between all the constructs. The Person Product-Monument Coefficient analysis results (Table 5.9) showed positive correlations between the variables meaning that all the variables are well correlated. This correlation analysis was subject to 2 tailed tests at 0.01 significant level and 0.05 significant level respectively.

Table 5.9:

Correlations

Variables	PA/PU	PU/PEOU	Cost of E-Banking Adoption	Security and Risk	All E-Banking Adoption
PA/PU	1	.822** .000	.889** .000	.938** .000	.923** .000
PU/PEOU	.822** .000	1	.739** .000	.755** .000	.908** .000
Cost of E-Banking Adoption	.889** .000	.739** .000	1	.885** .000	.861** .000
Security and Risk	.938** .000	.755** .000	.885** .000	1	.882** .000
All E-Banking Adoption	.923** .000	.908** .000	.861** .000	.882** .000	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). N = 176

5.3 Overall Findings from Quantitative (Questionnaire)

Table 5.10 below provides the summary of finding from the quantitative research

Table 5.10: Summary of Key Findings			
SN	Themes	Key Findings	
1	Demographic variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Marital status • Educational level • Occupation • Income • Religion • Culture 	Influence e-banking adoption
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Age 	Does not influence E-banking adoption
2.	TAM-DIT related factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived usefulness/perceived advantage • Complexity of use/perceived ease of use • Perceived Cost • Perceived security and risk 	Strong E-banking adoption determinant factor
3.	E-banking Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATM, • Internet banking • Mobile banking 	Most utilized E-banking channel
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Point of Sales (POS) • Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) 	Less patronized E-banking channels/products

It can be deduced from the descriptive result of demographic variables shown in the table above that all the demographic characteristics such as age; marital status, educational level, occupation, income, religion and culture were all found to be significant influencing factors determining customers' e-banking adoption. However, the results further indicate that the level of their influences defers, but the overall findings regarding the demographic variables suggest that all the variables except gender and age do not influence, affect and determine the customers' adopting e-banking services adoption in Nigeria.

Furthermore, it was deduced from the descriptive statistics that a significant number of the respondents contends that perceived usefulness/perceived advantage and complexity of use/perceived ease of use of the TAM and DIT models are critical factors that significantly influence, affect and predict e-banking uptake in Nigeria. This finding is found to be consistent with the findings of Inegbedion *et al.* (2018); Agwu *et al.* (2014) and Adeshina and Ayo (2010) who contends that these constructs influence customers' e-banking usage in the Nigeria banking environment. Further to this, the findings on the cost of e-banking revealed that e-banking cost in terms of switching cost and service charge determine its usage or adoption. This finding is in line with the studies of Agwu *et al.* (2014); Kartiwi, Rfieda and Gumawan (2013); Yang and Peterson (2004) which revealed that e-banking switching cost has a

significant positive effect on the customers' commitment to its adoption. With regards to the security and risk constructs, finding indicates that perceived security and risk related to the e-banking greatly influence its adoption. This finding is found to be in parallel with the findings of (Inegbedion *et al.* 2018; Dobdinga, 2013) which suggest that perceived risk and security are very crucial predictor that influence customer e-banking adoption.

Overall, the key findings from the descriptive statistics of the constructs suggest that all the four constructs: perceived advantage/perceived usefulness; complexity of use/perceived ease of use; cost of e-banking; and security and risk were found to be useful predictor and critical factors that influence, affects and determine customers' attitude or intension towards e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking environment. Conversely, it was deduced from the last construct covering the level e-banking adoption that all the e-banking channels ATM; internet banking; mobile banking; POS and EFT all appears to be significant for customers e-banking transaction, but ATM, internet banking and mobile banking remains the most utilized e-banking channels. This finding is consistent with the result revealed by researchers such as (Inegbedion, *et. al.* 2019; Eze, *et. al.*; 2018; Ololade and Ogbeide, 2017). The next section presents the qualitative result and findings.

5.4 Qualitative Analysis (Interview)

The first part presented the results and reported the findings produced in the quantitative phase of this study. Building on these findings, this section reports the findings related to data collection and data analysis related to the qualitative phase. The significance of this section lies in analyzing and discussing the findings of the interviews in order to examine the influences and factors affecting customers towards adopting e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

This section entails three important sections, beginning with section 5.4.1 which provided the gender and age of the participants representing the demographic profile of the participants. Having provided the gender and age of the participants, sub-section 5.4.2 reports the data collection and analysis process. Next, section 5.4.3 discussed the key findings of the qualitative data in line with the basic themes identified. Section 5.6 then conducted a comparative analysis of quantitative and qualitative results by incorporating the findings of both studies to identify key findings. This then led to section 5.7 that presents the overall summary of the findings of the quantitative and qualitative phases.

5.4.1 Gender and Age of Respondents

As noted in section 3.9.2 of the methodology chapter. The interviews were conducted with 10 participants who are bank customers and are e-banking adopters and they all participated

actively in the interview. The table below presents the summary of the participants gender and age.

Table 5.11: Gender and Sex of Participants				
		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Age	16-25 Years	1	-	1
	26-35 Years	1	2	3
	36-45 Years	2	1	3
	46-55 Years	1	1	2
	56-65 Years	1	0	1
	Over 66 Years	-	-	-
Total		6	4	10

Table 5.9 above detailed the gender and age of the participants that took part in the interview. Majority of the participants were male. The reason for this may be attributed to the fact that majority of those that have interest in latest technological innovation in Nigeria are male. Conversely, gender divide inherent in Africa culture may be another reason for the difference in the gender of the participants (Gilwald, Milek and Stork 2010; Olatokun, 2007). More importantly, those between age group 26-35 years and 36-45 years representing six respondents were the most group that took part in the interview and remained the highest adopters. The reason for this may be because those that have regular access to internet needed for the e-banking services are between age 25-50 years in Nigeria and generally in Africa (Ajuwon, 2006). The data was collected for two weeks, specifically from April 2019 to May 2020. Section (5.4.10) below provides the data collection and analysis process.

5.4.2 Data Collection and Analysis Process

As noted in section 3.11.2 of the methodology chapter, this discusses the steps which the researcher undertakes to analyse the data (transcripts) collected during the qualitative phase of this study. Thematic network analysis approach (Attride-Stirling, 2001) with Powell-Taylor and Renner (2003) four-stage qualitative data analysis process was used to form the emerging themes for the analysis. The thematic network analysis process: category codes and concepts identification; themes identification; thematic network development; thematic network description; summary and interpretation of the thematic network. All these activities were then applied to the four-stage qualitative data analysis process (Powell-Taylor and Renner, 2003).

However, interviews must be transcribed before starting the data analysis. In this research as previously stated in section (3.11.2) of the methodology chapter, data collected from the 10 interviews were carefully transcribed word-to-word and verbatim. In consequence, this had resulted to many textual data. The researcher therefore began the analysis of the large

contextual data in accordance with the Powell- Taylo and Renner (2003) four-stage data analysis process. The four-stage process embedded the thematic network activities used for the research (Table 5.12).

Table 5.12: Data collection and analysis process		
No	Stages	Description
1	Collect and analyze interview data	Bank customers interviewed and transcripts that match research questions were selected. Interview were read and re-read Interview were segmented into series of statements and then grouped the statements for analysis
2	Data categorized (Coding)	Concepts and knowledge embedded in interview data extracted answer to answer research questions Identified category labelled
3	Thematic network analysis applied	Basic theme extracted and organized into coherent categories that summarized and bring meaning to the texts
4	Interpret the thematic network	Interview transcripts interpreted and key points from the text identified in the context of the research questions

Source: Researcher’s generated

At the beginning, the researcher read and re-read the interview transcripts carefully. The purpose of this was to familiarize the researcher with the data to make sense out of it; to get better view and summary of what was said in the transcripts, to identify the relevant data that connect with the main theme identified and disregard irrelevant data; and to identify potential patterns that emerge from the data of the interview (Creswell, 2013). Next, the identification of the basic themes and subthemes guided within the contexts of the TAM and DIT proposed framework identified in section (2.4.1) of the literature review chapter. Specifically, perceived usefulness/perceive ease of use; Risk/security; cost; culture and religion contexts were used as the main theme to deductively categorise the content of the data (Cresswell, 2013). To facilitate the coding procedure, all the themes were assigned a code as illustrated in table 5.13 below.

Table 5.13: Categorization/coding of the basic theme		
No	Theme	Code
1	Perceived usefulness/Ease of use	PUEU
2	Security Concern	RST
3	Cost Implications	CST
4	Culture and Religion Perception	CRG

Following the main theme categorization as shown above, chunk of text was further coded to show the relationship and patterns among the data and then relating it to the main theme (Creswell, 2013; Braun, Clarke and Terry, 2014). This gives the researcher opportunity to break the data of the transcripts into smaller chunks to help manage the large interview contents by sorting and labelling the data with codes. Six sub themes further emerged, and codes were assigned to each of the themes and they were traced back into the basic themes. In all, the

researcher arrived at 10 codes from the basic themes the list includes; perceived usefulness, perceived advantage, perceive ease of use, complexity of use, security, privacy, trust, cost of switching, service charge, culture and religion Table 5.14 below detail the basic theme, the codes including their abbreviations presented.

Table 5.14: Sub-Theme coding and abbreviations			
No	Basic theme	Code	Code Abbreviation
1	Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use (PUEU)	Perceived usefulness	PU
2		perceived advantage	PA
3		Perceive ease of use	PEoU
4		Complexity of use	COU
5	Risk and Security (RSoE)	Security	STY
6		Privacy	PVC
7		Trust	TRT
8	Cost (CoS)	Cost of switching	CST
9.		Service charge	SCG
9	CRoE	Culture	CLT
10.		Religion	RLG

Having identified the various themes for the interview data, then a thematic network analysis was applied, all transcripts were organized and summarized coherently to bring meaning to the data. Table 5.13 present example of how every transcript data of the interview were organized and summarized in a meaningful and easy to understand manner. To ensure the findings of each of the interview transcript was properly differentiated to avoid mixed up, a code was further assigned to each extracted segment of the text. For example, code PT3 PU was used for the views of the participants “perceive usefulness and perceive ease of use”. Similarly, the view of participants 5 and 9 on “risk and security” was coded as PT5 STY and PT9 TRT.

Table 5.15: Sub-theme identification with the data				
No	Basic/main theme	Participant	Comments	Data Extract Code
1	Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use (PUEU)	PT3	“I used e-banking services and find it extremely useful, time saving and effortless. Such innovation has added a new dimension to work and personal life, making it easy, noble and gentle”.	PT3 PU
2		PT8	“How can I continue to use e-banking services when the internet that will give me access to online services is not always available when needed and when it does it takes ages to come up”	PT8 PU
3		PT 3	“Yes, personally I have easy access to e-banking products and services because I prefer to do my things online. So, I just make sure my accessibility to these channels are not disrupted by any means. Although, many people do not regularly have easy access to these e-banking services because of poor interconnectivity of the online e-banking channels among the banks and unregulated online banking activities inherent in the Nigeria banking system”.	PT3 PEoU
4	Risk and Security (RSoE)	PT5	“E-banking is not in any way secure than manual banking. I can say I like using-banking only for the convenience it offers. Aside this, too many risks are associated with e-banking usage. My money can be stolen with e-banking usage because of lack of adequate security for e-banking channels by the banks”.	PT5 STY
		PT9	“Honesty, I am not convinient with the bank having my details because of their staff, I do not trust them, they could be fraudulent sometimes, I prefer to go to the bank in person occasionally for e-banking transactions so that I can have evidence for all my transaction”.	PT9 TRT

5.4.3 Findings of the Qualitative Data (Interview)

From the data analysis, 4 basic themes emerged as identified in table 5.11 based on the analysis of the interview transcripts; (1) perceived usefulness/advantage and ease of use; (2) trust, security and privacy; (3) cost of switching; (4) cultural and religion. This section provides the findings related to the various themes in detail.

Theme 1: Perception

Perceived usefulness/advantage. Previous study found significant relationship between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as critical factors in using e-banking (Pikkarainen, *et. al.* 2004). E-banking offers convenience to customers enabling them to access e-banking services at any place and time. Result of the qualitative data shows that majority of the participants acknowledged the advantage of e-banking and their usefulness and some expressed their willingness to adopt other e-banking products and services. The participants overall views are summarized in the words of participants 2, 5, 7 and 9:

Participant 2: *“I used e-banking services and find it extremely useful, time saving and effortless. Such innovation has added a new dimension to work and personal life, making it easy, noble and gentle”*.

This was a comment from an e-banking adopter (customer) that prompt accessibility to e-banking products and services is a major influencing factor to e-banking adoption. Although, some participant complained that lack of infrastructural facilities such as electricity and strong internet facilities or infrastructure are affecting their continuous usage.

Participant 5 commented that: *“my bank manager introduced me to e-banking services since 2003 and it has helped my business greatly, for example, I can check any amount maid to my account instantly with the e-banking service that alone gives me joy”*.

Similarly, accessibility to a system means that customers should not only aware of it but also have access to it. Participant 7 commented with depression:

“How can I continue to use e-banking services when the internet that will give me access to online services is not always available when needed and when it does it takes ages to come up”?

Essentially, the accessibility of a technology is perceived as a measure of relative advantage (Gerrard and Cunningham, 2003). Therefore, it has generally been acknowledged that usefulness and convenience have positive impact on customers e-banking adoption. According to Pikkarainen *et. al.* (2004), interactivity in service provision is an important factor that attracts customers in e-banking acceptance (Gerrard and Cunningham, 2003) also identified the ability of an innovation to meet users' needs as an important factor for e-banking adoption.

The researcher found ease of use to be a significant factor for the participants to adopt e-banking. All the participants believed e-banking is easy to use. Except participant 9 who commented that e-banking is not convenient to operate, and the comment was that:

“I can say that e-banking is difficult to use. Manual banking may not be as convenient as e-banking, but people still find it as a common way of doing banking transactions. Though, electronic banking is more flexible than traditional banking, but to me it can be complicated at times, as I'm not too good in operating computer, for this reason, I have to be extraordinary careful every time while am using e-banking services to avoid my savings not distorted from my account”. Participant 9

Theme 2: Trust, Privacy and Security

Majority of the participants commented they do not have trust in the Nigeria banking system especially when internet is involved; the internet and online banking system in Nigeria are completely unregulated. This is in line with the study by Acha, (2008) who conform that there was no specific law regulating electronic practices in Nigeria. Additional reason given was that using the internet for e-banking services will distort their bank accounts. Virtually all the participants commented were afraid of the ethical practices on internet banking. Participant 2 and 9 echoed this and pointed out that:

“I do not have 100% trust in my bank regarding my details. Infact, I cannot use majority of e-banking products and services”

“I do not trust the system, infact my account has been hacked like 2 times on the internet while shopping with my card details online; and majority of customers using e-banking services would rather go to bank staffs in the banking hall to probably transfer fund to someone’s account or do other transactions if I don’t want to blame myself should things go wrong”.

Another participant commented: *‘Honesty, I am not happy with the bank having my details because of their staff, I do not trust them, they could be fraudulent sometimes, I prefer to go to the bank in person occasionally for e-banking transactions so that I can have evidence for all my transaction’.*

This comment shows how trust influences the participant’s decision to adopt e-banking. Participants often emphasized on trust when answering the interview questions as they believe that nobody should be trusted especially when it involves sensitive information including money.

The researcher noted that there is also fear of using some e-banking services among some educated people in Nigeria. Despite this fact, they are still vast in knowledge and aware of the system. According to participant 10, one of the participants, an MD of an organisation and one of the banks customers for 10 years stated that:

“Lack of IT policy framework, e-commerce laws to regulate e-banking practices and customer protections legislations to protect the customers are some of the reasons why e-banking adoption in Nigeria is still slow or crawling, E-banking adoption depend on effective national information technology Policy. The current IT policy is not comprehensive enough to promote e-banking and minimum IT standard to make e-banking services more easier”.

Privacy

This research found that customers are not too concerned about privacy regarding e-banking activities. Most respondents are of the view that they were aware of the risk involved but the benefits mater as well. Participant 2 stated that:

“Well, I so much believe that my privacy is at risk as my banking details might be used by my banks or third parties who are very much interested in marketing their services to me, but I don’t have issue with that its ok I am happy with the benefits it offers me”.

Users were aware of privacy issues including whether their personal information would be used by non-authorized parties to do what they did not authorize. Most users highlighted that privacy is not an important factor in deciding to adopt the e-banking services.

Security

Security was found as a major determining factor for customers' decision to adopt e-banking. Security is well known challenge for e-banking throughout the globe. Although, banks are using proactive measures and various security protocols to ensure customer details are protected safely during electronic banking transactions. However, public education regarding keeping security details confidential is still fundamental as some e-banking users are still weak and forgetful in keeping their e-banking details to themselves.

Some of the participants emphasized on security as their main reason for opting out or not adopting some electronic banking services. They are of the opinion that electronic banking transactions are not safe because of persistent internet fraud in Nigeria. Participants further emphasized on credit card scams and how their families and friends have been duped. For example, participant 4 commented that *"my friend was ripped off his savings by some fraudsters who pretends to help him at the ATM machine, this was enough warning to desist from using e-banking service"*.

Another participant 7 commented *"I do not even use internet banking again. I visit banking hall every time for my internet transactions. I do not trust the system and those things. I cannot allow the young greedy computer literate steal all my money, customers are frightened by the headlines of media on how customers are daily duped on internet banking, these are evidences that e-banking should no longer be used for banking transaction in this country, although the banks are working actively to right the wrongs"*.

This result is in matched with the study of Agwu, (2017) who investigated customer adoption of electronic banking in Nigeria and found security as one of the significant factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Tarhini *et al.* (2015) also found security as the main concerning factor that influences the customers' decision to adopt electronic banking in Nigeria. Majority of the interviewees claimed that lack of privacy and security issues are among the primary reasons for slow adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. However, participant 7 further stressed that:

"Most bank customers are not aware of e-banking services and because e-banking services are not widely accepted in some part of this country, most customers still find it difficult using ATM cards, mobile banking, telephone banking, for this reason, some customers are still afraid using e-banking services because they think any mistake on any of them like the ATM, internet that means loss of money".

From the findings above, the research found that the participants argued that banks find it extremely difficult to reverse an e-banking transactions that was done by mistake by themselves or another person unknown to them even when customers lodge complaint in the bank, as banks believe that it is difficult for them to manage an e-banking problem when it happens. Nigeria banks are most likely to experience issues even when they try to reverse a failed transaction to

the customer's account due to lack of strong internet access and inadequate power supply. So far, however, e-banking transactions might freeze thereby causing issue for the bank customers as well as the bank.

Theme 3: Cost of Switching

The cost of switching from manual banking to e-banking services coupled with the lack of free switching cost and lack of government policies to prevent e-banking adoption charged are too exorbitant for majority of the customers thus, these switching barriers such as transferring charges, registering for internet banking, using the ATM etc are seen the reasons inhibiting majority of the bank customers from adopting e-banking. The cost implication of e-banking adoption can be summarized from the comments of participants 1, 2 and 9 below.

According to Participant 1:

“Majority of the bank customers cannot afford the cost involved in adopting e-banking and apart from the switching cost, the extra charges such as message alert cost, transfer and card issuance cost are part of the factors contributing to non-adoption of some e-banking services like internet banking”.

According to participant 2 and 9:

“I will say switching to electronic product and services is not easy. The process of switching to a e-banking product can be frustrating at times, because the banks makes it a kind of rigorous process all to profit from it. Again, you will still pay for adopting any of the e-banking service”. Participant 2

“Honestly speaking, cost of switching to e-banking services is exorbitant. The banks made the cost of using the e-banking products and service a bit difficult for the users. This alone and the culture of paying for using bank service online and not in the banking hall is affecting the users' continuous usage”. Participant 9

In the same vein, switching cost was found as one of the major factors that influences the banks customers' e-banking adoption decision and e-banking adoption cost was found not affordable by most of the users. This was in line with the study of Alhaji, Sayf and Rosmaini (2012) who investigated e-banking adoption focusing on consumer behavior in Nigeria and found cost of adoption as a strong factor affecting customer adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. The study also noted that most of the interviewees were of the opinions that exorbitant bank charges and cost of maintaining e-banking adoption such as unreliable power supply and lack of adequate internet infrastructure are among the main reasons for low e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

Theme 4: Culture and Religion

Culture and religion are found to be very significant determinant factor for e-banking adoption. The type of culture and religion of the bank customers are part of the reasons for their adoption or not. According to participant 6:

“I am using e-banking services because my culture and religious belief support its usage, I can tell you that a lot of people are not using the e-banking services because of their religion and cultural beliefs contradict e-banking uptake due to the incessant atrocities and unethical behaviour of banks personnel at times, for this reason, they prefer to avoid innovations that contradict their cultural and religious belief”.

This was the comment of one of the adopters which proves that culture and religion are very strong determinant factors in the adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. This comment matches the finding of Tarhini, *et. al.* (2015) who carried out a qualitative analysis on online banking adoption in Nigeria and found that culture and religion of bank customers are significant factors that determine customers adoption in the Nigeria context, as some Nigerians still find it beneficial to use traditional banking method rather than adopting any of the e-banking channels. Apparently, culture and religion also appear as top factors affecting e-banking adoption among the Nigeria banking customers in this study.

General opinion about the influences affecting e-banking development. The researcher further asked questions on influences affecting e-banking development. From the response, the researcher realised that the participants understanding on e-banking is either too broad or one sided. For this reason, their understanding on the development of e-banking defers. In all, the result on this question was summarized from the responses of the interviewees that answered this question accordingly, the researchers found that lack of necessary infrastructural facilities and inadequate e-banking regulations as major factors identified as influences affecting e-banking adoption in this country. This finding is supported with this statement:

“I think poor internet connection and electricity are affecting e-banking the willingness of the people to use the e-banking products and service” Participant 1

Another participant commented that:

“security, fraud and lack of e-banking policies affects the acceptance e-banking adoption in this country in my own candid opinion. Failure to address these issues will leads to adoption resistance” Participant 8

5.5 Overall Findings from Qualitative (Interview) Phase

Several factors have been identified as factors influencing and affecting e-banking adoption in the qualitative study. Majority of the factors are similar and are dependent on each other. Table 5.16 below present the summary of the key findings from the qualitative result based on the various themes examined.

Table 5.16: Summary of Key Findings		
S/N	Themes	Key Findings
1.	Perceived Usefulness/Ease of Use	❖ Perceived usefulness, relative advantage and ease of use affects and determine e-banking uptake.
2.	Risk and Security	❖ Fear about the security and reliability of the e-banking channels ❖ Risk of losing security details to third parties ❖
3.	Cost implications	❖ Rigorous process and cost for switching to e-banking ❖ Exorbitant cost for using e-banking services eg service charges for debit and credit cards ❖ E-banking maintenance cost eg alternative power supply cost, high internet data cost
4.	Culture and Religion	❖ Religion and cultural belief strongly affect e-banking adoption
5.	Influences affecting e-banking development from the participants customer perspectives	❖ Lack of adequate technological infrastructure (internet) for e-banking transactions on the part of the service providers (banks). ❖ Security and Fraud ❖ Poor internet connection ❖ Epileptic power supply ❖ Lack of e-banking policies and regulations

The researcher presented the overall result of the qualitative study of this research in the above table, the influences and factors that affects e-banking adoption including the cost implication of e-banking has been identified. On this note, the next section presents the comparative analysis of key findings on e-banking adoption from the survey questionnaires and interviews analysis.

5.6 Comparative Analysis of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

As previously mentioned in chapter three the methodology chapter of this research, this study adopted a convergent parallel mixed-method approach. A method that gives room for a parallel collection of quantitative and qualitative data at the same time, and later analysed them separately for the purpose of comparing their results before interpretations and conclusions (Creswell, 2013). Following this methodological approach, it is therefore imperative here to integrate the findings of both the quantitative and qualitative study before the final interpretation.

As further noted in section 5.1.1 of this chapter, the researcher distributed a survey questionnaire for the customers of two of the current existing tier 1 commercial banks in Nigeria. This survey was conducted concurrently with interviews in a bid to unravel the influences and factors that are currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. The overall result of the quantitative phase with respect to demographic characteristics of the respondents found marital status, education, occupation, income, religion and culture as major factors that influence, affect and determine e-banking adoption. Interestingly, the result on culture and religion matches the overall findings of the qualitative study on culture and religion. While the e-banking users (survey respondents) confirmed culture and religion as significant determinant factor influencing e-banking usage in the Nigeria banking environment (see section 5.3). It is crucial to note that this result is parallel with the finding of Tarhini, *et. al* (2015) on e-banking adoption in Nigeria. This result is further substantiated with interviewee's 6 comment:

"I am using e-banking services because my culture and religious belief support its usage, I can tell you that a lot of people are not using the e-banking services because of their religion and cultural beliefs contradict e-banking uptake due to the incessant atrocities and unethical behaviour of banks personnel at times, for this reason, they prefer to avoid innovations that contradict their cultural and religious belief".

In addition to the above findings, the quantitative study and qualitative studies further investigated the influences and factors that are affecting e-banking adoption using some key variables/themes and similarities were found in both findings. Both studies found perceived usefulness/advantage; complexity of use/perceived ease of use as strong factors affecting and influencing customers' intension towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector (see section 5.3 and 5.4.3). The two studies also found security, risk and cost such as electricity cost, internet data cost, debit/credit card issuance cost as critical factors determining e-banking adoption in Nigeria.

Conversely, this research has confirmed from the quantitative study that ATM, internet banking and mobile banking are the most utilized e-banking channels in Nigeria. This finding matches the research of Inegbedion *et. al.* (2019) and Eze *et. al.* (2018) who confirmed that ATM, internet banking and mobile banking as the top e-banking channels used in Nigeria. The qualitative study does not cover this area, rather explore influences affecting e-banking development in Nigeria. Overall, this research has also found deficiencies in technological infrastructure (internet) of the banks, security of e-banking channels (platforms), fraud, poor internet connection and epileptic electricity as the major influences affecting e-banking development in the Nigeria banking environment. In sum, incorporating the quantitative and qualitative results has yielded robust findings towards e-banking adoption in the Nigeria

banking environment. Thus, the summary of key findings needs to be addressed to enhance adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. Figure 5.2 below showcases a best e-banking adoption model generated from the integration of the key findings of the quantitative and qualitative results.

Figure 5.2:
E-banking adoption model

Source: Generated from key research findings

5.7 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study and presented the findings with 176 respondents and 10 participants interviews. In this chapter, a mixed method has been adopted to investigate the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. T-test was conducted to statistically test the research questions, validity and reliability tests were also computed including KMO sample adequacy test and Bartlett test. Through, Person Product-Monument Coefficient analysis results, it was identified that positive correlation exist between all the variables used for the research questions. The data presented and analysed has answer the research objectives stated in chapter one by revealing the key findings influencing and affecting e-banking in Nigeria. Additionally, the overall findings of the study showed that key influences affecting e-banking development and adoption in Nigeria are lack of adequate technological infrastructural facilities such as internet connection, electricity; inadequate e-banking regulations; security and cost. In addition to this, the research further revealed that marital status, education, occupation, income, religion, culture regarded as demographic variables affect e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector. Additionally, perceived usefulness/perceived advantage, perceive ease of use, security and cost are key factors influencing e-banking in Nigeria. ATM, internet banking and mobile banking were revealed as the most adopted channel in the Nigeria banking environment. The next chapter will discuss the research findings of the study in a wider perspective, with purpose of answering the research questions.

CHAPTER SIX

DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapter presents the data analysis and reports the findings generated from the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study. Building on these findings, this chapter aims to discuss the research findings in line with previous studies. Three main sections are embedded in this chapter. Section 6.2 provides the summary of key findings from quantitative and qualitative. Section 6.3 presents a substantive discussion on the key findings of the study identified in figure 5.2 chapter five covering the TAM-DIT related factors affecting and influencing e-banking adoption. This section led to a discussion of the demographic-related factors affecting e-banking in Nigeria. Next is sub-section 6.3.2 which discusses the demographic-related factors affecting e-banking adoption Nigeria. Sub-section 6.3.3 then discusses the most patronized E-banking channels in Nigeria, while sub-section 6.3.4 covering research objective four briefly provides recommendation on future e-banking adoption strategies. Thereafter, section 6.4 then presents the conclusions of the chapter and provide how the aim of this chapter has been achieved.

Before discussing the research findings, the research aims, and objectives addressed in the last chapter of the thesis are restated in line with the methodological approach in table 6.1 below:

SN	Research Objective	Research Questions	Method Adopted
1	To qualitatively ascertain the influences affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria	What are the influences affecting the development of e-banking adoption in Nigeria?	Primary source of data (Interviews of e-banking adopters)
2	To investigate the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria using mixed-method.	What factors are currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector?	Quantitative and qualitative methods (Survey Questionnaire and e-banking adopters' interviews)
3	To ascertain the bank customers most patronised e-banking channels in Nigeria.	What are the most patronized e-banking channels in Nigeria?	Quantitative method (Survey Questionnaire of e-banking users of banks)
		What impacts does the most patronized e-banking services has on customer satisfaction?	Quantitative method (Survey Questionnaire of e-banking adopters who are banks customers)
4	To develop an e-banking model that can help inform the recommendations on future e-banking adoption strategies.	What recommendations are available for the bank managements and other stakeholders to improve e-banking adoption?	

Source: Researcher generated

The first objective focused on the influences affecting the development of e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector using the interview as the primary source of data. Objective two and three focused on the influence of the proposed model designed with TAM and DIT constructs on e-banking adoption in Nigeria. These objectives used both the survey questionnaire and interviews as the main sources of data. The last objective focus on how e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector can be promoted.

As earlier discussed in the chapter three, this study finds its stance in the pragmatist philosophical approach that allows a research study to be conducted with mixed method (Creswell, 2014). Following the methodological approach of the pragmatist, quantitative and qualitative methods were adopted, their findings were integrated in chapter five of this study to investigate the influences and factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. The table 6.1 above shows how each of the study research objectives were tailored towards the research questions and how the objectives addressed the research questions which then led to the achievement of the overall aim of this thesis.

The summary of the findings from survey and interview are provided in section 6.2.

6.2 Summary of Key Findings from Quantitative and Qualitative

SN	Themes	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings
1.	TAM-DIT related factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived usefulness/perceived advantage strongly affect e-banking adoption • Perceived ease of use/complexity of use significantly influence e-banking • Perceived Cost affect e-banking adoption • Perceived security and risk determine e-banking usage • Lack of quality internet • Unreliable electricity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived usefulness, relative advantage and ease of use affects and determine e-banking uptake. • Cost of switching to e-banking and exorbitant e-banking cost for using e-banking services influence e-banking adoption • Fear about the security and fraud influence e-banking adoption and development • Poor internet connection from internet providers • Epileptic power supply <p>Developmental factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of adequate technological infrastructure such as internet speed from the e-banking providers • Lack of e-banking policies and regulations

2.	Demographic variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marital status, Educational level, Occupation, Income affect adoption of e-banking. • Religion and Culture influence e-banking adoption • Gender and Age does not influence E-banking adoption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religion and cultural belief strongly affect e-banking adoption
3.	E-banking Channels mostly patronised	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ATM, Internet banking and Mobile banking most patronized e-banking channel • Point of Sales (POS) and Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) less patronized e-banking channels 	

Source: Author generated from survey questionnaire and interviews

6.3 Discussion of Findings

This section attempts to elaborate on the findings reported in chapter five of this thesis. It also aims to analyse the principal findings of the study identified in figure 5.2 of the previous chapter, summarised in Table 6.2 of this chapter and relate the findings to the literature on e-banking reported in chapter two. As the aim of this research revolves around understanding the factors that affect e-banking adoption in the context of Technology Acceptance Model, Diffusion of Innovation and Demographic constructs, the discussion of the findings is divided into three sections with each section explaining the findings related to a specific context.

6.3.1 Discussion of TAM-DIT related factors

TAM and DIT factors being an important technology adoption framework in banking setting as extensively discussed in section 2.4 of the literature review chapter, surprisingly, in this research, there are some interesting findings that depart from previous studies.

In this study, perceived usefulness/perceived advantage appears to challenge previous research which found perceive usefulness and perceived advantage as not a determinant of e-banking such as Adapa and Roy (2017) and Cheng and Yeung (2015). In fact, this study has found perceived usefulness and relative advantage as significant influencing factor that affects e-banking adoption in Nigeria. The result is consistent with the studies of existing empirical studies in Nigeria and other country such as (Anouze and Alamro, 2020; Inegbedion *et al.* 2018; Tarhini *et al.*, 2015; Agwu *et al.* 2014; Asiegbu, *et al.* 2015; Adeshina and Ayo, 2010; Oladokun and Igbinedion, 2009; Birbirsa, Tesfaye and Hailu, 2019; Bambore and Singla, 2017; Rawashdeh, 2015; Hettiarachchi, 2014; Abu-Assi *et al.* 2014; Wang, *et al.* 2012) which contents that these constructs influences customers' e-banking usage, and to some extent in line with Rodrigues *et al.* (2017). However, the finding of the current study with respect to

perceived usefulness/perceived advantage is inconsistent with previous published empirical studies on e-banking such as (Adapa and Roy, 2017; Cheng and Yeung 2015, Cheung and Lai, 2005). This result therefore suggests that the Nigerian customers are concerned about the perceived usefulness and the relative advantage (convenient) of the e-banking services/products while using the various e-banking products and services, as always claimed by bank marketers that it can save time and reduce the likelihood of inaccurate account balance when adopted. Importantly, this finding demonstrates that the Nigeria bank customers are so much concerned about the usefulness and advantage of the e-banking products and services to keep their adoption. The advantages and usefulness of the e-banking matters so much to the people in the Nigeria banking environment.

Perceived Ease of Use; as identified in section 5.6 of the previous chapter, perceived ease of use was found as a crucial influencing factor that affects customer decision to adopt e-banking in the Nigeria banking environment. This finding means that the Nigeria banks and other stakeholders in the banking industry must make e-banking products and services easier to use to enhance continuous usage. Similarly, the results demonstrate that with ease of use of the service, the problem of ineffective technological infrastructure for e-banking services needed in the bank to make customers feel comfortable while using e-banking services and to enable them to adopt additional services/products would be minimized if not totally eradicated. The complex e-banking switching procedures inherent in the Nigeria banking sector and the long-time taken to make financial transaction are good indicators of problems in the use of e-banking products/services. This result on perceived ease of use as a strong factor affecting e-banking adoption reinforces existing published studies such as (Anouze and Alamro, 2020; Inegbedion, 2018; Agwu, *et al.* 2014; Awara and Anyadigbibe 2014; Abu-Assi *et al.* 2014; Asiegbu, *et al.* 2015; Rawashdeh 2015). However, this finding is exactly different from some research results of Xiao, *et al.* (2017) and Adapa and Roy, (2017) who revealed that perceived ease of use does not influence and affect customers' attitude towards adoption of e-banking services as such is insignificant.

The result of the current study also suggests that cost of e-banking as a major factor currently affecting e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector. This result implies that the cost of using the e-banking services/products is a strong determinant factor affecting the Nigerian bank customers to adopt and continue using e-banking services. The finding regarding the cost may be attributed to the fact that the Nigeria banking customers are so much concerned about the running cost of using e-banking services to determine their adoption or not. More importantly, the cost of using e-banking service/products is relatively high in Nigeria due to

taxes imposed on Nigeria communication companies by the government while average income level of the people is low, the unnecessary charges from the part of the Nigerian banks and the high cost of internet data for e-banking services in Nigeria influenced e-banking adoption in the country. This cost has made it difficult for the bank customers to adopt or sign up for all the e-banking services needed for their banking transactions. The rising cost has also made it difficult for the people to use e-banking. Additionally, the finding demonstrates that the cost of using the e-banking services/products influence their usage. The finding of this research regarding cost is very much in line with extant e-banking studies such as Agwu, 2017; Anouze and Alamro, 2020; Agwu, *et. al.* 2014; Dobdinga, 2013). However, the finding regarding cost of e-banking is inconsistent with Xiao, *et. al.* (2017) who found that cost of e-banking as less significant to affect e-banking adoption.

Security; Apart from IT infrastructure that was discovered as part of the key findings of the factors affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria. Security was equally uncovered as a significant factor that influence e-banking development in the Nigeria banking environment (see fig 5.2, chapter five). The findings presented in table 5.14, section 5.5 of the result and finding chapter found the security and fraud inherent in the Nigeria banking system as key factors responsible for low adoption which in turn affects the development and adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. Though, the Nigerian Government through the Central Bank of Nigeria and the commercial banks have tried to combat security issue in Nigeria through various proactive measures such as extra securities features, policies, warning through e-media and print media, but to no avail (Ezeoha, 2006), human resources and additional policies are still needed. This finding corroborates the findings of published studies on e-banking in Nigeria (Agwu 2017; Tarhini *et. al.* 2015; Awara and Anyadigbibe, 2014; Agwu, Simon and Onwuka, 2016; Bojuwon, 2015; Ogunlowore and Oladele 2014; Adeshina and Ayo, 2010; Chiamaka *et. al.*, 2006) who confirms security as a major hinderance affecting e-banking usage in Nigeria. This finding is further substantiated by (Siyanbola, 2013), who reported that the perpetual e-banking fraudulent activities in the Nigerian banking industry is a great challenge for users, which needs to be resolve by the banking industry to increase e-banking usage and for cashless policy to be effective (Siyanbola, 2013). Oladejo and Yunus, (2008) have earlier found that e-banking users are more vulnerable to risk of using e-banking because of high prevalence of electronic transaction frauds, and computer crimes by the “Yahoo boys” and hackers in Nigeria which affect e-banking usage. However, the present study regarding security does not agree with the study of (Egwali, 2008), who found security not important for e-banking services.

The key finding in relation to security further demonstrates that security of the system as per privacy and that of the e-banking platform, remains a strong determinants factor for the development and adoption of e-banking in the Nigeria banking sector. For this reason, to ensure continual usage of e-banking service/products and increase the adoption by existing and upcoming bank customers, the Nigerian government needs to fight the crime in collaboration with the bank managements, financial regulators and other stakeholders in the financial sector. Furthermore, the government needs to also implement policy and regulations that can combat the security and fraud inherent in the Nigeria banking system in order to instill public confidence, safeguard customers money and in turn encourage adoption of other e-banking services. Conversely, the e-fraud must also be resolved to promote e-banking adoption, because the alarming rate of e-fraud in the Nigeran banking industry has made many bank customers prefer to incur additional costs for cash transactions rather than using e-banking services in Nigeria (Oladejo and Yunus, 2008).

Lack of quality internet; the key findings discovered and identified strong internet as a prominent influencing factor affecting the development of e-banking, including its adoption among the sampled customers. Inegbedion *et. al.* 2018; Agwu 2017; Tarhini *et, al.* 2015; Agwu, Simon and Onwuka, 2016 findings confirmed internet as a strong influence affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Virtually all e-banking studies in Nigeria reported lack of strong internet connection as a prime factor that affect e-banking uptake and development in Nigeria. The reason for this is attributed to lack of strong internet facility from the internet provider and the banks' internet used for their website. This has been recognized as major concern for the users which affects the development and adoption of other e-banking products and services. Poor internet is an issue that needs an urgent attention from major players in the banking and finance industry such as the Government, Bank, IT providers, among others to enhance adoption and development of e-banking in Nigeria.

Developmental factors, as noted in chapter two of this thesis, the Nigerian banks changed their banking IT strategies in order to meet the ever-changing e-banking needs of their customers, but acceptance was reported very low (Agwu, 2017). The studies of Inegbedion 2018; Anthony, *et. al.* 2018; Adepoju and Alhassan, 2010; Chiemeké, *et al.* 2006 on e-banking also reported that the Nigerian banks realised the need to use e-banking services to attain competitive edge, gain customers' loyalty and enhance their mode of operation. Based on these findings, research objective 1 was formulated in a bid to examine the influences that affect the development of e-banking in Nigeria (see Table 6.1, SN 1), and the various findings generated from this research objective in chapter five of this study are discussed as follows;

Lack of adequate IT Infrastructure; as discussed in section 2.3.3 of the literature review chapter, information technology infrastructure has been regarded as important influential factor for e-banking adoption in the banking environment. Correspondingly, in this study, IT infrastructures was found to be one of the influences that affects the development of e-banking in Nigeria. This finding appears to be in parallel with other studies in Nigeria such as (Ovia, 2002; Agwu, 2017; Ononuga, *et. al.*, 2015; Ikpefan *et. al.*, 2018) that found IT infrastructure as understandable important factor that affects the adoption of e-banking in Nigeria. It was also evident from literature that Nigeria banks has invested in IT to enable e-banking adoption, but e-banking adoption does not progress in similar speed (Agwu,2014). On this note, there appears to be a gap regarding uptake, as the Nigeria banks seem to have introduced e-banking services which the core infrastructure in Nigeria cannot accommodate in order to meet the CBN dictates on effective electronic services (Sokari, 2017).

This finding in relation to IT infrastructure is also consistent with the studies of Tunmibi and Falayi (2013) who reported that the Nigeria banking system is ineffective and incapable to accommodate e-banking service. So, based on these findings, the deficiency in IT infrastructures can be concluded as core factor affecting the development of e-banking and likewise responsible for its low adoption in the country. The studies of Ogunlowore and Oladele, (2014); Agwu, (2017) equally identified lack of infrastructure as a prime factor affecting e-banking development and adoption in Nigeria. This finding is further substantiated with the findings of Agwu, (2017) who noted that IT infrastructure in Nigeria are insufficient to promote e-banking development due to inability of the government to implement necessary law and low ability of banks to promote e-banking services. Hence, the key lesson that can be draw from this is that, adequate IT infrastructures in conjunction with effective system is fundamental to facilitate the development and adoption of e-banking in Nigeria.

Lack of e-banking policies and regulations. As noted in section 2.1.3 of the literature review section, there is no specific regulation governing e-banking practices in Nigeria (Edghill and Bird 2019). Correspondingly, in this study, the lack of policy and regulation to safeguard e-banking services has been identified among the principal findings identified in section 5.6 in the analysis and result chapter. Lack of effective policy and regulations to govern electronic banking has been noted as one of the critical factors hindering e-banking development and adoption in Nigeria. This finding fits the study of Agwu, *et. al.* (2014) on e-banking, who found that the lack of ICT policy framework impacts the development of e-banking in Nigeria. In sum, the key lesson drawn from this finding is that effective ICT policy framework to regulate e-banking practices and safeguard the customers is fundamental to enhance e-banking

development and adoption in Nigeria, as inadequate ICT policy can hinder continual usage of e-banking products and services.

Having discussed the TAM-DIT related factors that affect, and influence e-banking adoption as identified in the key findings in this research, the next section discussed the demographic related factors that currently affect the adoption of e-banking in Nigeria based on the key findings.

6.3.2 Demographic related factors

In this section, findings regarding the demographic variables are discussed. The factors affecting the adoption of e-banking in the Nigeria banking sector as identified in table 6.2 of this chapter and section 5.6 of the previous chapter are discussed in relation to previous literature on e-banking adoption.

Despite demographic characteristics being an important determinant in banking setting as literature established, interestingly, some findings of this research differ from prior studies. Demographic factors such as marital status; education; occupation; income; religion and culture were found to be significant factors that affects the adoption of e-banking in Nigeria banking environment. The study identified marital status as critical factor that determine an individual bank customer's adopting e-banking products and services. This demonstrates agreement with the limited studies that specifically consider marital status as a variable of e-banking adoption in Nigeria such as (Adekoya, 2006; Onyia and Tagg 2011) who argued that marital status does influence customers e-banking adoption. On the other hand, this finding is in contrast with some studies conducted in Nigeria and other African contexts (eg Mauritius). Their findings found marital status as insignificant factor that determine e-banking uptake (Agwu, 2016; Gillwald, *et. al.*, 2010).

With respect to education, education was identified as a critical factor that influence e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking context. This result concurred with the findings of (Oyeleye, Sanni and Shittu 2015; Agwu 2014; Onyia and Tagg 2011) suggesting that education is pertinent factor that influence Nigeria bank customers towards e-banking adoption. Similarly, this finding is consistent with earlier study by Shafeei and Mirani (2011) that demonstrates that customers' education can influence their acceptance of e-banking usage. However, the finding does not fit prior study like (Abayomi, *et al.* 2019), which claimed that education is an insignificant factor in e-banking adoption in Nigeria. The education inequalities inherent in the Nigeria environment may be the prime factor that contributes to education being a strong influencing factor affecting e-banking uptake in Nigeria.

Occupation of the bank customers was found as a strong factor that affects the customers towards e-banking adoption. Specifically, the finding reveals that the type of occupation of the sampled bank customers is a strong variable that influences e-banking usage and adoption in Nigeria. This finding matches those of Onyia and Tagg (2011), and Mohammed, (2012). The empirical result on occupation demonstrates that bank customers with high level paying occupation are more likely to use e-banking in Nigeria. This finding implies that the type of occupation of the bank customers remains a strong determinant of e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector.

Income, as identified in section 5.6 of the preceding chapter, was found as a major influencer of e-banking adoption in Nigeria. This finding corroborates the findings of earlier studies that have investigated e-banking adoption in different banking domain (such as Agwu 2017; Lichtenstein and Williamson, 2006; Tuj, 2014; Abayomi, *et al.* 2019). The result further implies that in Nigeria, the level of income of the people determine their decision to adopt or use e-banking service as the cost of using e-banking services is currently high than when e-banking was first introduced. This finding is supported by scholars such as Karjaluoto, *et al.* (2002) and Wan, *et al.* (2005) who argued that people with higher income are more prone to adopt e-banking than people with lower income level.

Religion, as reported in section 5.6, religion was found as a strong factor that affect e-banking adoption of bank customers. This finding matches previous empirical study that investigated e-banking in Nigeria contexts Tarhini, *et al.* (2015) who revealed that religion is an influencer of e-banking usage in the Nigeria. From this finding, it is evident that religion of the people in Nigeria serves as a key determinant for adopting or using e-banking products and services. Considering this fact, religious belief remains a most critical factor considered whether in line with the peoples' religious belief prior to usage. Moreso, adopters of the e-banking services reported in section 5.2.1 of the earlier chapter adopt some of the e-banking services in order to keep the teachings of their respective faith at par with digital world, while at the same time adapt to the persistent, revolutionary change in the information and communication technology. However, since religion appears one of the least demographic characteristic studies in previous published studies, so, it is felt that further research is needed to investigate and confirm this finding.

Culture, as revealed in section 5.6 of this chapter, culture was identified as a critical factor that determine e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector. The empirical result of this variable implies that the culture of the banking customers significantly influences their e-

banking uptake. This finding fits prior empirical published studies on e-banking that have been conducted in Nigeria such as Agwu, (2017) and Agwu *et. al.* (2014). Similarly, this finding substantiates the finding of Tarhini *et. al.* (2015) who reports culture as an influencing factor of e-banking in the Nigeria. Considering this empirical result regarding culture, it demonstrates that many of the customers sampled are cultured people who had one culture or the other, this makes culture to be a strong influencer of e-banking uptake in the Nigeria banking environment.

Having discussed the demographic-related factors affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria with respect to the discussion above, based on this discussion, it can then be concluded that the demographic related factors that affect e-banking adoption in Nigeria has been established. The next section discusses the most patronized e-banking channel in Nigeria.

6.3.3 The Most Patronized E-Banking channels in Nigeria

This section focusses on the key findings already highlighted in section 5.6 of the preceding chapter and summarised in table 6.2 of this chapter, its objective is to discuss the most patronized e-banking among the five products and services investigated in this study.

Survey questionnaire was used to examine the most patronized e-banking channels otherwise refers to as the adoption level of the e-banking products and services by individual bank customers. Findings on the most patronized reveals that ATM, mobile banking internet banking remains the most utilized e-banking channels with highest adoption level. The finding on the five channels investigated; (ATM, mobile banking, internet banking, POS and EFT) suggest that high disparity exist among these e-banking channels, despite the advocacy of the Central Bank of Nigeria to promote e-banking adoption level through cashless policy and the commercial banks various promotions to promote e-banking services or usage.

This study reported 38.6% level of patronage for ATM, followed by mobile banking which is 22.0% and the least of them was EFTs which is just 10.7%. It is crucial to note that the least two patronized channels (POS and EFTs) recorded lower patronage perhaps because POS has not gained popularity in Nigeria, and only available at big departmental stores (Inegedion, *et. al.* 2019). The reason for the low patronage of EFTs is also attributed to the fact that most people in Nigeria fear transferring money electronically because they worry that their account can be hijacked by fraudsters or savvy computer expert who are fast in fraudulent activities.

The ATM has remained the most patronized e-banking channels, this result matches most recent findings on electronic innovations adoption (Inegedion, *et. al.*, 2019; Eze, *et. al.* 2018;

Ololade and Ogbeide, 2017; Ayo and Adeshina, 2010; Chiamaka *et. al.*, 2006). In addition, this result is consistent with those of Yaqub *et al.*, (2013), Foroudi, (2018), and Ernst and Young (an advisory firm on financial business) result in 2014 which found that Nigerian are the highest user of ATM among the 43 ATM users in Africa (Encomium, 2014), and partially inconsistent with Okoro (2014), who reported ATM, internet banking and POS as the most significant with the highest level of patronage, and found mobile banking as insignificant with lower level of patronage. Similarly, the finding on ATM as being the most patronized e-banking channel in Nigeria is also supported by Abubakar, (2014) who noted in his mode of payment research in Nigeria that ATM patronage levels in terms of value and volume of transactions are 90% and 85%. This evidence means that Nigerians are very much aware of the cashless policy of the government and they moved in the direction of making it a success by adopting the ATM channel amongst others for their financial transactions

According to the finding, the second most adopted is *mobile banking*. The reason for this may be because the bank customers perceived mobile banking to be effective for their banking transactions than ATM and other channels (eg POS). Based on this fact, the bank customers belief that the distance challenge attributed to ATM and POS channels are avoided and serves as benefit for adopting mobile banking because of the convenience and portability attached to phones. Moreover, additional evidence from the finding showed that affordability of mobile phone compared to internet banking that requires computer may be another reason for the higher mobile banking adoption level as opposed to internet banking, POS and EFTs. It is pertinent to note that, the high influx of mobile phones into the Nigeria market (Omofe and Egbokhare 2013), and the increase in internet penetration rate in country (Internet Live Stats, 2016) also contributed to the adoption of this mobile banking in the Nigeria banking industry.

Internet Banking. According to the finding, the third most adopted is internet banking. The reason for this may be attributed to the fact that Nigeria likes to be in their comfort zones (quiet area) for financial transactions. The major reason that makes the bank customers to use the internet banking channel than other channels (eg, POS, ETFs) is perhaps because Nigerians strongly believe that the internet banking can afford them comfortability and ease of use. Furthermore, the positive perception of the bank customers regarding the time needed for internet banking compelled them to adopt this channel over others, and another reason for the third most adopted is the time of accessing the internet banking is much easier to connect the computers without locating POS machine for financial transactions. Furthermore, another evidence from the findings showed that the bank customers are motivated to adopt internet banking because it offers them the convenience of making financial transactions at any time

and at any location. These are the part of the reasons for adopting the internet banking than POS and EFTs according to the findings because the bank customers sometimes cannot withstand the stress and the time it takes to successfully make financial transaction on the internet). This finding is substantiated with the result of Pikkarainen, *et. al.* (2004) who found that time, freedom from place and cost savings are main reasons for internet banking adoption. To further enhance adoption, customers' confidence in the system in terms of trust must be instilled.

The most patronized e-banking channel has provided insight into the most utilized e-banking channel concerning their adoption levels. The results suggest that ATM, mobile banking and internet banking appears the most utilized, but ATM remains the most widely patronized amongst all. On this note, it can be concluded that research objective 3 tailored towards research question 3 has been answered.

6.3.4 Recommendation for future e-banking adoption strategies for the bank managements

As earlier stated, the among the principal objectives of this study is to develop an e-banking model that can help inform the recommendations on future e-banking adoption strategies. So, in the light of the reversed version of the e-banking framework produced based on the key findings in figure 5.2, section 5.6 of the preceding chapter, and in line with some constructs of TAM and DIT models. Following this framework, this study recommends that adequate understanding of the various factor identified in the framework are essential for the management and all the bank stakeholders to enhance and promote e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Furthermore, since marital status appears the least demographic variable investigated in existing studies, hence, it is felt that further research is pertinent to confirm and investigate this finding. As religion also appears one of the least demographic characteristic studies in previous published studies, it is also recommended that further research is needed to investigate and confirm this finding. The next section will present the conclusion of the chapter and more details on the recommendations.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter has provided the summary of the key research findings in section 6.3 and has demonstrated how the principal findings are in line with prior studies or differ from the literature review. Additionally, the aim of this chapter has been achieved as the chapter has discussed the developmental factors affecting e-banking in banking and the influencing factors currently affecting e-banking in Nigeria under TAM-DIT related factors in section 6.3.1 and

demographic related factors in section 6.3.2. Furthermore, this chapter has also elaborated on the most patronized E-banking channels in Nigeria in section 6.3.3. Thereafter, this chapter recommended that adequate understanding of various factors outlined in the reversed TAM and DITs are fundamental strategies to boost e-banking adoption level in Nigeria. The next chapter serves as the overall conclusion of the study, providing the main contributions of the thesis, detailing the recommendations made by the research, the implications and limitations of the thesis, and suggestions for future research.

CHAPTER SEVEN

Conclusions, Contributions and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

The previous chapter thoroughly discussed the findings of this research in line with the results of the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study. This final chapter aims to discuss how the research objectives/questions have been achieved. First, this chapter begins with the research objectives and questions, leading to a summary of the key findings that address each of the research questions and the significance of the thesis e-banking model provided in section 7.3. Next, section 7.4 discusses the research contributions; theoretical, methodological and practical contributions. Thereafter, section 7.5 elaborates the research implication for practitioners, and section 7.5.1 examines the implications for Banking Authority in Nigeria. Follow on from this section 7.6 discusses the conclusion and recommendations of the study. This is then followed by section 7.7, which provides the research limitations and challenges. After that, section 7.8 proposes the areas for future research directions. Finally, section 7.9 provides the chapter conclusion.

7.2 Research Objectives and Questions

This section discusses the extent to which the research objectives have been achieved and how the research questions have been answered.

This thesis aimed to investigate the factors affecting customers towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector and provide recommendations to promote e-banking adoption. As stated in chapter one, the research had four objectives which the study has thoroughly addressed. The summary of how each objective has been achieved are presented in the table 7.1 below;

SN	Research Objectives	How the objective has been met
1	To qualitatively ascertain the influences affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria.	This research objective has been achieved through the interviews of e-banking adopters.
2	To investigate the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria using mixed-method.	Survey Questionnaire and interviews was used to identified factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria.
3.	To ascertain the bank customers most patronised e-banking channels in Nigeria.	A quantitative method (Survey Questionnaire) was adopted to ascertain the most patronised e-banking channels by bank customers in Nigeria. users of banks)

4.	To develop an e-banking model that can help inform the recommendations on future e-banking adoption strategies.	An e-banking model has been developed through the principal findings that helped in providing recommendation on e-banking adoption strategies.
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The extent to which the research objectives stated in Table 7.1 has been achieved are further explained below;

The first two objectives focused mainly on the influences affecting e-banking development and adoption in Nigeria using primary sources of data. Specifically, these two objectives have been achieved as the study has used primary sources to supplement influential studies Tarhini, *et al.*, (2015) by incorporating demographic characteristics such as culture and religion to investigate factors impeding e-banking adoption. Furthermore, perceived usefulness/perceived advantages, perceived security, and trust of the TAM-DIT model have also been used to supplement Inegbedion (2018) perceived ease of use factor research to meet these research objectives.

Objective three has been attained by using a questionnaire an instrument adopted to ascertain the most patronise e-banking channel in Nigeria in section 5.2.3 of data analysis and result chapter. Also, the study has used Point of Sales (POS) and Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) to supplemented key influential studies Inegbedion, *et al.*, (2019); Eze, *et. al.*, 2018; Ololade and Ogbeide, (2017) to attain this objective. The study has achieved the last objective by developing a multi-perspective framework from the key research findings which can help inform future e-banking adoption strategies.

Four research questions were generated from the research objectives. The extent to which the research questions have been answered are presented in the summary of the research findings which were discussed in relation to how each of the research questions has been achieved in section 7.3 below;

7.3 Summary of Research Findings

As reported in chapter two, many studies have been conducted on e-banking adoption. Many of the research has been undertaken in developing countries, and very few published research has been conducted on e-banking in developing countries, particularly in Nigeria. There has been a gap in the literature in e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking, particularly in the customer context. A mixed-method has been adopted as the most suitable to address this gap.

The findings that addressed each of the research question and how they have been achieved are stated in section 7.3.1.

7.3.1 Research Question 1

What are the influences affecting the development of e-banking adoption in Nigeria?

This question has been answered through literature review and interviews. The findings related to this research question in presented in chapter six revealed that e-banking is still developing in Nigeria. The interviewees mentioned that a deficiency in IT infrastructure, security and fraud, lack of strong internet connection, lack of effective policy and regulations are the core factors affecting e-banking development and likewise the reasons for its low adoption. Although, the literature review suggests that, the CBN and commercial banks in Nigeria used extra securities features, warnings through print media and e-media to enhance e-banking development in the country, but, to no avail (Ezeoha, 2006). So, adequate technological infrastructure and effective policies are still needed to boost adoption.

7.3.2 Research Question 2

What factors are currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector?

The factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in Nigeria were investigated. Factors such as marital status, education, occupation, income, religion, and culture of the customers highlighted in chapter six were the most significant demographic factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector. Culture and religion of the demographic characteristic were noted as the most critical and impeding factors currently determining e-banking uptake in Nigeria.

Other major factors identified as significant determinants of e-banking usage in Nigeria are perceived usefulness/advantage, perceive ease of use, the cost of e-banking and security. Of these inhibiting factors, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were seen by the majority of the users as the main factors hindering the adoption of some e-banking. It was also noted that some of the e-banking adopters still use virtually all the five e-banking investigated despite the security and fraud inherent in the Nigerian banking environment.

7.3.3 Research Question 3

What are the most patronized e-banking channels in Nigeria?

In respect to the most patronised e-banking channel in Nigeria, the study examined five e-banking channels. The statistical analysis revealed that ATM, mobile banking and internet banking appears most patronised e-banking channel in Nigeria (see section 5.2.3). The major reason for the most adopted e-banking channels is due to the government's cashless policy formulated to enhance e-banking uptake. The study further found two of the channels (POS and ETF) as the least patronised channels in the Nigerian banking sector

7.3.4 Research Question 4

How can e-banking adoption rate be improved in the Nigeria banking sector?

This research question has been answered in section 7.6 the conclusion and recommendations section where future e-banking adoption strategies has been stated.

7.3.5 The Significance of the Developed E-Banking Model

The developed e-banking model highlighted in section 5.6 of the data and result chapter is significant in the following ways:

- The model will inform future researchers interested in e-banking in Nigeria to understand the demographic-related factors and technological-related factors that are strong influencers to e-banking adoption in Nigeria.
- The framework can serve as a reference point for e-banking researchers in Nigeria as it will help them widen their knowledge on the most critical factors that affect e-banking uptake.
- The model will inform future research on e-banking most utilized channels in Nigeria
- It will act as guidelines for upcoming researchers in Nigeria as it will inform their understanding of the critical factors bank customers consider when adopting new technology.

The next section will discuss the contribution of the study.

7.4 Contributions of the Study

This thesis has offered contributions in two broad areas: theoretical contribution related to TAM and DIT model; and contribution in the context of information technology literature. Specifically, the study provides two contributions in respect to the theoretical contributions by (i) establishing the critical influencing factors; (ii) adopting empirical evidence to substantiate the effectiveness of the TAM and DIT framework to investigate new technology adoption. The rest of this chapter will explain how it has been achieved.

7.4.1 Theoretical Contributions

This study builds on existing literature on information technology adoption in the banking context which argued that various factors influenced customer's adoption of new technology. Specifically, the study builds on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT) models to examine the factors that affect and influence customers towards e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector. As literature review suggested that previous studies on e-banking have not sufficiently integrated TAM and DIT variables in E-banking research, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. In this respect, this study has contributed significantly in this area by integrating some constructs of the TAM and

DIT model, and demographic variables to provide greater insight on the factors affecting customers towards e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector.

This research contributes to the body of knowledge by increasing our understanding of the various factors determining the decision to adopt new technology, particularly e-banking. In this regard, this thesis has contributed to TAM and DIM models by blending some constructs of the two models together (perceived usefulness/perceived advantage; perceived ease of use/complexity of use; and other constructs (perceived security; perceived trust; perceived cost/service charge; perceived risk; quality internet connection and reliable power) in the quantitative phase to explore the factors influencing customers decision to adopt e-banking. The qualitative study also confirms these constructs as a significant critical factor that affects e-banking adoption in Nigeria, as discussed in section 5.4.3 of the data analysis and result chapter. It can then be concluded that this study has provided reasonable insight into the understanding of the factors that influence and affects e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking context.

Furthermore, this study contributes to the current body of knowledge on e-banking adoption in the banking context. This research has improved our understanding regarding the significance of the TAM and DIT in the adoption of a particular e-banking product or service. Essentially, unlike the previous studies (Ayo and Adeshina, 2010; Onyia and Tagg 2012; Tarhini, *et al*, 2015; Agwu, 2017; Inegedion, *et al.*, 2019), this study has formulated a model that provides three contexts to understanding the factors affecting e-banking adoption (TAM, DIT and demographic variables (see section 2.4.1). The model in section 5.6 discusses how demographic characteristics serves as critical influencing factors for Nigeria bank customers' decision to adopt e-banking innovations.

Conversely, this study has contributed greatly to the major limitations of e-banking research, specifically in the areas of culture and religion in developing country such as Nigeria. More specifically, this study has addressed the lack of study on e-banking adoption in culture and religion contexts, as prior studies conducted in developing countries has suggested the study of other factors such as culture and religion (Tarhini, *et al.* 2015). It can then be said that the current study has added to the scant literature on e-banking in religion and cultural contexts in Nigeria, and this study is among the first in Nigeria to study e-banking adoption in relation to culture and religion. As such, this thesis serves as a response to the clarion calls of researchers (Tarhini *et al.* 2015; Agwu 2017); and is of great importance to the overall body of knowledge.

Furthermore, the study has contributed by revealing that the most adopted e-banking channels in Nigeria is ATM, followed by Internet Banking and then Mobile Banking.

In sum, the research has added to literature on e-banking adoption in customer context by investigating the uptake of different e-banking products and contributed to academic research on e-banking adoption in the banking industry. The next section discussed the methodological contributions of the study.

7.4.2 Methodological Contributions

The methodological contribution of the study is in two areas; (i) the study has contributed significantly to the limited mixed-method studies on e-banking. The research methodology adopted for this research is not new but scanty in literature. Many of the e-banking researches such as Inegbedion, (2019), Orji, *et al.* (2018); Agwu, (2017); Ogunlowore and Oladele, (2014); Aliyu, Younus and Tasmin (2012); Tarhini, *et al.* (2015); Agwu (2017) mainly focused on quantitative study or qualitative study, they completely ignore the mixed research method due to its complexity. The researcher has been able to incorporate both methods to provide a more holistic understanding of the factors affecting e-banking in Nigeria by using mixed-method. This research confirms that the mixed-method approach in e-banking allows a greater understanding of the e-banking influencing factors.

Furthermore, this study provided statistical analysis such as; T-test analysis and correlation analysis to contribute to methodological practice. The reason for using the statistical method was made explicit to encourage future researchers and to promote adoption despite the complexity it entails for analysis. More specifically, the adoption of the statistical analysis provides a deeper insight into e-banking factors, thus, has helped the researcher to offer significant methodological contributions from a statistical perspective.

7.4.3 Practical Contributions

This research has contributed to practice by revealing the six-demographic influencer of e-banking adoption (marital status, educational level, occupation, income, religion and culture). Furthermore, the research also contributed to practice by showcasing the critical factors that influence e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking context. The banking practitioners, government agencies and policy makers can then devise proactive strategies that can enhance adoption of the five e-banking products/channels based on this research results and findings. High level of commitment may be required to devise the strategies needed to promote the e-banking product adoption, the study model has helped to provide the influencing and affecting

variables. From this, banking practitioners and stakeholders can prioritise the variables based on the ones considered most important to them.

In the next sub-section, the research implications to practitioners and banking authority are discussed.

7.5 The Research Implication for Practitioners (Managerial)

The empirical findings of the current study have useful implications for commercial banks operating in the country. The most important of the implications from the findings is the development of a model that can be employed by the Nigerian e-banking practitioners to determine the demographic-related factors and technological-related factors that serves as a strong influencer to e-banking adoption. The commercial banks in Nigeria including other practitioners of e-banking could make use of the revised model generated according to finding in section 5.6 of this study: (i) to generate insight of the factors that affects e-banking development in Nigeria; (ii) to get awareness about the various influences affecting e-banking uptake in Nigeria; and (iii) to determine the most patronized e-banking channels in the Nigeria banking environment.

Another managerial implication of this study hinges on the developmental factors. This study identifies five developmental factors (see section 6.3.1) that affects e-banking development in Nigeria. The finding on these factors suggests that they are the prime factors that affect e-banking development in the Nigeria banking system. Two out of the five factors (IT infrastructure and security) are related to e-banking service providers. The bank management will need to re-engineer their IT system to facilitate e-banking uptake. Furthermore, e-banking service providers need to address the securities features in their IT system in order to instill customer confidence in e-banking, to assure them that e-banking products and services are safe. Banks managers will need to use the right promotion tools to send effective message to current e-banking and upcoming users that the security of their IT system is adequate to enable users to feel comfortable when using e-banking services.

In general, another implication from the study is that the perceived usefulness/advantage; and perceived ease of use/complexity of use shows they are very strong motivator of customer e-banking adoption and continual usage. This result is essentially important for the bank managers in devising efficient strategies that can promote e-banking service delivery medium, expand their customers base and retain the existing customers (Adapa and Roy, 2017). Specifically, e-banking practitioners need to develop better strategies relating to marketing and communicating their e-banking services to widely publicize the advantages, the ease associated

with using e-banking products, and to encourage adoption of the less adopted products. Banks can employ advertising to influence their consumers' attitudes towards uptake of the e-bank products (Page and Luding, 2003). Bankers can also create awareness about the usefulness/advantage associated with the e-banking to enhance adoption through personal selling, a method considered viable for creating awareness and influencing customer's attitude (Kasper, *et al.*, 1999). Furthermore, the e-banking providers need to focus more on how to make their e-banking delivery channels easy to use and reliable so that customers can feel confident using the channels conveniently and repeatedly for a positive experience by providing service according to the needs of their customers and including monetary benefits for adopters of e-banking products to help boost customers motivation and willingness towards e-banking uptake.

The implication arising from the demographic related factors indicate that culture and religion are critical factors for e-banking adoption in Nigeria. As noted in section 6.3.1 of this research findings, the findings suggest that culture and religion strongly influence e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking environment, implying that e-banking managers and other e-banking practitioners need to make their e-banking service more compatible with the culture, religious belief and the lifestyle of their customers in order to promote e-banking uptake. With value-added e-banking services and various support, the more likely the customers perceive e-banking to be useful, which will in turn increase the adoption of their products. Thus, e-banking practitioners should focus more on designing effective, reliable and easy to use banking services and better customer relationship management, for instance, including user-friendly options in their e-banking interface.

In addition, another important implication is related to the most adopted e-banking channels. The research findings (see section 6.3.3) revealed that in sum, customer use ATM, mobile banking and internet banking than POS and EFT. ATM, mobile banking and internet banking adoption are increasing while the adoption of POS and EFT are declining. This implies that banks need to create awareness on the channels with less patronage, communicate the relative advantage of POS and EFT channels compared to other banking channels that requires physical presence in the bank. In all, banks need to reduce customer perceived risk regarding e-banking channels by offering specific guarantees to protect them and treat their complaints urgently.

7.5.1 Implications for Bank Authority: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)

The implication for CBN in this study can be seen from general perspective and specific perspectives explain below;

- **General Implications:** These are general implications that are related to the findings of the research model and the descriptive analysis in section 5.2 and section 5.2.3 of this thesis. The most important implication in this area is related to the development of a TAM-DIT and demographic based-model of variables affecting and influencing customers towards e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking domain. Importantly, this model has clearly highlighted the influencing factors and states how they play a critical role in customers decision to use e-banking services. This model can help Nigeria banking policymakers, particularly Central Bank of Nigeria to develop strategies that could help bank customers understand why they need to adopt e-banking services, and how to promote e-banking adoption rate in Nigeria. Most importantly, this research's descriptive results have revealed that the sampled bank customers are either adopters of all the five e-banking channels or part users who have the intention to adopt other channels in the future. Bank authorities need to make use of these findings to promote e-banking adoption in Nigeria.
- **Specific Implication.** This is the implication that emerged from the TAM-DIT and demographic factors examined in this study. The finding of this research in section 5.5 highlight lack of electricity as hindrance affecting e-banking development and adoption. This finding suggests that the stress and cost of sourcing for alternative power to use e-banking impact customers' decision to adopt e-banking services in Nigeria. Following this finding, therefore, the bank authority in Nigeria should formulate policies that will help combat the electricity issue in Nigeria to help increase e-banking adoption by existing adopters and the upcoming or future adopters.

The finding of this study also found the internet to be a significant factor that influence e-banking in Nigeria. The result of the findings indicates that the poor internet connection in Nigeria impede e-banking adoption, the slow internet peculiar in the Nigeria business environment has affected uptake of e-banking channels. This has significant implication for the banking regulators, hence, the implication of this finding is that the Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC) also needs to put policies that will enable internet providers to provide better internet services in order to promote e-banking service adoption.

Having provided this research implications for e-banking practitioners, bank authority and other important stakeholders, the next section provide the overall conclusion and recommendations of this study.

7.6 Conclusions and Recommendations

This research provides useful insights into the factors that affect customers towards e-banking adoption. All variables identified influencing e-banking uptake in this current research are technology-based and demographic-based factors. Following these findings and in line with the research objective of the study, this research concludes that addressing these factors are fundamental to promote e-banking adoption in Nigeria. In view of this study's various findings, this research, therefore, answered research objective 4 by providing several recommendations for banks, banking authorities, and other related authorities on how e-banking can be enhanced in Nigeria as;

- Banks should utilize user-friendly, easily navigated information technologies that meet customers need to provide e-banking services and products for their customers, where there is change in customer's need, the bank should adjust their technologies as well, to ensure their technology delivery system work in same direction with their ever-changing customers' need.
- Furthermore, bank management should play a major role in ensuring effective e-banking delivery. Relevant strategies towards enhancing customers patronage should be generated where necessary. In addition, all bank needs to develop a strategy to sensitize their customers and the general public on why they need-to adopt e-banking services. Doing this will result in a multiplier effect in the long-run, because e-banking services adoption is important to make the Nigeria banking industry move in the same direction with advanced countries such as UK, USA, Canada who have incorporated effective e-banking models to their banking service.
- Similarly, banks should continue to stress the important of adopting e-banking services, and emphasis should be lay on how e-banking services are gradually taking over from traditional method of banking to stimulate customers' interest and elicit their positive attitude towards adoption.
- Bank management are advised to improve their E-banking channels such as ATMs, Internet Banking, and Mobile Banking relentlessly, urgently redesign them in such a way that they will be easy for customers to use, as not all customers find the channels easy to use, especially the older customers. Providing 24/7 and every day online support and giving users the choice for their preferred language will promote e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Banking authorities can also designate personnel at relevant e-banking facilities, for example at the ATM stand to help customers who are stuck or having difficulties using the

ATM. Providing this instant support can enable customers with difficulties learn and get acquainted with such e-banking services.

- It is equally important for banks to sensitize their customers to enhance customers perception on e-banking adoption cost including the hidden cost as a very large number of the respondents 83.9% are of the view that the exorbitant transaction charges are hindering their adoption of some service. From this result, conscious efforts of the banks and government are crucial to reduce the switching cost as a matter of urgency.
- Moreover, the banking authorities must use all available means to educate and train their customers, on how to avoid being victim of online scammers, how to recognize messages from banks. Such education could help to allay customers' fears on e-banking associated risks and see the need to adopt more e-banking service.
- The Nigeria commercial banks should create awareness of all their e-banking services to enhance adoption rate. They can use radio jingles, posters, fliers and seminars to create awareness of the e-banking products and services.
- It is also recommended that the Nigeria banks should not exploit their customers by attaching unnecessary e-banking charges to their customers. But, where this is not possible, the bank should ensure that the cost of transacting in the banking hall does not exceed costs of using e-banking.
- The Nigeria banking industry needs to take security of their e-banking sites into serious consideration as websites hacking and fraud still dominate the Nigeria banking sector. Perhaps, the banking authorities can incorporate more advanced encryption to protect their internet website from unauthorize access.
- In all, this study recommends that the Nigerian government should implement e-banking policies that will enable bank customers to migrate from traditional banking to e-banking services. Specific e-banking policies such as E-Sign Act should also be formulated to facilitate e-banking adoption rate in Nigeria. Furthermore, the government and banks should adopt a tandem approach to increase e-banking adoption among the lower-income earners in Nigeria. Conversely, the Central Bank of Nigeria should establish law and policies in line with international standard to promulgate and enforce cybercrimes as previously suggested by Ezeoha, (2006), to promote e-banking adoption.

7.7 Research Limitations and Challenges

Every research irrespective of how they have been carefully planned are expected to have limitations and challenges that occur in the research process to prevent the execution of the

study plan and which are beyond the control of the researcher, this study is not an exception. Thus, the limitations and challenges of this research are provided as follows:

- This research was limited in geographical context. This study was geographically biased as the focused on commercial banks in Lagos and Ogun State in Nigeria where the researcher has access to the data and where the headquarter of commercial banks in Nigeria are located. Including other state in this study would have been difficult because of accessibility to required data.
- Furthermore, interviewing some participants such as participant 2 and 7 was quite challenging. The travel costs to get the data needed for the second phase negatively impacted the budgeted cost of administering the questionnaire. For future research, a realistic sum is recommended.
- This study was restricted to only two commercial banks customers which are new generations banks; GTB and FCMB, the study has overlooked incorporation of old generation banks customers
- The research focused only on customers who are already users of e-banking products and services, including non-adopters would have been better for the study
- Furthermore, little research has been undertaken on demographic characteristic factors such as culture and religion in relation to e-banking adoption among bank customers, making it difficult to obtain literature on these factors which also makes it crucial to investigate this research area further.
- The sample size for the first phase of this study was not large which hinder generalizing the results of this research to the entire banking sector in Nigeria.
- Adopting the mixed method approach for this research was very challenging, as it is time-consuming and complex to incorporate the two phases of the research adequately as required

Despite the limitations and challenges of this research, this study was able to be completed within the required time and contributed to the general body of knowledge

7.8 Future Research Direction

Several areas for future research arise from this study. First, future studies need to determine the extent to which this research results can be generalized. They can use the conceptual model of this study to investigate the factors determining e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking industry. Another way to investigate the result of this study is by using the revised model in section 5.6 to examine how the revised model in this study could be used to investigate factors

that influence e-banking adoption of both users and non-users (non-adopters). Adopting this perspective to investigate the influencing factors towards adoption would provide deeper insight into the revised model of factors influencing customers' decision to adopt e-banking. Furthermore, future research can replicate this research in the banking sector of other Africa or developing countries. Other research is also needed in this area to re-examine whether there are other factors that affect customers' e-banking uptake in other contexts. Extending the research to all banks and not only the new generation commercial banks will triangulate the results of this study.

In addition, further research could be conducted on other variables that influence e-banking adoption as the current study only covers demographic related variables; TAM and DIT related variables; and does not cover other variables that can determine e-banking adoption. Moreover, as religion appears one of the least demographics determining factors studied in previous published research, so, it is felt that further research is needed to investigate and confirm the result of this construct.

Adopting other theories to examine the influencing factors would significantly support upcoming researchers and banking authority in Nigeria. Conducting a comparative study in other developing countries with a similar condition as Nigeria would extensively enhance and contribute to current academic knowledge.

The overall suggestion for future research is that all constructs of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovation Theories should be blended together using a mixed-method approach for a rich understanding of the factors that influence customers e-banking adoption. Taking this approach would help to address the lack of research with a blend of qualitative and quantitative methods in e-banking studies.

7.9 Closing Remarks

This research investigated the influences affecting e-banking development and the factors currently affecting e-banking adoption in the Nigerian banking sector. As a result, the study has been able to report the constructs that impede the e-banking adoption and recommendation has been provided on future e-banking strategies to enhance e-banking uptake.

This thesis has contributed to the limited knowledge on e-banking adoption by using mixed methods to provide deeper understanding of the variables that affect e-banking in a developing country context. Specifically, in this study, a convergent mixed-method approach has been adopted to provide better picture of the Technological Acceptance-Diffusion of Innovation

related factors and demographic factors that impede the e-banking adoption of commercial banks customers in Nigeria.

Furthermore, a revised version of e-banking adoption model has been formulated. In this thesis, the research implications in theory and in practice has been provided and recommendations and suggestions for further research provided. Therefore, it can then be concluded that this study has contributed theoretically, empirically and methodologically to knowledge from statistical point of view. In sum, the findings reported in this has helped to provide new insight of the e-banking influencing factors and its various channels.

CHAPTER EIGHT

Reflective Summary

8.1 Critical Reflective Summary

In this chapter, the researcher reflects on how her DBA journey and experience from the start of the Doctoral programme has led to the completion of this DBA thesis. Reflection involves “looking back on an experience and making sense of it to identify what to do in the future” (Drew and Bingham, 2001:221). The reflective account starts with section 8.2 which discusses the thought modules of the DBA programme such as Strategic Thinking and Value Management (STVM), Strategy into Action (SIA), Leadership and Professional Development (LPD) and Research Methodology and Proposal (RMP). Section 8.3 explains how the researcher was able to move to the second year of the DBA programme in January 2018 to begin the research. Furthermore, the researcher also elaborates on the lessons learnt doing the DBA. The details of the researcher’s career goals are explained in section 8.4, and the summary of the reflection are presented in section 8.5.

8.2 DBA First Year

I began my DBA programme in March 2017 with two modules in two semesters. The modules titles are Strategic Thinking and Value Management (STVM) and Strategy into Action (SIA) Value Management thought from March 2017 to June 2017. I was able to enrich and adds to my knowledge on the importance of strategy in any organisation, particularly how strategies can be turned into action.

During this period, I was expected to complete two assignments on STVM and SIA which were consultancy reports, they were done and completed before the due date.

The STVM assignment involved choosing a business entity that was well known and researched about the current strategic issues affecting the company. The SIA assignment also requires researching a company of choice and write a strategic report about their culture, where I choose Dropbox. At first, writing the two assignments was very difficult for me, as I had never been involved in researching more than two companies at a time to identify the companies with current strategic issues and cultural problem. Also, writing the two reports was challenging for me and very time-consuming, as I had no adequate research skills needed for the assignments. At the end of my research about the companies, I was able to identify the issues with the two companies. I finally choose Dropbox for the STVM assignment and Barclays Bank Plc for the SIA. I wrote my consultancy report on how Dropbox can improve their service as there were rated low by their customers, and how Barclays Bank can adopt a

balanced innovation and change management to overcome the trust and reputation issues, I selected Barclays Bank Plc as they were having these issues as at the time I was conducting the report due to their poor customer service as at that time. After my rigorous research into Dropbox current strategic problem, my research skill improved, and I was still able to complete the two reports before the due date. Despite this challenge, at the end, I scored Bs in both modules.

Looking back, I thought I should have limited my search criteria to a particular business sector or organisation, rather than searching for more than two companies and their challenges at the same time, which could have saved my time and energy. Nonetheless, the two assignments improved my critical thinking and research skills and had helped me to learn how to use some models such as Metal Model, a framework used for examining the system state of an organisation at a particular period to ascertain organisation's issue, and Canvas Business Model. Essentially, I felt great I was able to learn how to write a consultancy report in practice through the SIA module, business consultant an area I intend to work after successfully completing my DBA

During second semester of my DBA, two modules were thought; Research Methodology Proposal and Leadership and Professional Development. The Research Methodology and Proposal module helped in choosing my research area and topic and also exposed me to different research methodologies and choosing the most appropriate for my research. With this module, I was able to identify my research area and finalised the country I will be researching, as I was also considering banking innovation in other developing countries. After my extensive research into other developing countries, I concluded researching on banking innovation in Nigeria context. The Nigeria banking sector was finally selected because I look forward to working in the banking sector after my DBA research. At first, it was very difficult for me to write the proposal of the selected area due to inability to identify the most appropriate article for the research. This was very challenging but, I was able to get the final draft completed before the submission date. At the end, I passed the module and I received positive feedback from the module leader compared to my colleagues who were asked to resubmit, this was because I was able to write the problem statement and provide justification of my research area. On the other hand, the Leadership and Professional Development (LPD) module enrich my understanding of different leadership styles of organisation leaders and how leadership style of the leaders can influence organizational performance. The module also helped me to understand how I can develop my PDP over a period. Similarly, my PDP enabled me to devise my long-term goal over five years and what would happen during and after my DBA journey.

8.3 Research Phase (DBA Year Two)

The research phase of the DBA began after I passed my research proposal in year one. DBA two began in 2018 January to be precise. I started this research phase first with the literature review of my thesis, which was one of the most difficult part for me, as it was very time consuming and difficult for me to grasp the author's opinion. Finding the appropriate literature on e-banking in Nigeria and in a global context was my first challenge. Although, I was happy I started my literature review, but, I realised that the literature on e-banking adoption in developing countries such as Nigeria are limited and not sufficiently researched compared to the literature on developed countries such as the United Kingdom, United States of America, Australia among others, which was the beginning of identifying the research gap from literature. That was not a pleasant experience for me which affected my research progress slightly. Then, I invested lots of time researching around my research area and I found five interesting articles that were written in Nigeria context that informed my research, these studies are Tarhini, *et. al.* (2015), Bojuwon (2015), Agwu *et. al* (2017), Olawepo (2013), Adesina and Ayo (2010), and from these studies I was able to formulate my research questions.

While the study of Tarhini *et al.* (2015), Bojuwon (2015) and Agwu *et. al* (2017) reported low adoption of e-banking in Nigeria, Olawepo (2013) claimed that e-banking in Nigeria was not sufficiently researched, these studies failed to report fully the factors hinder the adoption of the e-banking service. The findings from these articles influenced and caught my attention to want to investigate the factors that affect customers attitude towards adoption of e-banking in Nigeria.

My experience of reading articles intensified after I read all these studies. Then, I proceeded to reading e- banking studies not only in Nigeria context but also in developed countries to generate literature suitable for the e-banking in a global context in my research.

Majority of the articles established that perceived ease of use, complexity of use, perceived usefulness, perceived advantage, security and cost influence e-banking uptake. Similarly, one of the inspirational studies Tarhini *et al* (2015) highlighted the significance of culture and religion on e-banking adoption. These discoveries led to the development of the main research questions, which was to ascertain the factors that are currently affecting e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector. Another research question, what are the most patronised e-banking channel in Nigeria after reviewing the literature on e-banking channels and findings on the most patronised e-banking service was not consistent. While some studies mentioned ATM and Internet banking as the most patronised, some reported ATM, mobile banking, point of sales has the most used e-banking channel in Nigeria. With all these discoveries, I kept writing

my literature review, although, not moving in the right direction, I had to write, rewrite and keep reviewing literature through the suggestions of my supervisor.

Having done the literature review to some extent, I decided to leave the literature review and I moved to the methodology chapter because I kept getting new information for the literature which makes the literature review ongoing.

During the time I was writing my methodology. I knew I am conducting mixed-method research, but, integrating the quantitative and qualitative methods to me at first was extremely challenging for me, this is because many of the articles I used for my research either used the quantitative method or qualitative method for their research but, I add to employed the two methods to add credibility to the research findings on the factors that affect e-banking adoption in the Nigeria banking sector. I had to also employ a mixed-method research approach since I also want to apply the mixed-method to investigate the e-banking channels mostly used by the customers in Nigeria. Eventually, I discovered Creswell (2014) and Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2015) textbook on mixed methods that guided me in incorporating the two methods successfully for the study. Despite, deciding the methodology of the research right from the research proposal phase, discussing he mixed-methods with my research mate was very discouraging due to the complexity, but despite the discouragement to change to only quantitative method, I was able to stand my ground to employ the mixed-method to answer the research questions as expected. I kept working and updating my methodology chapter for four months, while I was also working on the literature review chapter. The literature review was finally completed after writing the background into information into banking in Nigeria which was very challenging as well, as I have to research extensively for the information particularly when I was making the PESTEL analysis of the Nigeria banking environment and the comparative analysis of the e-banking practices of the two banks I used for my thesis.

The most challenging issue in the methodology chapter is how to justify my research strategies and approach especially the philosophical underpinning my choice of pragmatism. At last, I was able to justify my research choices with the feedback and various suggestions received from my Director of Studies (DOS). Another challenge I experience was gaining ethical approval, this took close to three months before it was approved because I was asked to get additional evidence from the two banks I used for my research; Guarantee Trust Bank and First City Monument Bank Nigeria. I started collecting data immediately after I gained ethical approval. I was able to collect the data as I have a copy of my interview guide and survey questionnaire before I gained ethical approval. I conducted a pilot study for both questionnaire

and interview, necessary corrections were made before I went for the main data collection for my research. The researcher travelled to Nigeria in May 2019 for the main interview, face-to-face in the participant's house, eateries or office as they were in two different parts, Lagos and Ogun state, Nigeria. The interview went smoothly due to the interview guide already prepared. The only problem I encountered was travelling between two geographical areas for the interview and conducting the interview at the most convenient time for the respondents is also challenging. Conversely, another challenge I experienced in the interview stage was the difficulty in analysing the interview data because I have never done a qualitative study before. This stage was extremely stressful and difficult for me to write especially using thematic analysis. To combat this problem, I read various textbooks on qualitative studies, watched Youtube video and went for seminars on how to analyse qualitative data. With the help of all these, I was able to analyse my interview data successfully by generating relevant themes through thematic network analysis approach.

During the questionnaire distribution stage, a total of 250 questionnaires was distributed but I realised 176 of the total distributed could be used for the research, as 29.6% of the questionnaire were not appropriately filled as results there were not used for the research. As a result, only 70.4% (176) were used and analysed for the research work through the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS). Analysis of questionnaire was equally challenging and stressful, as I need to sort, group, code and entered the data in the SPSS data editor. After successfully analysing the data in SPSS, then, analysing the data and result in the context for the research question was very difficult, so, I had to analyse the result and report the findings of both the quantitative and qualitative data in phases with the quantitative analysis starting first before there result were compared and summary of key findings from both analysis and development of a revised e-banking adoption model. Thereafter, a discussion of finding in relation to the previous e-banking studies. Next, conclusion and recommendations were provided for the research.

Looking back, I felt great I have learnt and gained knowledge in this research despite the difficulties and challenges I have been through while writing the thesis, I have learnt a great deal from doing my DBA research and I was able to still complete my thesis before time. I have also learnt that researcher should perseverance, this quality and the various feedbacks from my DOS although, can be demotivating sometimes, but overall both gave me the strength to keep moving in the research process which helped and contributed to my research.

8.4 Future Career Goals

I would like to be working as a consultant in any reputable organisations such as PWC, KPMG in Nigeria or oversea. I have registered for jobs with employers via social network site (LinkedIn). Infact, I have applied for an internship with PWC and AECOM through Student Circus, a job search platform for international students. I would also like to be employed in research methodology in the future, as this research experience has helped me gain knowledge and interest in this field. Importantly, I planned to publish articles on E-banking adoption in Nigeria after completing my DBA. I also intend to publish a systematic review of existing e-banking studies in Nigeria. I would like to publish my thesis for the future researcher interested in researching e-banking in developing countries, especially Nigeria.

8.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a reflective account of my DBA journey or experience. The details of the experiences starting from the year one of the DBA programme, which includes taught modules of the DBA have been presented in section 8.2. The experience of the second year of the DBA which explained how the taught modules in year one of the DBA transformed to the research phase in year two and the experiences about the challenges of writing the research and how the researcher overcome the research challenges are provided in section 8.3. Thereafter, the future career goals of the researcher are elaborated by providing what was learnt from doing the DBA and what the researcher intend to do next.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix A

Ethics Form (5690)

New Application Form

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **BEFORE** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Postgraduate

Principal Investigator

Title	First Name	Surname
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text" value="Sherifat"/>	<input type="text" value="Odudu"/>
Email	<input type="text" value="E [REDACTED]"/>	

School

Business and enterprise

Are there any co-applicants

- Yes
 No

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title	First Name	Surname
<input type="text" value="Dr"/>	<input type="text" value="Julia"/>	<input type="text" value="Falon"/>
School	<input type="text" value="Cardiff Metropolitan University"/>	
Email	<input type="text" value="[REDACTED]"/>	

Collaborators

Are there any other collaborators?

- Yes
 No

Project Information

Title of Study

Primary purpose of the study

Original Research

Where will the proposed research take place?

The proposed research will take place in Abuja the capital of Nigeria

How will the costs of the study be met?

The costs of study will be met by the student

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
 No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

The purpose of the study is to critically examine the impact of E-banking adoption on customers' satisfaction in the Nigeria banking sector. Hence, the objectives of the study are:

1. to critically review the literature on e-banking
2. to investigate the factors affecting e-banking adoption
3. to analyse the impact of e-banking adoption on customer satisfaction
4. to examine the factors facilitating/influencing e-banking adoption in Nigeria banking sector
5. to produce a framework for best practice management in e-banking applicable across the Nigerian banking sector.

Statement of the problem

Banking organization are rapidly changing to electronic-based service delivery thus changing the way service are rendered to customers. Nigeria banks has invested heavily on innovative (new) technologies and increasingly deploying various e-banking services as a tool to generate insights about customer behavioural patterns, preferences and to improve customers' satisfaction through convenient banking (Oginni, Omoeyele and Ogunwole 2013); to improve service delivery channel and improve banking customers' experience. Despite Nigeria banks' effort to achieve customer satisfaction through the deployment of electronic banking technologies, the adoption rate of most of the channels are still very low (Yaqub et al., 2013; Asiegbu, Nwakanma and Etus 2015). Factors such as ease of use, security, trust and others affects the adoption rates, therefore this study on E-banking adoption in Nigeria banks and customer satisfaction has emerged as a key determinant for measuring long-term economic performance and competitive success of an organisation (Fomell et. al. 2004). Thus, the study aimed at providing in-depth understanding about the factors influencing Nigeria banks customers' decision to adopt electronic products/services and produce a framework for best practice management in E-banking applicable across the Nigerian banking sector.

Design and methodology of the planned study

To achieve the objective of the research, the research study will employ a mixed methods (qualitative and quantitative approaches) for achieving clearer insights. This method give room for triangulating data sources i.e process of finding convergence of both qualitative and quantitative methods (Creswell, 1998; Jick, 1979). In addition, mixed method is suitable for the research study as it gives rigor and breadth to the research area and provides confirmatory evidences for data obtained. Ultimately, the research study will be descriptive and explanatory at the end.

However, the research work will use cross-sectional survey design which will ask respondents about electronic banking product and services channels. Cross-sectional survey is suitable when a population have large numbers and where it is very difficult to study all the number in the population, thereby using sampling for generalizing and inferring the entire population. Study like Barnes and Vidgen, (2000) used this research design successfully. The use of triangulation approach offers greater validity and reliability than a single methodological approach (Denzin, 1970).

However, the research will adopt a random and purposely sampling technique. The study population shall be drawn from two (2) branches of the 19 Nigeria commercial banks namely; FCMB and GTB in Lagos and Ogun, all have their headquarters in Lagos State, the economic capital of Nigeria. Banks customers and customer service manager will also constitute the population. Two Fifty (250) customers of two randomly selected banks will be use for the study. One hundred and twenty five (125) respondents from each branch including customer service managers of the two branches of Nigeria Commercial Banks in Lagos (commercial capital of Nigeria) and Ogun will constitute the population. Ten (10) semi-structured interviews with customers, five (5) from each bank will also form part of the population for in-depth and holistic knowledge about the research area, clearer picture of vital issues likely to be faced in the research.

Sample size of two hundred and fifty (250) will be targeted. The sample will include retail banking customers between 18 and 64 ages who maintained a regular account with the new generation commercial banks will participate in the study as long as they are adopter of one form of electronic banking or the other.

The study will use primary data to gather data through well-structured questionnaires that will be completed by customers and managers of the banks. The questionnaire will be divided into three sections (A, B and C). Section 'A' will require respondents to indicate their perception on electronic products and services adoption. Section 'B' of the questionnaire will include closed-ended and open-ended questions on various channels of innovative technologies (electronic banking) to achieve a realistic result relating to the research questions and hypotheses. However, five (5) Likert Scale of SA (Strongly Agreed), A (Agreed), SD (Strongly Disagreed), D (Disagreed) and Undecided (U) shall be use for the closed-ended questions. Questions will be systematically formulated based on the research objectives, research questions and hypotheses. Section 'A' will be design to provide demographic data including genders, race, age, marital status, educational background, professions etc of the respondents. Great care will be taking into consideration while designing the questions and instrumentation bias will be avoided while designing the instrument. The questionnaire will be administered to selected individual bank customers through the bank managers.

Semi-structured interviews will also be carried out for knowledge about electronic banking and customer satisfaction. An interpretative approach will be adopted in this regard to identify issues that cannot be discovered using traditional/positivist approach, study like Tahini et. al (2015) has used this method successfully.

Pilot study will be carried out with twelve (12) participants for pretesting the research instrument. Pilot studies are "small-scale version/ trial run perform in preparation for the main study (Polit et al. (2001).

The research will builds upon previous studies like Munirudeen (2007), Ayo, (2010), Oni and Ayo (2010) Tahini et al. (2015), Agwu (2017).

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

Sample Size

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

The intended sample size of 250 respondents is targeted. Experienced researchers will consider a sample size of between 200 and 1000 for a population of 10,000 and more (Sathy, 1999; Aireck and Settle 1985). Since the Nigeria banking customers are more than 10,000, thus target sample size of 250 will be use and the sample size will be a representative of the Nigerian population. The target market for electronic banking is cosmopolitan cities (Lagos and Ogun state), so a sample which is potentially representative of the target population will be use.

However, quantitative methodologies are related with large sample sizes to ensure high degree of accuracy and to ensure findings are true representatives of studied population and unbiased (Saunders et al., 2003; Collis and Hussey, 2003; Hair et al., 2003).

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

The process of data analysis will be inductive emerging from qualitative data of the semi-structured phone interviews. Deductive analysis will be used for research questions to test theories, replicate and generalize the findings. However, Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS) shall be used to quantitatively analyse the data collected for hypotheses testing via Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Scale ranging from -1 to +1 will be use to show the degree of the relationship of the correlation coefficient, the degree of the correlation shall be considered at 0.01 level of significance and null hypothesis (H0) will be tested at 0.5% level of significance.

Content analysis approach as prescribed by Taylo-Powell and Renner (2003) will also be used to analyse qualitative data. However, content validity will be adopted to measure how well the content of the research instrument (questionnaire) measures what it is designed to measures. Cronbach alpha technique shall be used to test the reliability of the instrument i.e whether it is free from random error and will be accepted at above 0.7.

Participant data will be separated from their identifying details, their data will be coded and data will only be published in anonymised form and the results of the research will be published.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
 No

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule

Type	Name	File Name	Date	Version	Size
Default	INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	INTERVIEW QUESTIONS.pdf	28/09/2018 12:00:00 AM	1	10.4 KB

30 September 2018 Modified 1

Reference 8

Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

- Yes
 No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

A letter of introduction will be obtain from my supervisor soliciting for participation in this research. Participants will be recruited through the two selected banks, the two banks have already given their consent to participate. The bank manager will be interviewed and asked to distribute questionnaires.

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
 Adults with learning disabilities
 Adults with a terminal illness
 Adults in emergency situations
 Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
 Adults with dementia
 Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
 Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
 Other
 None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

None

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
 No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

The expected participation in the study is 15 mins for the questionnaire and 20 to 30 mins for the telephone interview

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

- Yes
 No

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

Participation agreement form will be obtain from the study participants that they give informed consent to take part in the study and information like participation is voluntary and that they are free to opt-out of the study at any time without giving reason.

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Type	Name	File Name	Date	Version	Size
Default	Participants information corrected	Participants information corrected.docx	26/09/2018 12:00:00 AM	1	258.2 KB

Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)

Type	Name	File Name	Date	Version	Size
Default	Consent form corrected	Consent form corrected.docx	26/09/2018 12:00:00 AM	1	275.4 KB

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

- Yes
 No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

- Yes
 No

Other ethical considerations

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
 No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
 No

Please provide details of when this debriefing will take place, who will do it and how it will be done

Participants will be debriefed as soon as the research activity has been completed. The principal investigator will send email to all participants after the study is completed to ensure that all participants (those that completed and those that may have stopped mid-way) receive the outcome of the findings.

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
 No

Please provide details

The research needs personal data (telephone no) of participants for interview

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Every effort will be made to ensure that data provided can not be traced to individual bank customers in reports, presentations and other forms of dissemination. All information collected about participants will be kept strictly confidential. Data collected will be stored in personal computer in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies. Data collected may be shared in an anonymised form to allow reuse by the research team and other third parties. These anonymised data will not allow any participants or their banks to be identified or identifiable.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

The researcher and the Director of Studies will have access to collected data. It will be protected by passwords and other relevant security processes.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Type	Name	File Name	Date	Version	Size
Default	FCMB Letter	FCMB Letter.pdf	25/09/2018 12:00:00 AM	1	704.8 KB
Default	GTB letter	GTB letter.pdf	25/09/2018 12:00:00 AM	1	443.9 KB

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by Sherfat Odutolu [REDACTED] on 29/09/2018 08:47

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Julia Fallon [REDACTED] on 30/09/2018 17:33

A1. Ethics Approval Letter

24/10/2018

Dear Sherifat Odutolu,

Your application 5690: An Empirical Investigation of E-Banking Adoption and their Impact on Customers Satisfaction: A case study of the Nigerian Banking Sector , submission 4035, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

A2. Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Research Title: An Empirical Investigation of Factors Affecting Customers Towards E-Banking Adoption in The Nigerian Banking Sector

Principal Investigator: Sherifat Odutolu

Research Ethics Committee Approval No: 5690

Dear Respondents,

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

The purpose of the study: this research project aims to examine the factors influencing customers' decision to adopt electronic banking in Nigeria and provide Nigerian banks with the relevant strategies to achieve customers satisfaction.

Why you have been invited to participate: you have been invited to participate because as a customer of Nigeria commercial bank who uses electronic banking products/services and, or Customer Service Manager who have knowledge about research data. A total of 250 people will participate in the study.

Do you have to take part: it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part, you will be given a copy of this information sheet and be asked to sign a consent form. You are free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen if you take part: the method of data collection for the research is through questionnaire and semi-structured interview. You will be asked to complete a questionnaire which we estimate will take you 15 minutes and interview which we estimate will take you 30 to 45min.

What you have to do: please answer the questions in the questionnaire. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

Possible disadvantages and risks of taking part: participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort.

Benefits of taking part: there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work will have a beneficial impact on banks and policy makers.

If the research study stops earlier than expected: where the research stops earlier than planned and you are affected in one way or the other, we will tell you and explain why.

Taking part in the study will be kept confidential: All the information that we collect about you for the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Any data collected about you in the questionnaire will be stored in personal computer in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies. Data collected may be shared in an anonymised form to allow reuse by the research team and other third parties. These anonymised data will be used for research purposes only.

You will be recorded, and how recorded media is used: your input is only needed for the questionnaire, your consent will be gained for recording the interview and will be use for the research only.

Type of information that will be sought from you and why the collection of this information is relevant for achieving the research project's objectives: the questionnaire will ask you about your opinions and current practices in relation to electronic banking adoption. Your views and experience are just what the project is interested in exploring.

The results of the research project: the result will be use in the DBA thesis and the the results of the research will be published. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

Supervising and funding the research: the study is supervised by Dr Julia Fallon and is self-funded.

Contacts for further information: if you have any concerns about the way in which the study has been conducted, they should contact:

The Chair of the University Research Ethics Committee on businessandenterpriseethics@uws.ac.uk

Dr J. M. Fallon, University of the West of Scotland, UK. Tel: [REDACTED] email: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this research

A3. Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

An Empirical Investigation of Factors Affecting Customers Towards E-Banking Adoption in The Nigerian Banking Sector

Please tick where appropriate.

	Please initial box
1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving reason.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I agree to take part in the above study.	<input type="checkbox"/>

The following statements should be ticked, if appropriate.

If not, please *ignore*.

	Please initial box	
	Yes	No
4. I agree to the interview being audio recorded	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. I agree to the use of anonymised quotes in publications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. I agree that my research data may be used for a further project in anonymous form, but I am able to opt out of this if I wish.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

SHERIFAT AJOKE ODUTOLU
Researcher

Date

Signature

This project is supervised by: DR JULIA FALLON

Researcher's Name and Contact:

Sherifat Ajoke, Odutolu, Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) student, School of Business, University of the West of Scotland London, UK. Tel: [REDACTED] email: [REDACTED]

Appendix B
QUESTIONNAIRE

Table 3.4
Section A

S/N	Questions	SA	A	SD	D	U
<i>Perceived Advantage/ Perceived Usefulness</i>						
1	E-banking make it easier for me to carry out my e-banking transaction					
2	Using E-banking services safe time					
3	I do not see value in using e-banking					
4	E-banking is a convenient banking platform					
5	I may not be able to use traditional banking any longer if I switch to e-banking					
6	More time and efforts are required for necessary information needed to adopt e-banking services.					
7	Adopting the e-banking service and products has really enhance my relationship with the bank					
<i>Complexity of Use/ Perceived Ease of Use</i>						
8	E-banking is more difficult to use					
9	Learning how to use e-banking services are easy for me					
Cost of e-banking adoption						
10	Switching cost for adopting e-banking is too expensive					
11	The hidden charges involved in e-banking services make adoption difficult					
12	Exorbitant transactions charges make me not to adopt e-banking					
Security and Risk						
13	I am afraid to adopt the e-banking services because of lack of security of the system					
14	Lack of trust in the system makes me not to adopt the service					
15	I cannot use the e-banking services because of fraud					
16	Lack of user protection law makes it difficult for me to use e-banking					
17	Unavailable power supply makes me not to adopt e-banking services					
18	E-banking is not consistent with my cultural and religious belief					
Section B: E-banking Adoption Level (Most Patronized Channels)		SA	A	SD	D	U
19	I often use all e-banking channels and it increases my satisfaction					
20	I always use the ATM for my banking transaction everyday					
21	I use the POS everyday					
22	I use EFTs services					
23	I use Internet banking on daily basis					
24	I always use the mobile banking for my banking transaction					

25. Please indicate other reasons for adopting or not adopting e-banking.....

Section C: Demographic Data

- 1. Gender: Male { }
 Female { }
- 2. Age: 16-25 Years { } 26-35 Years{ } 36-45 Years{ }
 46-55 Years { } 56-65 Years Over 66 Years{ }
- 3. Marita Status: Married { } Single { }
 Others { }
- 4. Educational Level: High School/College { } Diploma/HND { }
 First University Degree { } Postgraduate Degree { }
- 5. Occupation: Public Servant { } Self Employed { }
 Professionals { } Others { }
- 6. Income Less than ₦30,000/£60 { } ₦60,000/£120{ }
 Over ₦60,000/£120 { }
- 7. Religion: Islam { } Christianity { }
 Traditional { }
- 8. Culture: Yoruba culture- South { } Hausa-Fulani- North { }
 Igbo Culture- East { } Edo-Benin- South-South { }

RATIONALE FOR QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGNED

Construct	Question	Rationale	Literature Source
<i>Perceived Advantage /Perceived Usefulness (PU)</i>	E-banking is more effective than the manual banking	This question is meant to examine customers' perception regarding their evaluation of e-banking in Nigeria. This question has been validated and used in previous research to test this construct (Moore and Benbasat, 1991).	Davies (1989) and Rogers (1995) claimed that innovation will be accepted if perceived usefulness and benefit over existing one. If this is true in Nigeria, then e-banking should be embraced.
	E-banking is a convenient banking platform	This question is intended to determine customers' perception of the comfort that e-banking claims to afford. Previous research Agwu et. al (2014) has used and validated this construct.	Rogers (1995) postulated that if customers perceive e-banking to be convenient than manual banking that will be added advantaged to be considered for its adoption.
<i>Complexity of Use/ Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)</i>	E-banking is more difficult to use	This question intended to evaluate the Nigerian bank customers perception regarding e-banking usage. Moore and Benbasat, (1991); Agwu (2014) has successfully used this question in their prior research	Going by Rogers (1995) ideology, the perception of bank customers in Nigeria as regards e-banking will enhance the adoption rate.
	E-banking make it more easier for me to carry out my e-banking transaction	This is to examine customers' ability to carry out e-banking transaction themselves. (Ayo & Adeshina, 2010) Agwu, 2014) has previously use this question to test their construct.	Customers' ability to be able to use e-banking more easily will determine the adoption. This is in line with Davies (1989) and Rogers's (2005) ideologies.
	Learning how to use e-banking services are easy for me	This is intended to evaluate the Nigerian banks customers regarding their perception about the learning process of e-banking. Moore and Benbasat, (1991) used this question in a previous research to test this construct	Simple e-banking learning process will determine the overall adoption of e-banking services in Nigeria.
<i>Patronage level</i>	E-banking platforms such as Internet banking, Mobile banking, EFTs, ATM, and POS	The reason for this is to examine the level of customers' e-banking platform usage.	Studies established that e-banking channels are hardly patronise except ATM CBN, 2013
	Adopting e-banking has enhance my relationship with the bank	This is to examine if adopting e-banking has promoted customer relationship management	Madueme (2009) established that Nigeria banks adopt electronic banking to enhance service delivery that transcends to customer satisfaction

Appendix D

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Interview No: _____

Date: _____

Thank you for showing your interest to participate in this research. My name is Sherifat Odutolu. I am a student of University of West of Scotland UK and I am currently conducting a research on the topic “An Empirical Investigation of Factors Affecting Customers Towards E-Banking Adoption in The Nigerian Banking Sector”. I am soliciting your permission to record this interview will be around 30-45 minutes. Please be informed that you are free to discontinue with the interview at any time, please let me know at any time you wish to discontinue the interview. All your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used for better insight of the factors affecting customers towards e-banking adoption in Nigeria. Thank you once more for taking part in the interview.

1) E-banking perceived usefulness/perceived advantage and perceive ease of use/complexity of use			
SN	Question	Rationale	Justification
1.	Do you have easy access to e-banking products and services regularly?	To examine customer's perception regarding e-banking accessibility to e-banking products and services	Davies (1989) and Rogers (1995) claimed that innovation will be accepted if perceived usefulness and benefit over existing one. If this is true in Nigeria, then e-banking should be embraced.
2.	Do you believe e-banking is convenient to use than manual banking?	To determine the customer's perception on the comfort that e-banking claims to offer	Rogers (1995) postulated that if customers perceive e-banking to be convenient than manual banking that will be added advantaged to be considered for its adoption.
3.	Do you agree E-banking makes it easier to carry out banking transactions?	The purpose of this question is to find out if the customers carry out e-banking transactions themselves	Customers' ability to be able to use e-banking more easily will determine the adoption. This is in line with Davies (1989) and Rogers's (2005) ideologies.
4.	Do you belief e-banking is too difficult to use?	This question intends to examine e-banking adoption usage by customers	Going by Rogers (1995) ideology, the perception of bank customers in Nigeria as regards e-banking will enhance the adoption rate.
2) Risk and security			Justification
5.	Do you agree E-banking is more secure than manual banking?	To investigate if customers are aware of risk associated with e-banking activities	Perceived risks are hinderance to electronic banking spread Ayo, Adewoye& Oni (2010)
6.	Do e-banking adoption reduces the possibility of fraudulent transactions in my account	To investigate if customers are aware of bank's effort to solve e-banking fraud	GTBank reiterate benefits of electronic banking channels, declared them safe and secure (ThisDay Newspaper, 2013)
7.	Do you consider security as the major influencing factor for e-banking adoption?	To find out if customer consider security as the major factor hindering e-banking adoption	Security is the most influencing factor for customer adopting of e-banking (Tarhini, et. al. 2015).
(3) Cost implication for adopting -e-banking			Justification
8.	Do you agree that switching to electronic banking products and services are easy?	To find out the modalities in switching or adopting any of the e-banking products and services	Roger (1999) a complex switching process could discourage electronic banking channels.
9.	Do you consider the cost for switching or adopting e-banking products and services to be cheap?	To examine if customer are aware and consider the cost implication for adopting e-banking products and services	Cost and time are reasons underlining e-banking adoption (PIkkarainen, et. al. 2004).
(4) Culture and religion			Justification
10.	Do you belief culture act as determining factor for e-banking adoption?	To investigate if culture is a determinant of e-banking adoption	Culture is a prime factor determining e-banking adoption (Tarhini. et. al. 2015)
11.	Do you agree that religious belief causes resistance to e-banking adoption?	To investigate whether religious belief can influence e-banking adoption.	Religious belief influences the adoption of e-banking product and services in Nigeria (Tarhini. et. al. 2015)

12.	What is your overall opinion about the influences affecting e-banking development?	To ascertain the factors that are affecting the development of e-banking in Nigeria	Adequate policy framework and critical infrastructural facilities are required for e-banking development (Ononuga, <i>et. al.</i> , 2015; Ikpefan <i>et. al.</i> , 2018)
	<p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>		

Appendix E
Bank Approval Letters

E1. GTB Bank

Guaranty Trust Bank plc
RC 152311
Plot A4, Alimos Beach Estate, Ikate, 10830,
Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria.
CPC Tel: 01-4480/41
Branch www.gtbank.com

24/7/2018.

To: Sherifat A, Odutolu
School of Business and Enterprise
University of The West of Scotland
235 Southwark Bridge Rd,
London
SE1 6NP

Dear Sherifat Odutolu,

RESEARCH APPROVAL LETTER

This is to notify you that your request soliciting for permission to conduct your research study "An Empirical Examination of E-Banking Adoption and Their Impacts on Customers' Satisfaction" using Guaranty Trust Bank PLC as one of the case studies has been approved.

I promise that Guaranty Trust Bank PLC support this effort and will provide any assistance needed whatsoever for the success of the research. You can reach me on [REDACTED] for subsequent assistance.

Sincerely,

Olufemi Michael
Operation Manager
Lekki Branch

E2. FCMB

FIRST CITY MONUMENT BANK
A MEMBER OF FCMB GROUP PLC AC 4719

July 24th, 2018.

Sherifat A. Odutolu
School of Business and Enterprise
University of The West of Scotland
235 Southwark Bridge Rd,
London
SE1 6NP

Dear Sherifat Odutolu,

APPROVAL LETTER

We hereby write to notify you that your request seeking us to permit you to conduct your research study in our bank FIRST CITY MONUMENT BANK (FCMB) on the research topic "AN EMPIRICAL EXAMINATION OF E-BANKING ADOPTION & THEIR IMPACTS ON CUSTOMER'S SATISFACTIONS has finally been approved by the management of the bank.

We will give you all the necessary support that is required for the success and completion of this Research work.

Feel free to contact FCMB AKOKA branch for further assistance

Best regards

Aminat Durojaiye

Email [REDACTED]

